

ORISON

innOvative **R**esearch **I**nfrastructure based
on Stratospheric ballo**ON**s

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Abbreviation	Definition
ADS-B	Automatic Dependent Surveillance – Broadcast
AGL	Above Ground Level
AGU	Aerial Guidance Unit
ANSP	Air Navigation Service Provider
ASI	Italian Space Agency
ATC	Air Traffic Control
ATS	Air Traffic Service
BEXUS	Balloon Experiments for University Students
BLAST	Balloon-borne Large Aperture Submillimeter Telescope
CAR	Canadian Aviation Regulations
CFR	Code of Federal Regulations
CFRP	Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic
CICA	Convention on International Civil Aviation
CNES	Centre National d'Études Spatiales
COTS	Commercial Off The Shelf
DLR	German Aerospace Center
EASA	European Aviation Safety Agency
EBEX	E- and B-Experiment
EIRP	Effective Isotropically Radiated Power
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration
FCC	Federal Communications Commission
FIS	Flight Information Center
FP7	7 th Framework Programme
FWHM	Full Width Half Maximum
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HAPS	High Altitude Platform Station
HDD	Hard Disk Drive
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organization

IFR	Instrument Flight Rules
IMT	International Mobile Telecommunication
IP	Impact Point
ITU	International Telecommunications Union
JAXA	Japanese Aerospace Exploration Agency
L/D	Lift to drag ratio
LDB	Long Duration Balloon
LOS	Line of sight
MCI	Multi-Channel Imager
NAS	National Airspace System
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NDB	Non-Directional Beacon
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NOTAM	Notice to Airmen
OBC	On-Board Computer
PSF	Point Spread Function
SBD	Short Burst Data
SERA	Standardized European Rules of the Air
SNSB	Swedish National Space Board
SPMN	Spanish Meteor & Fireball Network
SSR	Secondary Surveillance Radar
SSC	Swedish Space Corporation
SSD	Solid State Device
UHF	Ultra High Frequency
ULDB	Ultra-Long Duration Balloon
VFR	Visual Flight Rules
WFI	Wide-Field Imager
WRC	World Radio Conference

1 INTRODUCTION

The ORISON project aims to provide a flexible multipurpose platform mainly for research in astronomy, but also for research in other fields, using balloon flights to reach the stratosphere. The stratosphere offers excellent observing conditions that are not met from the ground, and which are similar to the conditions obtained from space, but at a considerably reduced cost compared to space missions. Currently, scientific ballooning is mainly carried out in dedicated balloon missions for very specific scientific goals in a specific scientific field, whereas the ORISON idea is to provide an astronomical-observatory-type facility, where several telescopes and several instruments are available for flights and where many different science cases can be addressed in a variety of disciplines. Hence, it would be a balloon-based stratospheric facility analog to a general purpose ground-based astronomical observatory. With the desire for some regularity in flights and the desire for some flexibility to accommodate different science cases comes a wide range of requirements that a generalized balloon platform needs to fulfil. The technical feasibility of such a concept must be analyzed if this observatory idea is to be pursued further. Thus, one of the main goals of this European-funded H2020 INRAFSUPP-2 project is the feasibility analysis of the balloon-observatory concept. Hence the present document is one of the key documents of the project. Based on the conclusions of this report, different courses of action for the possible future realization of the observatory can be taken and will be explored in subsequent reports.

2 SCOPE

The aim of this report is to review all the key aspects of the proposed observatory (based on the technical specifications document of the ORISON project [1], to be able to address many of the goals compiled in the uses and needs report [2]) and address whether there is a general feasibility from the technical and operational points of view. Throughout this process, an eye must be kept on the possible future realization of the project through any of the means that the H2020 funding scheme allows, mainly through public procurement strategies. The public procurement schemes in the H2020 program require that the technologies employed are more or less mature so that suppliers in the market can provide the needed components, at least to a high degree. In a previous document (State of the Art and Market Offer Report [3]) this has been explored, and specifically, the document contains an analysis of commercially available parts and / or suppliers for subsystems and elements of the balloon platform that the ORISON study considers more or less critical.

The current document aims at providing a feasibility analysis of a platform that would meet the requirements keeping in mind what is technologically available on the market and mature enough in terms of reliability. Hence, this document is organized in three main chapters: a chapter on pure technical feasibility (with the main focus on the payload aspects), a chapter on operational feasibility and a third chapter (which is somewhat related to the operational feasibility) on the legal feasibility of different aspects that are key in the operations of balloons in different countries.

3 TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY

For a successful operation of the ORISON platform, technical requirements formulated in the technical and functional report [1] have to be met. Challenges and possible solutions concerning the overall technical feasibility are identified and discussed throughout this chapter.

3.1 STRATOSPHERIC CONDITIONS

All system components have to be able to withstand the environmental conditions at flight altitude and also the conditions during ascend and descend. Furthermore, the science instruments are supposed to operate at stratospheric conditions.

The coldest layer in the troposphere is passed during ascend and descent between 12 and 22 km, where temperatures can drop below -70°C . Water may condense or freeze on the gondola. During daytime, large temperature differences occur between shaded areas and areas directly exposed to the sun [4].

According to the model of the international standard atmosphere, temperatures at 30 km altitude are about -46.6°C , while the pressure is at about 1.2 mbar [5].

Component temperatures are influenced by a variety of the component's properties, such as surface geometry, emission coefficients and heat sources e.g. electronics, as well as environmental conditions, e.g. incoming radiation from the earth and the sun, air density and wind. Passive or active thermal control systems might be necessary for some components to operate within the specified temperature range.

Furthermore, we review some of the dominant conditions relevant to observational quality, particularly in order to estimate suitable flight altitudes. We particularly examine uncorrected spatial resolution capacity, scintillation noise, and the effect of aerosol on contrast and spatial resolution.

3.1.1 Aerosol

In addition to atmospheric turbulence, atmospheric scattering of light can have a negative effect on spatial resolution, but also on contrast of astronomical observations. The dominant source for relevant scattering in the atmosphere are aerosols.

While this topic has been discussed in more detail in [2], figure 3-1 should serve to recall the existence of the Junge layer with increased aerosol density in between 15 and 25 km. As the estimates in [2] suggest, at low elevation angles the scattering caused by these particles can degrade the PSF width of an observatory at 20 km altitude in the order of the desired spatial resolution of ORISON. For observational flexibility, it would thus be desirable to fly above the Junge layer.

Figure 3-1: Aerosol density profile according to the Elterman model. Data from [6].

3.1.2 Scintillation Noise

Scintillation noise degrades the photometric accuracy of an observation, e.g. of light curve measurements of solar system bodies or exoplanet transits.

Since scintillation noise is a function of not only atmospheric properties, but also of exposure time and telescope aperture, we estimated the scintillation noise for different exposure times of a telescope with 0.5 m aperture at different altitudes.

Figure 3-2 and figure 3-3 show these estimates for 60 s and 1 s exposure time. The plots show that in both cases, there is still a considerable reduction of scintillation noise in between 20 and 30 km altitude of around one order of magnitude, while the improvement between 30 and 40 km is only marginal.

From the perspective of photometric accuracy, it is thus desirable to observe from 30 km or higher.

Figure 3-2: Expected scintillation noise for a 0.5 m telescope and 60 s exposure time. Wind data used for modeling is taken from SPARC data (average values for 1992 to 1997) for 40 deg N latitude and average values for April. The month of April provides the highest scintillation noise values at high altitudes.

Figure 3-3: Expected scintillation noise for a 0.5 m telescope and 1 s exposure time.

3.1.3 Fried Parameter

Atmospheric turbulence severely degrades the quality of optical observations by broadening the image of point sources (the point spread function, PSF). This leads to a limitation in the achievable spatial resolution, independent of the telescope's size, and also to a severe degradation of the telescope's sensitivity due to the image's spread over a larger detector area. While most turbulence occurs at low altitudes, turbulence still exists between 20 and 30 km altitude on scales that can have a noticeable effect, particularly if the line of sight is not very close to the zenith.

Figure 3-4 to figure 3-7 thus show the derived Fried parameter r_0 for different altitudes, wavelengths, and zenith angles; r_0 thereby can be regarded as the maximum telescope aperture diameter for which observations close to the diffraction limit can be practically achieved (not accounting for lucky imaging).

A close look at these data shows that for observations at wavelengths above 300 nm, the resolution of long-exposure images taken with a 0.5 m aperture telescope is primarily diffraction limited above 18 km already, if the zenith angle is 60 deg or less.

On the other hand, this means that for observations in the far and mid UV it can be worthwhile to observe from altitudes higher than 20 km in order to avoid negative effects on the imaging resolution and signal spread even for telescopes of 0.5 or 1 m aperture. At longer wavelengths, this advantage is lost since the diffraction limit of small telescopes becomes as large as or larger than the seeing for ground-based telescopes. The same advantage still can apply for observations at longer wavelengths, however, if they require observations at large zenith angles. Examples can be observations with very long exposure times or observations for which the same target at low declinations has to be observed continuously for several hours (such as certain exoplanet transits).

Figure 3-4: Fried parameter at 1000 nm following the CLEAR I turbulence model.

Figure 3-5: Fried parameter at 300 nm following the CLEAR I turbulence model.

Figure 3-6: Fried parameter at 500 nm following the CLEAR I turbulence model.

Figure 3-7: Fried parameter at 550 nm following the CLEAR I turbulence model.

3.2 BALLOON SYSTEM CONFIGURATIONS

3.2.1 Payload Protection

Mostly undamaged and reliable recovery of the balloon gondola and payload is fundamental for the ORISON operations concept, aiming at repeated flights of the same hardware with short turnaround times between landing and the subsequent flight.

3.2.1.1 Separation from the Balloon

Since there typically are no means of manipulating the descent flight path of the payload after separation from the balloon, the time of separation has to be chosen well under the careful consideration of descent speed and up-to-date meteorological conditions to ensure landing in a safe area, preferably without obstacles that could damage the payload during landing. Safe landing thus depends to a large degree on the pilot's ability and his/her knowledge of the landing area, the meteorological conditions, and their influence on the separated flight train.

In conjunction with separation, the balloon is typically deliberately destroyed to avoid the abandoned balloon continue its flight and fall to the ground in an unforeseen location (the balloon envelope of large balloons has a mass of several 100 kg^a). For this purpose, typically a strong tearing tape is attached to the balloon envelope which is attached to the top of the parachute and pulled along with the parachute's separation from the balloon.

3.2.1.2 Descent on a Parachute

To avoid unnecessary high loads and to minimize risk, the descent parachute is usually installed unpacked, in an extended position, along the suspension system. This layout allows immediate and smooth deployment of the parachute after separation from the balloon. Until the parachute canopy has opened, an inevitable short period of freefall occurs, leading to a shock at deployment of the parachute. Given the time of freefall t_f (typically 3 to 5 s [7]), the parachute drag coefficient C_{D_p} , the parachute's effective surface area A_p , and the system mass (payload, flight train, including parachute mass) m_p , the maximum acceleration at parachute deployment can be estimated to (based on [7]):

$$\frac{1}{g} \frac{dv}{dt} = 1 - g \rho_a t_f^2 \frac{C_{D_p} A_p}{2m_p}$$

where g is the gravitational acceleration and ρ_a is the atmospheric density at deployment altitude.

Figure 3-8: Flight train with cutter to separate the balloon (1), circular parachute (2), and cutter to separate the parachute from the gondola (3).

^a For example, 100 kg for a comparably small 12,000 m³ balloon.

Typical accelerations at parachute deployment thus vary from 1 g or less at 30 km to 3 to 4 g at around 20 km deployment altitude in vertical direction, with additional uncontrolled tumbling and/or swinging of the flight train and associated horizontal loads [7, 8].

3.2.1.3 Landing

Landing typically occurs on a non-steered, either round or cross-shaped, parachute. Typical vertical landing velocities range between 3 and 10 m/s [7, 8, 9]. Due to the non-steerable nature of typical parachutes, horizontal velocities induced by wind cannot be compensated, so that horizontal velocities between 5 and 20 m/s need to be expected [8]. Equally, due to the non-steerable nature of the landing, damaging conditions in the landing zone cannot be avoided with high reliability, such as obstacles on the ground, trees, or landings in water. Consequently, landing loads as high as 35 g have been witnessed [9]:

In order to avoid damage to the payload upon landing, payload gondolas are usually equipped with crush-pads made of shock-absorbing material. These pads are typically lightweight honeycomb structures made from corrugated cardboard [7] and installed on the bottom of the gondola (see also Figure 3-9). Additional pads can be installed on the side of larger gondolas to avoid damage in case the gondola tips over. For details on the sizing of crush pads, see [4]. Alternative materials for the crush pads are aluminum honeycomb (such as used on the STRATCOM-VIII mission, primarily yielding the advantage of no outgassing that could affect in-situ measurements) [10] or balsa wood, as used on the Ranger 3 to 5 lunar probes. As an alternative to these classic crush pads, aluminum crash rings have been used (such as on the EUSO Balloon for ground landing) or any deformable and expendable part of the gondola structure can be used (such as on the EUSO Balloon for water landing) [11]. Instead of employing single-use shock absorbers, also reusable systems with non-permanent deformation of the shock absorbers can be employed. While these yield the promise of less design and assembly work over repeated flights, they so far have been used only infrequently and with frequent failure to either properly protect the payload or to survive the impact themselves [4].

Yet another option would be to use deflating airbags, which could simultaneously serve as flotation devices in case of water landing, as it has also been proposed for the NASA Gondola for High Altitude Planetary Science [12].

In case of landing in relatively open terrain, there is a risk of the parachute being picked up by horizontal winds and dragging the gondola along the ground.^b To avoid such events, and the associated damage, the parachute can be separated from the gondola using an additional cutter. Alternatively, the parachute canopy can be deflated by cutting part of the riser [7].

Despite all the previously mentioned precautions, landings on a non-steered parachute bear significant risk of damage to the payload gondola. An additional obstacle is a likely landing in a very remote location. Recovering the payload gondola is often a challenging

^b As happened to the BLAST gondola in 2007, which was dragged over the Antarctic ice for about 200 km, almost completely destroying the gondola and scientific payload.

task and requires special logistical solutions causing recovery costs up to the order of the costs for launching the mission.

The risk of remote landings and damage upon landing can be mitigated to a certain degree by employing guided parafoils instead of non-steered parachutes. Such parafoils are already in use for military and humanitarian airdrop applications and are also provided by European companies. Under the FP6 project FASTWing CL [13] a European consortium built and flew a steerable guided parafoil for payloads up to 6,000 kg, employing a two-step system with a stabilization parachute to decelerate the flight train to parafoil deployment velocity. The concept was further explored as an application for small aircraft under the FP7-funded PARAPLANE project with participation of the European high-altitude ballooning company zero2infinty [14]. Such an approach will likely be also necessary for a balloon gondola flying very high. The U.S.-based company World View, in cooperation with the Canadian Precision Aerial Delivery products company MMIST^c, has furthermore demonstrated the adaptability of this technology for lower-flying balloon payloads from 30 km altitude, with highly accurate flights to the landing zone (in up to 50 km horizontal distance from the cut-off point, depending on wind conditions, to a ca. 50 m radius landing spot) and structural landing loads on the payload considerably lower than the structural loads during parachute opening [15].

Table 3-1: Typical structural loads during balloon missions.

Event	Type of load	Size of load
Transport prior campaign	Shock, undefined vibrations	
Transport on launch pad	Undefined vibrations	
Launch	Shock	Typically: < 0.5 g [8, 4] Worst case: < 2 g [8, 4]
Parachute deployment	Shock, horizontal & centrifugal forces	1 to 5 g vertical [8, 4]
Landing	Shock	Ca. 7-10 g vertical, 35 g observed [9]
Recovery/transport back	Undefined vibrations, shocks	Up to 5-7 g [4]

^c <http://mmist.ca/>

3.3 PAYLOAD

3.3.1 Payload Configuration

Figure 3-9: Arrangement of gondola components.

GPS antenna (1), Antenna boom (2), Receiver (3), Pivot (4), Satellite antenna (5), Elevation torque motor (6), Rotary encoder (7), Gyro sensors (8), Star tracker (9), Battery pack (10), Crush pad (11), LOS antenna (12), Add-on instrument (13), Computer & electronics (14), Telescope (15), Frame (16), Reaction wheel (17)

The balloon-system's payload includes the gondola-frame, telescope, science instruments, electronics, sensors and actuators, batteries and further components that have to be carried during the mission. Figure 3-9 shows a sketch of the ORISON Gondola and the main components as well as a suggestion of what the gondola frame might look like and how the components can be arranged. Considering the size of the telescope including free space for a sufficient range in elevation and the volume of other main system components, the gondola's dimensions are expected to be around 2 m in height, 1.4 m in depth and 1.2 m in width (2.8 m including the antenna boom) according to the sketch above.

As suggested in the technical and functional report [1], small scientific payloads (add-on instruments, (13)) can be carried alongside the main telescope and the science instrument. Placing them at the bottom segment as shown above enables visual access to the ground and lowers the vertical position of the gondola's center of mass, which may prove beneficial for landing. However, this location could also be used for the batteries and electronics, therefore removing the additional payloads from the overall mission concept yields a more compact and less complex configuration without any drawbacks for the main science mission and should therefore be considered carefully especially with regard to minimizing costs.

The location of the sensors is crucial to achieve the very demanding pointing requirements. The gyro-sensors should be placed as close as possible to the telescope's center of mass in order to measure the rigid-body behaviour. As deformations in the mechanical structure could cause pointing deviations exceeding the required limits, additional sensors, such as accelerometers, might be necessary to measure these effects. A flexible body compensation system using these sensors as input could be implemented in the controller. Such a system is used for the SOFIA telescope [16].

Motors for the reaction wheel and the pivot rotate the gondola in azimuthal direction. Torque motors between gondola and telescope change the elevation angle. Using two elevation motors (one at each side) might be beneficial, as that would improve symmetry and might reduce deformations of the telescope due to torsion. This design is less complex compared to a system using gimballed frames (see e.g. WASP [17]).

For best sight, antennas for satellite communication (i.e. GPS, Iridium SBD service) are usually mounted on top of the gondola on a so-called antenna boom. The antenna boom allows for space between each of the antennas to reduce interference and to enhance attitude determination by the differential GPS (for details, see [3]). For line-of-sight communication with a ground station, the antennas usually hang below the gondola [18].

3.3.2 Attitude Control

For high-resolution images and long exposure times, a stable platform with minimal vibration is necessary. The projected goal of ORISON is the sampling of the diffraction limited point spread function. This leads to the challenging requirement of 0.1 arcsec rms image stability as stated in the ORISON technical and functional report in the requirements RT8-10 [1]. The coarse pointing shall be between 1-10 arcsec rms as stated in RT2 [1]. This is definitely a challenge on a moving platform that causes disturbances in terms of structural deformation and vibrations. Other airborne platforms, e.g. SOFIA, aim for high image quality to achieve its scientific goals, translating in a pointing requirement of 0.4 arcsec rms image stability, not yet reached and still above the ORISON goals. The overall excitation level on a balloon-borne telescope at cruise altitude (>20 km) is considerably lower than on a plane like SOFIA, however wind gusts and pendulum motion of the gondola could pose possible challenges [19, 20].

Different balloon missions have already shown that precise pointing is possible. The SUNRISE mission mostly managed pointing stability of less than 0.04" rms over a rather long time window. This is achieved by the combination of a coarse pointing system with a fine pointing system. The coarse pointing is realized with linear motors for elevation control and a pivot motor and reaction wheel for azimuthal control, which yields a 7.5 arcsec rms pointing precision. The fine pointing mechanism is made of a movable

tip-tilt mirror in the telescope's light path [19]. However, during operation it turned out that this accuracy was only achieved under optimal weather conditions. Wind gusts occurred frequently, which were strong enough to reduce the pointing performance, so that the longest gondola pointing within the required capture range of the image stabilization system was 45 min during their test flight in 2015 [21]. Notably, the sun is a very specific bright source for tracking and pointing, which is usually not the case other than in solar astronomy. Other astronomical balloons aim at a pointing level of several arcsecs or arcmins, e.g. BLAST (Balloon-borne Large Aperture Submillimeter Telescope) [22] or SPIDER [20], a balloon-borne polarimeter.

For ORISON, a two-staged system similar to the one used on SUNRISE will be necessary to meet the tough pointing requirements. The coarse pointing system includes the motors for elevation control and the motors at the pivot of the suspension line and the reaction wheel. A tip-tilt mirror in the optical light path (fine pointing) will further reduce the remaining image jitter. The star tracker and gyroscopes can be used for attitude determination for both fine and coarse pointing. During times, when precise pointing is not required or for initial pointing acquisition ("lost-in-space"), a basic-orientation system can be implemented using the combination of the coarse pointing motors with the differential GPS, which provides lower precision but higher range.

3.3.2.1 External Excitation

In order to achieve high-accuracy pointing, the attitude controller needs to be designed according to external excitations and the resulting behavior of the balloon-system (plant). Wind is one of the main causes for motion of the gondola resulting in oscillations of different frequency. Typical modes of a balloon system include a very low frequency mode with a period, where the whole balloon system acts like a pendulum and a higher but still low frequency mode, which is caused by the gondola rotating around its suspension point. Experiments were conducted by P. Bernasconi to measure these effects. Periods of 20 – 28 s for the first mode and periods of 2s and 2arcmin amplitude for the latter were measured [23]. These motions cause deviations in azimuth as a function of the telescope's elevation. Additionally, oscillations with 1s and 8s periods were measured.

During flights of the EBEX balloon, an azimuthal motion due to torsion of the flight train with a period of about 80s was measured [24].

Additional to the low-frequency modes of the balloon-system, eigenmodes of the gondola structure have to be considered. These are largely influenced by frame design.

3.3.2.2 Control Architecture

Due to a limited torque and the telescopes moment of inertia, the bandwidth of the torque motors is limited. A bandwidth of about 8 Hz for the elevation control loop (as for the fine-drive controller at the airborne observatory SOFIA [16]) should be sufficient to suppress the low frequency modes mentioned above. However, for azimuthal control, the bandwidth is probably smaller, due to the large mass and moment of inertia of the gondola [23]. In order to achieve high accuracy, the remaining higher frequency disturbances, especially for the eigenmodes of the frame, can be removed by a tip-tilt mirror in the telescope's optics path as implemented in the control architecture of

SuperBIT, where the tip-tilt mirror reduces disturbances of up to 45Hz to 0.02 arcseconds RMS [25].

A possible scheme for the control architecture is sketched in Figure 3-10.

Figure 3-10: ORISON control architecture.

The sketch shows a cascaded controller design: The rate loop includes the rate controller C_R which computes the torque commands for the motors based on the deviation between commanded rate and measured rate. The rate command is provided by the attitude controller C_A . The difference between commanded attitude (w) and measured attitude is input for the attitude controller. Furthermore, the attitude controller forwards the high-frequency deviations, which exceed the motors' bandwidth, to the tip-tilt mirror.

Both controllers try to minimize the input quantities (i.e. the deviation between desired value and actual value). The actual values are measured by the gyro-sensors and the star tracker. The gyro-sensors are able to measure angular rates and attitude can be obtained by integration. However, drift occurs and introduces a measurement error which increases with time. The star tracker can produce accurate measurements of the attitude, but is usually restricted to low update rates [3]. Using a sensor-fusion algorithm, the information from both sensors can be combined to achieve a drift-corrected attitude measurement signal with high update frequencies. One possible algorithm for sensor fusion which is commonly used is the so-called Kalman Filter.

In addition to the above described high-accuracy pointing control system, a coarse pointing system can be implemented, which can be used if orientation is lost, for periods where fine-pointing is not necessary or for initial orientation. For coarse pointing, attitude information provided by the differential GPS receiver can be used.

For the presented control architecture, a custom design for the whole pointing system will be necessary as currently off-the-shelf components are unlikely sufficient to meet the requirements mentioned above. Expensive sensors and development time will be inevitable, especially when the controller has to be optimized for image stabilization instead of acquisition.

3.3.3 Power

Power is one of the most critical aspects of a balloon mission. A good power-budget estimation is required for dimensioning the batteries. Appropriate power generation and storage equipment suitable to the mission profile have to be selected.

3.3.3.1 Batteries

Primary batteries are most attractive for short-term missions due to their two to three times higher specific energy, simplicity in system design, and general robustness against vibrations and shock. In comparison to systems that employ rechargeable secondary batteries and solar cells, primary batteries are mostly superior in terms of system mass when considering the power needs of missions with a short duration. At a given mass of a power supply system, the weight savings that result from omitting solar cells and all other hardware related to cell recharge allow implementation of a higher primary cell mass than it would be possible for secondary cells, increasing the energy density (W/kg) of the power supply system even further. It should also be considered that the conditioning losses of secondary cell based systems (e.g. multiple voltage conversions, power distribution etc.) are also generally higher due to their higher complexity, reducing their efficiency compared to primary cell based power supplies.

The coarse pointing system of a balloon gondola is generally used for pointing the payload. It might therefore be necessary to cover the gondola with enough solar cells in all directions to ensure that enough power is generated at all times of a mission, independent of gondola alignment, to avoid battery recharge periods that need to prioritize solar cell pointing over payload pointing. However, an independent solar cell alignment appears prohibitive considering the total system weight.

A decision which energy source shall be used also depends on the mission profile and length (e.g. flights at high latitudes during polar night or day). Another aspect is reusability; for multiple missions with the same balloon platform, solar panels might become more cost effective. Certain mission critical subsystems (i.e. powering systems that initiate decent or parachute unfolding, or powering a beacon after landing for recovery) might be designed to be powered with primary cells to mitigate risks.

Two possible scenarios have been considered. The first option is to mount the batteries without thermal insulation, which exposes them directly to ambient temperature. The minimal occurring ambient temperature will be around -56.5°C in the tropopause (International Standard Atmosphere). At the target flight altitude of about 30 km, the ambient temperature will rise to about -46.5°C . The expected cell temperature will be somewhat higher than ambient due to thermal dissipation, which depends on the battery's discharge rate. Given the very low pressure and density of the atmosphere at flight altitude, energy transport is also mostly through radiation, with little to no convection. As cell capacity depends heavily on temperature, thermal conditions have to be calculated / modelled based on expected load and individual cell discharge to see if the batteries' self-heating would be sufficient to keep them at acceptable temperatures.

The second option is to protect the battery with a thermal insulation, as it has been done for the secondary cells of BLAST [22]. The battery temperatures during three flights in 2003, 2005 and 2006 have been published. The minimal battery temperature during the test flight in 2006 was about -6°C . The typical temperature range of the batteries during nominal operations was between $+10^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $+21^{\circ}\text{C}$ during the three BLAST flights.

Due to the significant decrease of battery capacity with decreasing temperature, thermal insulation of the batteries seems to be favourable to make sure that the battery delivers sufficient power at all times and for the expected duration of the mission.

Due to their multiple advantages, lithium batteries have been further investigated as possible primary batteries for ORISON.

According to [1], primary batteries should be used at least for the design phase. The considered observation time per flight is at least 10 h. On this account, it would be favourable that the battery shows at least a minimum discharge rate of C/10 (total discharge in 10 h).

Lithium batteries are classified into soluble-cathode, solid-cathode and solid-electrolyte cells. Solid-electrolyte cells are excluded from the following consideration due to their low discharge rates. Table 7-2 in the State-of-the-Art-and-Market-Report [26] displays different primary lithium batteries with the ability of high discharge rates.

According to their characteristics, a Li/SOCl₂ (lithium / thionyl chloride) primary battery appears most advantageous due to its high specific energy as well as high voltage. Additionally, it shows a good low temperature performance. Li/SO₂Cl₂ is similar to Li/SOCl₂ and offers inherently greater safety as well as a higher discharge rate capability. On the other hand, its cell voltage is sensitive to temperature variations and offers a lower discharge rate capability at low temperatures. Li/SOCl₂ systems are currently considered to be the better option due to the temperature sensitivity of Li/SO₂Cl₂ systems.

The ORISON platform could use secondary batteries as an energy storage in combination with solar panels. As an independent energy source, secondary batteries are not able to compete with primary batteries due to their specific energy values, which is lower by a factor of two to three.

Ni/Cd batteries stand out due to a long cycle life, their reliability and their resistance to electrical and physical abuse. On the downside, they exhibit a low specific energy similar to lead-acid systems, but at a higher cost. In addition, Ni/Cd batteries suffer from the so called “memory effect”.

Zn/MnO₂ shows a higher specific energy but exhibits only a very limited cycle life. Therefore, it is not considered further.

Ni/MH systems show higher specific energy values in comparison to lead-acid and Ni/Cd. In addition, they exhibit a long cycle life and a good high-rate capability. On the other side, Ni/MH is more expensive than lead-acid, shows a decreased performance at low temperatures and must be charged at medium temperatures. That a Ni/MH battery could be a possible choice for the ORISON balloon is demonstrated by its usage on BLAST [22].

Ni/Zn systems show similar properties like Ni/MH systems. The specific energy of Ni/Zn systems are a little lower than for Ni/MH systems, but a higher cell voltage is possible. In addition, these batteries exhibit an excellent high-rate discharge capability and are abuse tolerant. Ni/Zn is capable of replacing Ni/Cd and Ni/MH in most high volume applications in the future. The main drawback of Ni/Zn is that it shows a gradual loss in

capacity after cycling. The end of life capacity only reaches about 60-80% of the initial value.

Lithium Ion systems show the best performance of all state-of-the-art secondary batteries. They exhibit the highest cell voltage as well as the highest specific energy of all secondary systems. Additionally, they are characterized by a long cycle life, rapid charge capability, low self-discharge rate, no memory effect and a high coulombic and energy efficiency. Decreasing costs in the past few years strengthen their top position amongst all secondary systems further. The drawback to lithium ion systems are the moderate initial cost and that they might become unsafe if rapidly charged at low temperatures ($<0^{\circ}\text{C}$). Further, they have no protection from overcharge, over discharge or over temperature conditions. Therefore, protective circuitry and mechanical disconnect devices are needed as safeguard systems.

In summary, four secondary battery systems are promising candidates for a long-term ORISON mission. These are lead-acid, Ni/MH, Ni/Zn and Lithium ion batteries. Given the current state of technology, Ni/Cd can be replaced by the other technologies and is therefore excluded from further consideration. Ni/MH batteries will be used for a mass budget estimation (below) due to their high energy density and successful application on other stratospheric balloons.

3.3.3.2 Solar Panels

A price for a launch of a balloon-borne platform is only a fraction of the costs of a rocket launch. Thus, it is expected that silicon solar panels offer a better cost effectiveness than gallium arsenide. Other balloon-borne telescopes like SPIDER [20] also use silicon solar panels. Additionally, the panels flown on SPIDER did not have a special space certification. It is expected that no special space certified solar panels are required for flight on ORISON.

3.3.3.3 Power Budget Estimation

To get an estimate of the power consumption, the power consumption of the subcomponents is estimated and added up (see Table 3-2). The first given value is the power consumption during observation mode, while an estimation for the power consumption during sleep mode (i.e. no observation is carried out) is noted in parenthesis, if applicable. Details are given below.

Losses for power distribution and conditioning have to be considered. Conditioning losses occur when transforming the battery voltage output to the required input for the consumers (i.e. from a high voltage to a lower voltage). The distribution efficiency takes losses in cables into account.

Table 3-2: Power budget estimation.

Power consumption [W]	Orison Heavy	Orison Light	Orison Infinity
Science instrument	150 (0)	50 (0)	50 (0)
Sensors	28	28	28
GNSS receiver	10	10	10
Gyro sensor	3x 2	3x 2	3x 2
Rotary encoder	2x 1	2x 1	2x 1
Star tracker	10	10	10
Actuators	121 (18)	121 (18)	121 (18)
Pivot motor	37 (6)	37 (6)	37 (6)
Elevation	37 (6)	37 (6)	37 (6)
Reaction wheel motor	37 (6)	37 (6)	37 (6)
Fine-pointing	10 (0)	10 (0)	10 (0)
Electronics	135	85	135
Main computer	100	70	100
Data storage	10	5	10
Other electronics (e.g. BUS system)	25	10	25
Communication	22	2	22
S-Band transceiver	20	-	20
Iridium SBD transceiver + antenna	2	2	2
Safety Systems	13	13	13
Strobe lights	5	5	5
ATCRB transponder	2x 4	2x 4	2x 4
Add-on instruments	20 (0)	-	20 (0)
Power consumption	489 (216)	309 (156)	389 (131)
Conditioning efficiency	0.8	0.8	0.7
Distribution efficiency	0.95	0.95	0.95
Safety margin	1.3	1.3	1.3
Required power	837 (369)	512 (250)	761 (256)

Three different scenarios are discussed:

- The *Orison Heavy* scenario represents a system working according to all of the functional requirements and is equipped with hardware for a 20 h observation time.
- The *Orison Light* scenario is used for an estimation for a pared-down mission design and 10 h of observation time. It represents the lowest weight limit which might be achievable for the ORISON mission.
- The *Orison Infinity* case provides estimates for a multiple-day mission (85 h observation time). Some of the values and quantities, which are presented below, are only very rough estimations based on comparisons to similar balloon projects or deduced from basic physical laws. In some cases, they are simply derived from common sense.

Depending on the mission duration, the required battery capacity can be estimated. For *Orison Heavy* and *Orison Light*, a 4 h period of sleep mode is assumed for ascend and descend. During this period, no science data is taken and power consumption can be reduced. For *Orison Infinity*, longer sleep mode durations are considered. The sleep mode can be activated during daylight.

Table 3-3: Energy budget estimation.

	Orison Heavy	Orison Light	Orison Infinity
Required power during observation [W]	837	512	761
Required power during sleep mode [W]	369	250	256
Observation length [h]	20	10	85
Flight duration without observation (sleep mode) [h]	4	4	85
Total required energy [kWh]	18.2	6.1	86.5

Several factors have to be considered for estimating the motors' power consumption. Additional to the mechanical work performed by each motor, resistive power losses have to be taken into account. Resistive power losses are characterized by the motor constant K_M and are calculated according to equation (3.1). Typical values for direct drive torque motors vary between 0.7 and 2 [3]. The required power P (mechanical P_M and resistive losses P_R) depends on the Torque T exerted by the respective motor and its variation in time.

$$P = P_R + P_M \quad (3.1)$$

$$P_R = \left(\frac{T}{K_M}\right)^2 \quad (3.2)$$

Mechanical energy for a rotary motion is the product of Torque T and angular velocity ω (3.2):

$$P_M = T \cdot \omega \quad (3.3)$$

For the variation of torque with respect to time, we assume a sinusoidal motion at the highest frequency the motor can handle: A typical bandwidth for pointing tasks is about 5-10 Hz (e.g. the SOFIA Telescope's Fine-Drive has a bandwidth of 3-6 Hz). Based on this excitation model of the torque motors, a first estimation can be obtained:

$$\varphi(t) = \hat{\varphi} \sin(\omega t) \quad (3.4)$$

$$\ddot{\varphi}(t) = -\omega^2 \hat{\varphi} \sin(\omega t) \quad (3.5)$$

$$T(t) = I \cdot \ddot{\varphi}(t) = -I \cdot \omega^2 \hat{\varphi} \sin(\omega t) \quad (3.6)$$

$$P(t) = |I \cdot \omega^3 \hat{\varphi} \sin(\omega t)| + \left(\frac{I \cdot \omega^2 \hat{\varphi} \sin(\omega t)}{K_M} \right)^2 \quad (3.7)$$

$$\bar{P} = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\pi I \cdot \omega^3 \hat{\varphi} \sin(t) dt + \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \left(\frac{I \cdot \omega^2 \hat{\varphi} \sin(t)}{K_M} \right)^2 dt \quad (3.8)$$

$$\bar{P} = \frac{2}{\pi} I \cdot \omega^3 \hat{\varphi} + \frac{I^2 \omega^4 \hat{\varphi}^2}{2 K_M^2} \quad (3.9)$$

$\varphi(t)$ = angular deviation

I = moment of inertia

$\hat{\varphi}$ = amplitude

T = torque

K_M = motor constant

It has to be noted that this model does not include the actual excitations which occur during flight. Excitations might occur at different intensities and different frequencies, which can result in a different power consumption. Losses due to mechanical friction are estimated to be 5% (R) of the mechanical work. Additionally, even if no external excitation occurred, a constant static torque due to the telescope being not exactly balanced has to be compensated by the motors. No mechanical work is performed but resistive losses occur. This value is listed in Table 3-4 as "static resistive loss".

Table 3-4 shows the power estimation for the elevation motor:

Table 3-4: Motor power budget.

Quantity	Symbol	Unit	Value	Comment
Telescope's moment of inertia	I	[kgm ²]	25	
Motor constant	K_M	[-]	1	
Excitation frequency	ω	[rad s ⁻¹]	50.3	$2\pi \cdot 8Hz$
Amplitude	$\hat{\phi}$	[arcsec]	2	(For coarse pointing requirement of 1 – 10 arcsec [1])
Friction ratio	R	[%]	5	
Static torque	T_S	[Nm]	2	
Mechanical work	P_M	[W]	19.6	
Friction loss	P_F	[W]	1.0	
Resistive loss	P_R	[W]	0.2	
Static resistive loss	P_{RS}	[W]	4	
Safety margin	-	[-]	1.5	
Energy consumption	p	[W]	37.2	

For the other motors, the power consumption is expected to have the same order of magnitude. When not in observation mode, pointing might be unnecessary. For this case, the power consumption is reduced to the energy required for generating a static torque.

For *Orison Infinity*, solar cells provide the necessary power, as the required amount of energy exceeds a reasonable value for using only batteries. For these calculations, a sleep period is considered, which can be enabled during daytime, when observations are impaired by the sun. The sleep period allows the solar cells to be pointed directly to the sun, which reduces the required panel area. During daylight, the solar cells have to harvest enough energy to fill up the batteries for one day of operation. Chosen parameters for the calculation are listed in Table 3-5.

Table 3-5: Parameters of solar cells used in calculations.

Name	Unit	Value	Comment
Average solar constant	[W/m ²]	1300	
Solar cell efficiency	[-]	0.2	
Efficiency (angle)	[-]	0.9	Solar Cells pointed towards sun
Required power	[W]	1235	
Required area	[m ²]	5.3	

The energy budgets for the science instruments are given below. The WFI Energy budget is based on the power consumption of the WFI mounted on the SOFIA telescope [27].

Table 3-6: Science instrument power budget.

	Power consumption [W]
Wide Field Imager	50
Multiple Channel Imager	150
Detectors	6x 20
Active cooling	30

Omitting the sleep period increases system mass, as solar cells have to be provided for each arbitrary pointing direction leading to a large loss in efficiency and increasing the panel size by a factor of 2 to 3.

3.3.4 Weight and Dimensions

The system's weight and volume are critical parameters that do not only determine operational cost but also technical feasibility. Technical and functional requirements have been formulated and are outlined in the technical and functional report [1]. This chapter presents a first estimation of the system's mass and dimensions based on these requirements in order to assess the overall feasibility and to furthermore get a better understanding of the requirements' effects on general design parameters.

Table 3-7 lists the components' weights for the different cases. The overall mass for the gondola will probably be around 390 kg (*Orison Heavy*), but not significantly lower than 260 kg (*Orison Light*). For a multiple day mission, a considerably higher total gondola mass (450 kg, *Orison Infinity*) is to be expected. Details are given below.

Table 3-7: System mass budget.

Mass [kg]	Orison Heavy	Orison Light	Orison Infinity
Telescope	100	100	100
Science instrument	45	10	10
Gondola frame	68.6	35	85
Mechanical structure	58.6	25	70
Shock absorber	10	10	15
Sensors	7.5	6.5	7.5
GNSS receiver	2	1	2
Gyro sensor	3x 0.5	3x 0.5	3x 0.5

Rotary encoder	2x 0.5	2x 0.5	2x 0.5
Star tracker	3	3	3
Actuators	55	55	55
Pivot motor	5	5	5
Elevation	2x 5	2x 5	2x 5
Reaction wheel motor	5	5	5
Reaction wheel	20	20	20
Fine pointing system	15	15	15
Electronics	25.7	25.4	27.4
Main computer	5	5	5
Data storage	0.7	0.4	2.4
BUS-system, other electronics	15	15	15
Housing/case	5	5	5
Communication	3.6	0.6	3.6
S-Band transceiver	1	-	1
Antenna	2	-	2
Iridium SBD transceiver + antenna	0.6	0.6	0.6
Thermal control / cooling (passive)	10	10	10
Safety systems	2.7	2.7	2.7
Strobe lights	0.2	0.2	0.2
Passive radar reflectors	0.5	0.5	0.5
ATCRB transponder	2x 1	2x 1	2x 1
Batteries	48.8	16.4	118.8
Solar panels	-	-	7.9
Add-on instruments	20	-	20
Total gondola	386.9	261.6	447.9
Balloon	180	155	240
Membrane	120	100	170
Parachute	50	45	60

Suspension line	10	10	10
Total system	566.9	416.6	687.9

3.3.4.1 Science Instrument

Two different Science Instruments for first light missions are proposed in the Technical and Functional Report [1]:

The Wide Field Imager (WFI) consists basically of a camera and a filter wheel. A similar instrument is mounted on the SOFIA Telescope. The values in Table 3-8 are based on dimensions of the WFI mounted on SOFIA [27].

Table 3-8: WFI mass budget.

	Mass [kg]
Wide Field Imager	10
Camera (incl. cooling)	4.5
Filter wheel	1.5
Focal reducer + adapter	4

The Multichannel Imager (MCI) consists of several detectors, one for each channel. Optical elements guide the light and separate it according to the wavelength. Considering a 6 channel instrument, the mass accounts to about 45 kg (Table 3-9):

Table 3-9: MCI mass budget.

	Mass [kg]
Multiple Channel Imager	45
Detectors	6x 3
Active cooling	10
Optics (mirrors/beam splitter)	2
Case, adapter	15

The lighter WFI is accounted to the *Orison Light's* and *Orison Infinity's* system mass, whereas the MCI is accounted for in the *Orison Heavy* case.

3.3.4.2 Gondola Frame

The mass of the gondola structure mainly depends on the type of materials used and the weight, volume and number of payloads to be supported.

For *Orison Heavy*, a sketch of a possible mechanical gondola structure is shown in Figure 3-11. The main structure is a frame made of aluminium-alloy rods, as it is used by several balloon borne telescopes (e.g. BLAST [22], Sunrise [21], EBEX [28]). This configuration is both lightweight and cost-efficient and is therefore taken as a reference for a mechanical structure weight estimation. An important aspect of the frame is its stiffness, which should be sufficiently high in order to avoid deformation of the optical path.

The mass estimation based on the total volume can be derived from the draft, details can be found in Table 3-10.

Figure 3-11: Gondola structure draft design.

The expected ratio of frame to total gondola mass is 15%, a value which is achieved by similar balloon-borne telescopes as shown in Table 3-11. Systems using an aluminium structure (BLAST) are usually heavier than their counterparts which make use of carbon-fibre structures (Spider, Claire).

For the mass budget estimation for *Orison Infinity*, the structure mass is scaled up to match the increased total gondola weight while maintaining the same mass ratio. The total mass is distinctively higher due to heavier batteries and the use of solar panels resulting in a heavier structure.

Table 3-10: Frame mass budget.

	Unit	Value	Details
Rods (support structure)			
Cross-sectional area	[mm ²]	460	
Length: Middle section (telescope)	[mm]	18720	4x1250, 4x1000, 4x830, 4x1600
Length: Bottom section (Add-on instruments and other system components)	[mm]	4740	4x270, 2x1000, 2x830
Length: Top section (reaction wheel, communication)	[mm]	4720	2x500, 2x830, 2x540, 2x490
Antenna boom			
Cross-sectional area	[mm ²]	200	
Length	[mm]	1970	2x985
Total volume (support structure)			
	[cm ³]	13751	
Density	[g/cm ³]	2.7	(6061 Aluminium)
Mass	[kg]	37	
Mass for stage floors and component mounts	[kg]	8	(floor: 4.5 kg/m ² specific mass for aluminium honeycomb structure as used on Spider [29])
Safety margin	[-]	1.3	
Total mass			
	[kg]	58.7	

The structural mass might be decreased by using carbon-composite materials (see Table 3-11). The *Orison Light* mission represents the lowest feasible weight achievable with state-of-the-art manufacturing. It has been shown by the Spider project that the frame might be as light as about 9% of the total gondola mass.

Carbon fibre structures have a higher stiffness, which is an advantage for pointing precision, however due to its anisotropic material properties and lower damping capabilities, it might be more susceptible to damages at impact especially when the gondola tilts over or doesn't land as expected.

Table 3-11: Frame-to-gondola mass ratios of existing balloon-borne telescopes.

Project	Mass Mechanical Structure [kg]	Total Gondola Mass [kg]	Ratio	Material
BLAST [22]	315	2020	0.16	Aluminum
Spider [20, 29]	194	2250	0.09	Carbon-Fiber-Composites
Claire [30]	60	500	0.12	Carbon-Fiber-Composites

The amount of shock absorbing material is estimated by the amount of energy to be absorbed during impact (equations adapted from [4]):

$$\text{Impact velocity} \quad v = \sqrt{2g \frac{m}{c_d A \rho}} \quad (3.10)$$

$$\text{Kinetic energy} \quad E = \frac{1}{2} m v^2 \quad (3.11)$$

$$\text{Margin} \quad \kappa = m_A \cdot \varepsilon / E \quad (3.12)$$

- m_A Absorber mass
- c_d Drag coefficient of parachute
- m Gondola mass
- ρ Air density
- A Parachute cross-section area
- ε Specific energy absorption capacity

A specific absorption energy of 4 kJ/kg (Paper honeycomb [3]) is used as a value to estimate the required mass.

Table 3-12: Crush pad calculation for Orison Heavy.

	Symbol	Unit	Value
Gondola mass	m	[kg]	390
Drag coefficient	c_d	[-]	1.2
Air density	ρ	[kg/m ³]	1.23
Parachute cross section area	A	[m ²]	100
Impact velocity	v	[m/s]	7.2
Kinetic energy	E	[kJ]	20.21
Specific energy absorption	ε	[kJ/kg]	4
Crush pad mass	m_A	[kg]	10
Margin	κ	[-]	2.0

3.3.4.3 Sensors and Actuators

Masses for sensors can be found in manufacturers' product catalogues and are also listed in the Market Offer Report [3].

For the actuator masses, the weights of bearings and cases have to be accounted for in addition to the bare mass given in the technical documents. The masses of the motors used on Spider [20] amount to 6.34 kg each (pivot and reaction wheel). Torque motors with the required specifications vary between 2 kg and 8 kg of mass as indicated by various manufacturers. The weight of the motors used on ORISON is expected to lie in that range.

3.3.4.4 Batteries and Solar Cells

The mass of the batteries depends on power consumption, mission length and the battery's specific capacity (see section 3.3.3 for details). The calculation assumes Lithium Soluble Cathode batteries as primary batteries (485 Wh/kg specific energy) and Nickel/Metal Hydride batteries as secondary batteries (100 Wh/kg) [3].

Table 3-13: Battery mass estimation.

Quantity	Unit	Orison Heavy	Orison Light	Orison Infinity (secondary batteries)
Battery Capacity	[kWh]	18.2	6.1	11.9
Specific energy	[Wh/kg]	485	485	100
Factor accounting for insulation and case for battery pack	[-]	1.3	1.3	1.3
Battery mass	[kg]	48.8	16.4	118.8

In order to meet the high energy needs for long-duration missions, *Orison Infinity* is equipped with solar panels with a mass of about 11.5 kg.

Table 3-14: Solar panel mass estimation.

	Unit	Value
Required solar panel area	[m ²]	5.3
Area-specific mass (including structure) [31]	[kg/m ²]	1.5
Solar Panel mass	[kg]	7.9

For details regarding the solar panel area, refer to section 3.3.3.

3.3.4.5 Electronics and Communication Systems

Electronics and Communication systems contribute considerably to the total system mass. As they have to operate during extreme conditions, components are expected to be heavier than standard home-use electronics; special containers protecting them from environmental conditions might be necessary and increase their mass.

A possible mass reduction measure might be to store all experimental data aboard and remove the LOS communication system (*Orison Light*). This bears the danger of data loss when the payload cannot be recovered after landing.

3.3.4.6 Add-On Instruments

Up to 9 instruments with a total weight of 20 kg and a maximum weight of 4 kg per instrument are intended to be carried additionally during the ORISON missions. Extra support structures have to be made for those instruments. They increase the overall system's complexity and pose augmented requirements for communication, power supply and handling. Therefore, discarding this functional requirement might turn out reasonable. The *Orison Light* scenario does not include add-on instruments.

3.3.4.7 Balloon Mass

In addition to the gondola, the ballast, the suspension line, the parachute, and the actual balloon have to be accounted for the total system weight. N. Yajima et al [7] present methods to determine the balloon mass depending on flight altitude, gondola mass and membrane thickness. For a conventional membrane of 20 μm thickness and a flight altitude of 30 km, the balloon mass will be between 100 kg (*Orison Light*) and 120 kg (*Orison Heavy*). Ballast is necessary for zero-pressure balloons, when lifting gas is vented due to temperature changes. Therefore, for multiple-day missions, ballast has to be carried aboard. For conventional balloons flying over the earth's middle latitude, the buoyancy is reduced about 7-10% of the total weight [7]. For the *Orison Infinity* scenario (7 days of flight), this would mean, that 44% of the total system weight has to be ballast.

As this is not practically feasible, a super-pressure balloon can be used, which doesn't need ballast, as lifting gas is not vented. For short duration flights, no ballast is required.

3.3.4.8 Summary

The mass budget analysis for the three different cases leads to the following conclusion: a gondola weight of about 400 kg can be expected. Increasing the observation time also increases system mass. Even with severe changes and mass reduction techniques, a mass below 260 kg turns out to be unrealistic especially when a fixed financial budget is considered. However, the overall mission concept might benefit from some of the optimization steps mentioned above (e.g. removing the add-on payloads and using carbon-fibre-composite materials). Some further considerations in this regard are described in chapter 6.

4 OPERATIONAL FEASIBILITY

Besides sketching out an innovative technical solution for a balloon-based telescope, one of the goals of ORISON is to find or develop an operational scenario that is suitable to support an affordable and accessible stratospheric observatory.

The ways in which a balloon-based observatory should be operated and interface with scientists (i.e. primarily observation time allocation, frequency of flights, data access, instrument selection and access) were already discussed in the ORISON Technical and Functional Report [1]. In this report, also technical and functional requirements were derived from the user needs which formed the basis of the feasibility study. This chapter will thus detail the main implementation options that were considered. It will focus on three aspects: ground facilities, considered flight trajectories, and communication and data handling options. Following a discussion of these aspects, a critical review of the original requirements will summarise the findings.

Furthermore, this chapter will present the experience gathered through lightweight pathfinder balloon missions carried out during the ORISON project.

4.1 GROUND FACILITIES

A considerable amount of effort, and a considerable fraction of the total mission cost of larger stratospheric balloon missions, is associated with on-ground operations. Particularly in case of regular flights, as foreseen for ORISON (also see RF1 in [1]), ground operations concepts thus need to be carefully chosen.

The main functions that need to be covered by ground operations and equipment are:

- Provision of space for payload preparation
- Launch support, further divisible into:
 - Provision of lifting gas
 - Safe balloon inflation
 - Payload handling before ascent
- Provision of a communication link with the balloon during flight, piloting of the balloon
- Operation of the instrument
- Recovery of payload and balloon.
- Preferably good observation capabilities of local winds

The hardware and manpower required to fulfil these functions greatly depends on the size of the balloon and the chosen operational concepts. There is a particularly large step in terms of effort at the point when the gondola becomes too heavy to be handled by hand, and auxiliary equipment particularly during the launch becomes necessary (which also increases the team size required during launch). This point is likely located somewhere between 30 and 40 kg payload mass. Since all three ORISON concepts assume a gondola mass considerably higher than that, the main focus in the following will be on functional areas where different operational concepts can decrease the required effort.

4.1.1 Launch Support

Launch operations of large balloons pose several challenges related to the size of the flight equipment and the special nature of balloon launches. The flight train can easily be 100 m long, particularly for astronomical missions when the obstruction angle at zenith due to the balloon should be minimised. The launch area thus needs to provide sufficient space to handle the flight train. Additionally, the balloon itself can easily have a diameter of 10 to 20 m at ground conditions and is therefore very susceptible to wind during preparatory and launch operations. It therefore has to be well restrained during preparation (filling the balloon with lifting gas takes about 1 h [7]) while protecting its sensitive membrane and wind has to be taken carefully into account during launch to avoid damage to the gondola.

Several techniques have been developed to handle launch operations at different sites, adapted to the site situations and requiring different amounts of equipment and effort. The technique mostly used by the Swedish Space Corporation (SSC) at the launch site in Kiruna/Esrange, but also by NASA at the launch sites in the U.S. and in Antarctica is the *dynamic launch technique* (see also figure 4-1). In case of this technique, the balloon is restrained by a roller vehicle during inflation which compensates the buoyant force. The gondola meanwhile is suspended slightly above the ground by a wheeled and mobile launch vehicle. At the time of launch, the launch vehicle is positioned downwind of the balloon. The balloon then is released from the roller vehicle and ascends freely subjected to its own buoyancy and the wind. The launcher at this point moves to position the gondola underneath the ascending balloon and releases the gondola, aiming to minimize shock and swinging motions of the gondola. The disadvantage of this technique is that it requires a comparably large launch area and a specialised launch vehicle.

Figure 4-1: Principle of the dynamic launch technique (left sketch) and semi-dynamic launch technique (right sketch).

Due to narrow launch fields in Japan, the Japanese Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) developed adjusted launch methods that lead to the currently used “sliding launcher” or *semi-dynamic launch method*. In case of this method, both the roller/spool vehicle and the launch vehicle are mounted on straight rails. In contrary to the dynamic launch method, the launch vehicle is thus not freely manoeuvrable, but rather features a turntable to adjust for the wind direction. Otherwise the launch procedure is similar to that of the dynamic launch (see also). A particular advantage of this technique, and the launch base on the Japanese Taiki Aerospace Research Field (TARF), where it is employed, is the fact that the balloon can be inflated inside a sufficiently large hangar (30 m wide, 35 m high), keeping it protected from wind during the inflation process [32]. Yet another technique is the one employed by CNES using an *auxiliary balloon*, as depicted in figure 4-2. In this case, the payload is kept aloft few meters above the ground by a smaller balloon, generating only slightly more lift than necessary to keep it aloft. At launch, both the main and the auxiliary balloon are released almost simultaneously and ascend in parallel

Figure 4-2: CNES launch method with an auxiliary balloon (front).

until the main balloon has risen enough to straighten the flight train and the auxiliary balloon detaches or is deflated. The advantages of this method are that ground winds are less critical than for a dynamic or a semi-dynamic launch and that no specialised launch vehicle is required. Particularly the latter make this technique well suitable for a flexible choice of launch locations.

Another technique that shall find short mentioning is that employed by Google for their Google Loon launches. Google repurposed container cranes as largely automated launch vehicles. As figure 4-3 shows, this allows them to inflate the balloon protected from the wind, to install the payload on the same launch vehicle, and to position the launch vehicle at the optimal angle to the wind before launch. The disadvantage of this method are that the flight train length is restricted, and that the size of the balloons is also restricted. Google Loon uses 1250 m³ balloons [33], whereas the ORISON scenarios will require balloons of 60,000 m³ or more.

Figure 4-3: Google Loon autolauncher. Image from [33].

4.1.2 Communication Equipment

Several communication options are available and in use for direct balloon-ground connection, as also discussed in [3]. Among them are prominently S-band connections, offering a high data rate for e.g. science data downlink and lower data rate options such as UHF. As the more detailed analysis in section 4.2.2 will show, due to the high-power requirement of a high data rate S-band system it makes sense to use a comparably large ground based antenna (in the order of 1.5 m diameter) to reduce the on-board transmitter power requirement, making the ground station comparably large. It may therefore be worthwhile to reconsider the requirement of full science data downlink (RF12) and to go without a high data rate downlink. This option gains further relevance when considering that even with an S-band downlink, it will likely not be possible to downlink all data from the Multi-Channel Imager or a similar instrument (see also section 4.2.2).

A second point to consider is that the flight geometry limits the range of line of sight (LOS) communication to a radius of approximately 600 to 700 km around the ground station (see section 4.2.2.1). This will likely not be an issue for long flights such as foreseen in the *Orison Infinity* scenario, since the flight distances in this scenario make satellite communication necessary anyway. It may, however, come into consideration for several trajectory options suitable for *Orison Light* and *Orison Heavy*. At wind speeds between 10 and 20 m/s in the stratosphere, a balloon flying at 20 km may reach the communication range limit in between 8 and 17 h, if continuously flying into the same direction. For trajectories such as the transmediterranean ones (see section 4.2.1), it would thus be necessary to consider either the use of additional ground stations along the expected flight path, or to only rely upon satellite-based communication channels after launch and early flight. For trajectories covering extended distances over land, it might be worthwhile to consider mobile ground stations, such as they have been used by the Italian Space Agency (ASI) in the past.

4.1.3 Available Ground Facilities

According to requirements RF14 and RF16 [1], ORISON shall make use of existing launch infrastructure if possible, and aim at launching from accessible, mid-latitude locations. Table 4-1 therefore lists a number of existing launch sites that are potentially suitable for the ORISON scenarios. The flight trajectories mentioned are covered in more detail in section 4.2.1.

However, suitable large private property or unused airports could be used as well.

Table 4-1: Existing launch sites considered for ORISON flights

Launch site	Country / main operator	Mid-latitude?	Potential flight trajectories	Suitable for
Northern hemisphere				
Esrange	Sweden / SSC	No	Turnaround conditions, Sweden-Canada	Orison Light, Orison Heavy, Orison Infinity
Trapani-Milo ^d	Italy / ASI	Yes	Transmediterranean	Orison Heavy
Aire-sur-l'Adour ^e	France / CNES	Yes	Short flights	TBD
Timmins	Canada / CSA	Yes	Short flights (~3h)	TBD
Southern hemisphere				
Wanaka	New Zealand	Yes	TBD	TBD
Alice Springs	Australia	Yes	TBD	TBD

4.1.4 Minimum Operations Concept

Following ORISON requirement RF16, it would be best to aim at using one of the existing ballooning bases mentioned in section 4.1.3. However, if launching from somewhere else was taken into consideration, e.g. from an inactive airport in Spain, the following minimum operations concept could be considered:

- Launch using auxiliary balloon launch method
- No high data rate connection, only UHF line-of-sight communication and potentially satellite communication link
- Use of helium as lifting gas
- Use of data from nearby weather stations

In this case, the required ground hardware would be mostly limited to:

- Hangar / facilities for payload preparation;
- Launch pad area of at least 140 m in one dimension, larger if longer flight trains are to be used;
- Helium supply and filling & measurement hardware for gas injection;
- Spool / roller vehicle;
- Crane or other equipment for transport of the payload;
- Ground station (commercially available^f).

^d The Trapani-Milo base has been inactive since 2010.

^e Due to increased safety regulations, the balloon base in Aire-sur-l'Adour has been mostly inactive since 2009.

^f e.g. from ISIS (<https://www.isispace.nl/>)

4.2 LAUNCH AND FLIGHT

4.2.1 Flight Altitude and Duration

Given the observation conditions described in section 3.1, a float altitude of 30 km or more is pursued as the baseline for all ORISON flights. Several trajectory options that are currently used for stratospheric balloon flights or have been used in the past can provide flight times at this altitude satisfying the observation time goals of the three ORISON scenarios. While each of them will be discussed in more detail in the following, table 4-2 provides a general overview of specific trajectories and trajectory types suitable for each scenario, also mentioning shortcomings if they exist. In addition to the suitable established flight trajectories, a potential future option is listed for the *Orison Heavy* and *Orison Light* scenarios. This trajectory option has to undergo further detailed study, however, and is discussed in more detail in section 4.2.1.5.

Table 4-2: Flight trajectory options for the three ORISON scenarios,

	Orison Heavy	Orison Light	Orison Infinity
Observation duration [h]	20	10	85
Option 1	Turnaround conditions	Turnaround conditions	Kiruna-Canada
Typical total flight duration	24 h	14 h	130 - 170 h
Comments	No night during flights ^g	No night during flights ^g	
Option 2	Transmediterranean	(Boomerang flight) ^h	
Typical total flight duration	17 -27 h	(10-13 h) ^h	
Comments	Max. 8 h night ⁱ		
Potential future option	Boomerang flight in Europe	Boomerang flight in Europe	

^g Assuming turnaround conditions over Esrang, Sweden. During the period when turnaround conditions exist, a maximum of ca. 5.5 h of nautical twilight + 2.5 h of civil twilight and occur on the ground.

^h The reference are boomerang flights in Japan (see also section 4.2.1.4). Due to a change of wind patterns, the long duration flights (10 h and longer) are not possible anymore, though, and flight durations are currently limited to around 3 h, which would not be sufficient for the Orison light scenario.

ⁱ Assuming flights around the 38th parallel. During the period of suitable westerly winds, a maximum of 8 h of night and 3 h of twilight (ca. 1 h each astronomical, nautical, civil) occur on the ground.

4.2.1.1 Background: Flights during Turnaround Conditions

Winds in the stratosphere predominantly blow from east to west (easterly winds) during summer and predominantly from west to east (westerly winds) during winter. In spring and late summer, the turnaround of the stratospheric winds between these two major directions leads to limited periods of very weak winds. These periods can be used to maintain a balloon over a confined area close to the launch site for extended times (typically around 20 to 30 h depending on the ballast carried, but 40 h have been reached). Particularly SSC regularly makes use of the turnaround conditions that are available over Kiruna / Esrange typically around late April / early May and during the second half of August [34]. Figure 4-4 shows the flight trajectory of a particularly successful flight during turnaround conditions over Esrange.

*Figure 4-4: Flight trajectory of a long-duration flight (40 h 20 min) during turnaround conditions in August from Esrange, Sweden.
Plot from [7], based on [35].*

Flights during turnaround conditions over Esrange, or potentially also elsewhere, would be well suitable for the *Orison Heavy* and *Orison Light* scenarios.

4.2.1.2 Background: Flights from Kiruna to Canada

For *Orison Infinity*, flight durations of ca. 7 days are necessary. One option to achieve these flight times is flights from Esrange during summer, when easterly winds (blowing west) in the stratosphere carry the balloon to Canada. This type of trajectory as shown in figure 4-5 has been used by several missions in the past and can offer, depending on the exact wind conditions and the associated choice of landing zone, between 5 and 7 days of total flight time (see table 4-3 for flight data of previous missions).

Figure 4-5: Exemplary flight trajectories from Esrange to Canada: Sunrise flights in 2009 and 2013.

Wind conditions generally would also allow longer, circumpolar flights, which have been conducted in the past. The difficulty of obtaining overflight permits over Russian territory have prevented such flights throughout the last years, however.

Table 4-3: Flight details of several long-duration flights from Esrange to Canada. Data on Sunrise 2013 from [36]; data on Sunrise 2009 from [21]; data on PoGO+ from [37]

	Sunrise 2009	Sunrise 2013	PoGO+
Float altitude	34 to 37 km	36 km ^j	n.a.
Total flight duration	5 d 17 h	5 d 7 h	6 d 19.5 h
Ascent (ca.)	3 h	3.5 h	n.a.
Time at float altitude	5 d 13 h	5 d 2.3 h (122.3 h)	n.a.
Descent (ca.)	1 h	1 h	1 h

4.2.1.3 Background: Transmediterranean Flights

An interesting trajectory option particularly for the *Orison Heavy* scenario would be transmediterranean flights from Sicily to mainland Spain. This route was used regularly until 2002 under agreements between Italy, Spain, and France, and later Italy and Spain, launching from the Luigi Broglio Stratospheric Balloon Launch Base in Trapani Milo on the western coast of Sicily, operated by the Italian Space Agency ASI. While the base was shut down in 2010, some of the infrastructure, most prominently the launch pad, remain, so that it might be possible to use the clear area for launch operations again.

^j Mean float altitude

Figure 4-6: Flight trajectories of eight transmediterranean flights from 1999 to 2002, launching from the Luigi Broglio base in Trapani-Milo (TPN). The plot also shows the ground stations in Trapani (TPN), Palma (PLM), and El Arenosillo (ARN). Plot from [38].

As Figure 4-6 indicates, given a good choice of the launching time, landings in the sparsely inhabited regions of Southern Spain could be arranged. A remaining risk was a drift too far to the South, making a land landing impossible. This risk was partly mitigated by equipping the gondolas with inflatable flotation devices [38].

The mean flight time that was achieved during these flights was slightly more than 20 h, with most flights lasting between 17 and 27 h [38]. These times are well suitable for the *Orison Heavy* scenario. Suitable wind conditions for these flights were found during June, July, and August.

4.2.1.4 Background: Boomerang Flights in Japan

A very interesting type of flight trajectories, both for *Orison Heavy* and *Orison Light*, are boomerang trajectories. This type of trajectories makes use of prevailing winds in opposite directions at different altitudes that tend to exist during certain times of year. The most favorable option is to use winds at lower altitudes to fly in one direction, drop ballast once a certain distance from the launch site is reached, and return towards the launch site at the eventual float and observation altitude (as shown in figure 4-7 for a flight from the Japanese Sanriku Balloon Center in 2006). The sequence “low altitude before high altitude leg” is generally preferable because the ballast drop at the turning point implies less risk of a terminal failure than the venting of large amounts of lifting gas to drastically lower the altitude would.

Figure 4-7: Typical trajectory and flight profile of a "boomerang" flight from the (now closed) Japanese Sanriku Balloon Center (SBC) at 39 deg northern latitude. Graph from [39].

As the flight data in table 4-4 indicates, flights from the now-closed Sanriku Balloon Center in Japan allowed flight times at float altitude of around 10 h, which would have been very well suitable for the *Orison Light* scenario. Unfortunately, the easterly Jetstream that the boomerang flights rely upon has become less reliable during the last years, so that only few boomerang flights are being carried out each year from the new ballooning base on the Taiki Aerospace Research Field (TARF). Furthermore, the Japanese Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) that operates the flights now limits domestic boomerang flights mostly to engineering test flights of about 3 h duration due to the changed wind conditions (see table 4-5 for flight data of more recent flights from TARF).

Table 4-4: Flight data of past boomerang flights from the Sanriku Balloon Center in Japan. Data on BETS from [40], data on BAT-1 from [41]

	BETS	BAT-1
Year	1994	1976
Float altitude	35 km ^k	25 km
Total flight duration	10 h	n.a.
Ascent (ca.)	n.a.	2 h
Time at float altitude	n.a.	9 h
Descent (ca.)	n.a.	n.a.

^k Average altitude

Table 4-5: Flight times of boomerang flights from the Taiki Aerospace Research Field. Data on bCALET-2 from [42]; data on GAPS from [43]; data on BBT from [44].

	bCALET-2	GAPS	BBT
Year	2009	2012	2009
Float altitude	35 km	31-33 km	32 km
Total flight duration	n.a.	n.a.	7.5 h
Ascent (ca.)	Ca. 2 h	3 h	3 h 55 min
Time at float altitude	2.5 h	3 h	3 h 10 min
Descent (ca.)	n.a.	n.a.	Ca. 30 min

For reference and illustration, figure 4-8 shows the seasonal variation of prevailing wind directions over the SBC. The plot of east-west wind components shows that roughly from May to mid-July and end-July to early September, the Jetstream blows towards the east, whereas winds in the higher stratosphere at 30 to 40 km blow towards the west, offering suitable conditions for boomerang flights. The plot of north-south wind components furthermore shows that these components tend to be small compared to the east-west components, leading only to limited drift of the balloon to the north or south.

Figure 4-8: Seasonal variation of the east-west (left) and north-south (right) winds in the vicinity of the Japanese Sanriku Balloon Center at 39 deg northern latitude throughout the year 2006. Positive numbers indicate westerly winds (blowing east), negative numbers easterly winds (blowing west). Wind speeds in m/s. Data from the ERA-Interim reanalysis of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), based on measurements and models [45].

4.2.1.5 Background: Potential Boomerang Flights in Europe

Several locations in Europe are also generally suitable for boomerang flights. These are particularly locations with large uninhabited areas (e.g. water) to their East, allowing eastward flights at lower altitude after launch and return at float altitude in the westward-blowing stratospheric winds during summer (it is generally preferable to fly the lower leg first, since the dropping of ballast involves less risk to the mission than the venting of large amounts of lifting gas). Potentially suitable locations that provide around 700 km

distance over water to their East (which, at ca. 10 to 20 m/s wind speed at a float altitude between 30 and 40 km would allow for 10 to 20 h of observation time) are e.g. Eastern Spain and Northern Scotland.

The wind conditions at these locations will be shortly explored in the following and can serve as a first indication of the general suitability of the locations. To properly judge the feasibility of boomerang trajectories from these locations, more detailed analysis and simulations will need to be carried out, however.

Eastern Spain / Castilla-La Mancha

The vertical wind profiles in figure 4-9 shows that similar to the situation above the Japanese ballooning base, during the period roughly from the beginning of June to the middle of September, westward winds dominate at the altitudes between 30 and 40 km. At the same time, lower altitude winds remain dominated by eastward components (even though north/south components are comparably strong as well).

Figure 4-10 supports the impression that flight times with little north-south drift can be found. It should be noted, though, that a small northward component at 15 km does exist also for the depicted date. Conditions at different dates did show stronger north-south components. The questions of stability of these conditions throughout flight durations and the ability to reliably forecast these winds remain to be answered by more detailed analysis.

A potentially suitable launch site for such flights could be the closed airport of Ciudad Real in Castilla-La Mancha.

Figure 4-9: Eastward (left) and northward (right) wind components in Castilla-La Mancha (40 deg N, -3 deg E) throughout the year 2016.

Positive values indicate eastward and northward winds, negative values westward and southward winds. Wind speeds in m/s. Data from the ERA-Interim reanalysis of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), based on measurements and models [45].

Figure 4-10: Wind fields at 15 km (left) and 33 km (right) in the potential flight region over Castilla-La Mancha. Data from August 2nd 2016 at 00:00 GMT. Data from the ECMWF's ERA-Interim reanalysis. [45]

Northern Scotland

As figure 4-11 shows, the summerly westward stratospheric winds equally exist over Northern Scotland. They commence at roughly the same altitude as over La Mancha (ca. 20 km), but grow stronger at higher altitudes than over La Mancha (e.g. the winds only reach westward velocities of 20 m/s above 40 km, whereas over La Mancha they reach 20 m/s already above 30 km). The North/South components seem roughly similar in this plot. Telling only from this plot, Northern Scotland thus would also be a potentially suitable location for stratospheric boomerang flights, if not even better than La Mancha due to the slower expectable westward drift velocity.

Figure 4-11: Eastward (left) and northward (right) wind components in Northern Scotland (58 deg N, -3.5 deg E) throughout the year 2016. Positive values indicate eastward and northward winds, negative values westward and southward winds. Wind speeds in m/s. Data from the ERA-Interim reanalysis of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), based on measurements and models [45].

Figure 4-12: Wind fields at 15 km (left) and 33 km (right) in the potential flight region over Northern Scotland. Data from June 15th 2016 at 00:00 GMT. Data from the ECMWF's ERA-Interim reanalysis. [45]

A closer look at figure 4-12 reveals, however, that the winds at 15 km, during a period and at an altitude that seems well suitable telling from figure 4-11, shows relatively strong northward components, particularly over the North Sea and getting closer to Norway. At least under these conditions, Northern Scotland as a flight location seems riskier due to the possibility of northward drift. To provide a proper decision base, more analysis of additional days and times would need to be carried out, however.

4.2.2 Communication

Two different cases may exist for both applications during a flight: the case in which communication with a ground station is possible along the line-of-sight; and in case of long duration missions, the case where direct communication with a single ground station is not possible anymore and over-the-horizon communication needs to be ensured. Available systems and solutions for both cases are discussed in the following.

4.2.2.1 Operational Range of Line-of-Sight Communication

The most direct, and thus theoretically most reliable and least affected by delay, with a balloon is a line of sight connection with an assigned ground station. Due to the comparably small distances, theoretically constant connectivity, and the practicability of using directed antennas on the

Figure 4-13: Maximum ground distance between balloon and ground station for different elevation limits and flight altitudes of 30 and 40 km.

ground, a line-of-sight connection also is the most mass- and power-efficient way of establishing a high data rate connection. Its range, however, is fundamentally limited by the flight geometry, more precisely by the flight altitude of the balloon and the minimum useable elevation angle of the ground station (mostly determined by obstacles low above the ground).¹ Figure 4-13 shows the maximum ground distance between balloon and ground station for which line-of-sight communication can be used, depending on the smallest accessible elevation angle and for flight altitudes of 30 and 40 km. It shows that under favorable conditions, i.e. an unobstructed view of the ground station down to ca. 1 deg elevation, line-of-sight communication is limited to ca. 500 or 600 km ground distance for flight altitudes of 30 or 40 km respectively.

4.2.2.2 Over-the-Horizon Communication

Satellite-to-ground communication is carried out in the L-Band. One of the advantages of Iridium is that a large range of terminals and other hardware is commercially available. With the Iridium NEXT constellation, Iridium will offer a range of new services called “Iridium Certus”. These will include broadband IP-based services, similar to what is currently available through Iridium Pilot, but with data rates of up to 1.4 Mbit/s (downlink) and 512 kbit/s (uplink) at full operational services [46]. The pricing of Iridium Certus is not yet clear.

The Inmarsat broadband services offer very high data rates, however, at higher power requirements than the Iridium equipment. Inmarsat broadband equipment usually uses mechanically steered, high-gain antennas to track one of the satellites to reduce the high transmit power otherwise required at the long distance to the geostationary satellites (orbital altitude of 35,786 km vs. approximately 800 km orbital altitude in low Earth orbit).

4.2.2.3 Communication Concept and Line-of-Sight Link Budget

In order to download generated science data, a broadband downlink connection is required. The uplink connection is only required for commanding the balloon or the instruments and thus can operate with a lower data rate. For the heavy case and the infinity case (7-day mission), an additional backup communication system is added. The backup system should be independent from the main communication system in order to prevent single point failures, thus an Iridium SBD system is a suitable choice for a backup system as it uses a different transmission path. With the backup system it is possible to acquire the balloon’s position for reestablishing a Line-of-Sight communication and to keep it under control even when it leaves the ground antennas’ field of view.

A Link-Budget Calculation after [47] for line-of-sight communication is presented in table 4-6. For the link-budget calculations, a ground station altitude of 500 m and a balloon flight altitude of 30 km is assumed resulting in a maximal distance of 700 km between groundstation and balloon for line-of-sight communication. The link margin should be higher than 5 dB in order to properly work even during bad weather conditions.

¹ The basic limitation to direct communication can be overcome in a way by making use of the capability of the ionosphere to reflect radio waves at certain wavelengths. This technique will not be considered for the following calculations.

A communication system using the assumed power and technical parameters thus could cover the entire available field of view of a ground station.

Table 4-6: LOS communication link budget.

<i>Quantity</i>	<i>Symbol</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Downlink</i>	<i>Uplink</i>
Frequency (S-Band)	f	[GHz]	2.3	2.2
Wavelength	λ	[m]	0.13	0.136
Transmitter power	P	[W]	15	1
Transmitter power	P	[dB W]	11.8	0
Transmitter line loss	L_i	[dB]	-2	-2
Transmit antenna diameter	D_t	[m]	0.06	1.5
Transmit antenna beam width	Θ_t	[deg]	152.2	6.4
Transmit antenna pointing offset	e_t	[deg]	80	0.6
Transmit antenna pointing loss	L_{pt}	[dB]	-6.3	-1.1
Transmit antenna efficiency	η	[-]	0.55	0.55
Peak transmit antenna gain	G_{pt}	[dBi]	0.6	28.2
Transmit antenna gain (netto)	G_t	[dBi]	-5.7	27.1
Distance	s	[km]	700	700
Space loss	L_s	[dB]	-156.6	-156.6
Propagation absorption loss	L_a	[dB]	-2	-2
Receive antenna diameter	D_r	[m]	1.5	0.06
Receive antenna beam width	Θ_r	[deg]	6.1	159.1
Receive antenna pointing offset	e_r	[deg]	0.6	80
Receive antenna pointing loss	L_{pr}	[dB]	-1.2	-6.0
Receive antenna efficiency	η	[-]	0.55	0.55
Peak receive antenna gain	G_{pr}	[dB]	28.57	0.22
Receive antenna gain (netto)	G_r	[dB]	27.38	-5.81
System noise temperature	T_s	[K]	135	614
Data rate	R	[bps]	2000000	1000
E_b/N_0	E_b/N_0	[dB]	17.2	31.4
BER			1.00E-05	1.00E-07
Required E_b/N_0 (BPSK modulation)	E_b/N_0 req	[dB]	9.8	11.4
Carrier-to-noise density ratio	C/ N_0	[dB Hz]	80.2	61.4
Implementation loss		[dB]	-2	-2
Margin (must achieve > 5 dB)		[dB]	5.4	18

4.2.3 Onboard Computing

In regards to onboard computing and data storage, again a distinction needs to be made between flight service equipment and payload equipment. Several standardized systems exist for the former and some basic systems exist for the latter, the baseline assumption seems to be, however, that experiments provide their own payload computer and data acquisition/data storage management. While the detailed split up of functions between the flight service equipment and the payload equipment differ between implementations, table 4-7 provides a general overview of the functions typically served by each system. The interface between the two usually consists of one or several communication lines and potentially several on/off command lines provided by the flight service on-board computer (OBC).

Table 4-7: General functional split-up between flight service system and payload onboard computing.

Flight Service System	Payload System
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Balloon piloting (lifting gas venting and ballast jettison)• Separation and parachute commands• Aeronautical navigation safety (control of radar transponder, strobe light, and Air Traffic Control Radar Beacon System transponder)• Acquisition, storage, and communication of flight telemetry• Provision of communication channel(s) to the ground	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Command and control of the experiment/instrument• Acquisition of payload data• Storage of payload data• Formatting of payload data for handover to flight service system, if applicable

4.2.4 Data Handling

Two main options for the management of (scientific) payload data exist: on-board storage of generated data with retrieval of the data from the on-board hardware after landing, and downlink of all scientific data during the mission. The ORISON baseline concept gives preference to the downlink of all scientific data before landing in order to minimize the risk of data loss (see [1], requirement RF12). In order to assess the feasibility of this preference, the amount of scientific data expected to be generated under different scenarios needs to be analyzed. Table 4-8 shows the average data generation rates expected from the baseline instruments (as per [1], of which only one would be flown simultaneously) and for housekeeping. For the raw data generation rate, a duty cycle of 90 % of the instruments during observing mode was assumed.

Table 4-8: Expected data generation during flight

	<i>Wide-Field Imager (WFI)</i>	<i>Multichannel Imager (MCI)</i>	<i>Housekeeping (TM)</i>
Direction of link	Downlink	Downlink	Downlink
Data generation during	Observing mode	Observing mode	Constantly
Rate of raw data generation	1.5 Mbit/s	81.5 Mbit/s	6.3 bit/s
Overhead	10%	10%	30%
Margin/contingency	50%	50%	50%
Compression factor	1.5	1.5	1 (no compression)
Resulting average data generated for downlink	1.7 Mbit/s	89.7 Mbit/s	12.3 bit/s

Table 4-9 furthermore shows the available downlink volume over the flight duration (starting with the first observation period) for the different scenarios (*Orison Light, Heavy, and Infinity*) and for different communication systems.

“Communication System 1” assumes that all communication is carried out via an S-Band line-of-sight link that is available without interruption. Constant line-of-sight connection might be achievable in the *Orison Light* and *Orison Heavy* scenarios, but will likely not be the case in the *Orison Infinity* scenario. This system would be best suited for the preferred operational scenario in which all scientific data should be downlinked during the flight.

“Communication System 2” represents the capabilities of only an Iridium Dial-Up data connection. This analysis optimistically assumes that a data rate of 2.4 kbit/s is constantly available. The performance of this system shows how many images could be downlinked during a flight time when no LOS connection is available.

“Communication System 3” represents a scenario where only telemetry data is downlinked via an Iridium SBD modem, while all scientific data is stored on board.

Table 4-9: Downlink data margins for the different ORISON scenarios and different communication systems.

	<i>Orison Light</i>	<i>Orison Heavy</i>	<i>Orison Infinity</i>
Flight duration	Ca. 14 h	24 h	Ca. 170 h
Time in observation mode ^m	10 h ⁿ	20 h	85 h
Available time for downlink (outside observation mode) ^m	1 h	1 h	82 h
<i>Communication System 1: Only LOS S-Band</i>			
Available constant downlink rate	2 Mbit/s	2 Mbit/s	2 Mbit/s
Total downlinkable data	8.9 GB	17 GB	133 GB
Available data margin factor WFI+TM	1.3	1.25	2.3
Available data margin factor MCI+TM	0.02	0.02	0.04
Available data margin factor TM only	1.6E5	1.6E5	1.6E5
<i>Communication System 2: Continuous downlink via Iridium Dial-Up data service</i>			
Available constant downlink rate	2.4 kbit/s	2.4 kbit/s	2.4 kbit/s
Downlinkable data ^o	10 MB	38 MB	168 MB
Number of downlinkable full WFI images ^p	0.8	1.5	12
Number of downlinkable full MCI images	0.01	0.02	0.2
Available data margin TM only	97	97	97
<i>Communication System 3: Iridium SBD only</i>			
Full TM downlink requires an SBD messages every	3.7 min	3.7 min	3.7 min

The analysis as represented by the results in table 4-9 leads to the following conclusions:

- Housekeeping data, even assuming a very high amount of data, can be comfortably transmitted via Iridium SDB.

^m Mode allocation during flight assumes 3 h of ascent to flight altitude before the start of the first observation and at least 1 h descent without observations.

ⁿ See RF2.

^o Between beginning of first and end of last observation

^p In addition to TM downlink and TC uplink. Assuming the same amount of data for TC uplink as for TM downlink.

-
- With an instrument like the Wide-field imager, it will be possible to downlink all scientific data if constant broadband line-of-sight communication is available.
 - With such an instrument, it would also be possible to downlink full reference images in between observations during longer duration flights when no LOS connection is available. Downlink times of full images with Iridium Dial-Up are expected to be in the order of 12 h, however.
 - For an instrument like the Multichannel imager, it is illusory to downlink all scientific data during flight via the available S-Band communication systems. Doing so would require an average continuous downlink rate in the order of 80 Mbit/s (*Orison Light*) to 40 Mbit/s (*Orison Infinity*). Such downlink rates could potentially be achieved by using an X-Band communication system with a bandwidth of 60 or 30 MHz respectively⁹. X-Band communication systems are not available for stratospheric balloons, however, require more power than the considered S-Band systems, and judging their feasibility for balloons would require further investigation.

4.2.5 Data Storage

As the analysis in section 4.2.4 showed, the scientific data will need to be stored on board for retrieval after landing. On-board storage of all data also would be recommendable for the purpose of redundancy even if downlink of all data was foreseen. As also discussed in section 4.2.4, the Multichannel Imager would generate considerably more data than the Wide-field imager. It is thus used as the driving instrument for the data storage sizing. Table 4-10 summarizes the maximum amounts of scientific data expected to be generated by the MCI in the three ORISON scenarios.

Available data storage hardware

Unlike for spacecraft, there seem to be no dedicated, commercially available solutions for data handling and storage for stratospheric balloons. If one does not want to use expensive spacecraft hardware, this leaves the options of using commercially available hardware made for ground-based applications or using custom made hardware. On short flights, such as BEXUS flights or also REXUS sounding rocket flights, commercial hardware is used frequently and successfully (see e.g. [48], [49]). For longer flights and higher data volumes, there seem to be certain limitations with regard to reliability, however, so that custom solutions become preferable [50].

For science data storage, three basic options are available: SD cards, solid state devices (SDDs), or rotating platter hard disk drives (HDDs). All three options would be able to provide the required write speed of 81.5 Mbit/s or more (see section 4.2.4). While SD cards and SDDs are intrinsically more tolerant to rough physical conditions, the suitability depends on the application in detail.

⁹ Assuming TCM-8PSK modulation and Reed-Solomon error-correcting coding. Note that for space science missions, the downlink bandwidth in X-Band is limited to 10 MHz (see European Cooperation for Space Standardization (ECSS) regulations [83]). Which frequency ranges within the X-Band could be used by balloons would need to be further investigated.

COTS SD cards and SSDs are frequently used on short duration flights, such as the BEXUS flights. For these short time applications, they are well proven and suitable, since they are relatively immune to low pressure, vibrations, and the occurring shocks. SSDs however are susceptible to data corruption during long-term storage [51], particularly under the influence of cosmic radiation at stratospheric altitudes [28]. Enterprise class SSDs, used for writing access up to 24 h/day, for example, are only required to guarantee a median time of 3 months prior to the first bit error [51], which can be relevant particularly for ultra-long duration balloon mission.

HDDs promise better data storage integrity, but are physically more demanding than SSDs. The disks need to be protected against vibrations and shocks, and they need to be flown in pressurized containers [51], as on the EBEX balloon experiment, for example [28].

EBEX used two independent pressure vessels with seven commercial 320 GB 2.5” parallel ATA magnet hard disks each. With custom disk management software, each of the pressure vessels had a steady state power consumption of 38.4 W. [28]

Data storage hardware assumed for ORISON

As mentioned above, all three options (SD cards, SDDs, HDDs) qualify for the application on ORISON with regard to write speed. Since the flight durations in all three ORISON scenarios are relatively short compared to ULDB or LDB missions such as EBEX, it is reasonable to assume that SDDs will be sufficiently reliable, particularly if they are foreseen to be exchanged after a few flights. To decrease the risk of data loss, fully redundant storage of the scientific data will be foreseen.

Table 4-10 summarizes the required disk space and potential data storage solution using standard 500 GB external SSD drives.

EBEX used two independent pressure vessels with seven commercial 320 GB 2.5” parallel ATA magnet hard disks each. With custom disk management software, each of the pressure vessels had a steady state power consumption of 38.4 W [28].

Table 4-10: Summary of potential data storage solutions for the three ORISON scenarios.

	<i>Orison Light</i>	<i>Orison Heavy</i>	<i>Orison Infinity</i>
Total MCI data generated ^f	0.55 TB	1.1 TB	4.7 TB
Min. required disk space (dual modular redundancy)	1.1 TB	2.2 TB	9.4 TB
Number of drives required	3	5	19
Available storage space	1.5 TB	2.5 TB	9.5 TB
Total mass of drives ^s	0.445 kg	0.745 kg	2.831 kg

^f Including a margin of 50 %, but not accounting for any overhead. Observation times as specified in table 4-5.

^s No power supply, cabling, or data management system included

4.2.6 Recovery Beacon

Both balloon and gondola need to be equipped with a system that allows operators to locate them for recovery. Regular line-of-sight communication systems usually cannot be used for this purpose due to irregularities in the terrain that interrupt the line-of-sight. Additionally, the recovery beacon should use a system with compact and robust antennas that have a low likelihood of getting damaged or destroyed upon landing.

Argos

Prominently CNES, but also ASI, use the Argos tracking and monitoring system. Argos employs instruments on different low Earth orbiting satellites and offers standalone tracking / location identification of transmitters based on Doppler shift measurements and repetition period. Argos relies on active transmitters, but the transmitters are small and have very low power demand. Argos transmitters are frequently used for tracking of animals.

The Argos service can reach accuracies down to ca. 150 m horizontal radius in the best case, but does not provide altitude information. On the contrary, the horizontal accuracy is dependent on the accuracy of the assumed transmitter altitude. Argos can also be used to transmit small amounts of data to the satellites, however, such as GPS positions.

The coverage of Argos is worldwide, but not continuous. Polar regions are typically crossed 14 times per day, lower latitudes less often. This leads to the location data and messages often only being available on the Argos internet server two hours or more after transmission. Messages can also be received in real-time by Argos handheld receivers. CNES uses this method, combined with GPS position transmission via the Argos messages, for recovery of their balloons. A similar system is incorporated in the IRIASI system that was used by ASI [52].

Argos was established by CNES, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), and NASA and is operated by the CLS Group, a CNES subsidiary. The transmission frequency used is 401.65 MHz.

Iridium SBD

Another option for transmitting the GPS position determined by an on-board GPS receiver after landing is using one of the satellite communication channels that offer messaging services. The Iridium SBD service is well suited for this application and is used by CNES in the NOSYCA system for this purpose. Inmarsat satellite phone services, or any other satellite phone services with automatable hardware, could be used for this purpose as well.

4.3 SUMMARY OF OPERATIONAL FEASIBILITY

Based on the first iteration of the feasibility analysis as described above, it is sensible to review the functional requirements of ORISON (see [1]) and the decisions taken on trade-offs during the earlier phase of the project (see [1]). Taking into account the additional feasibility analysis, it might be helpful for the ORISON goal to adjust some of them for the next iteration. All conclusions are based on the three technical scenarios studied: *Orison Light*, *Orison Heavy*, and *Orison Infinity*.

RF1: Opportunity for Balloon Launches Once a Week

The analysis of suitable flight trajectories shows that providing opportunities for balloon launches once a week throughout the whole year is not an easy task and, from the perspective of operational effort, likely not desirable.

For *Orison Light* and *Orison Heavy*, at least in the Northern hemisphere, the conditions necessary for favorable flight trajectories only exist seasonally (for several weeks in spring and in late summer in case of turnaround conditions, for ca. 4.5 months during summer for boomerang flights). For *Orison Infinity*, the easterly stratospheric winds that allow flights to launch in Europe and land on the American continent equally only exist in summer (also for ca. 4.5 months). Long eastward flights from Europe are not desirable with the considered system mass, due to the high population density areas that would need to be overflown and due to expected political difficulties concerning overflight (overflight rights over Russia are not granted at the moment; more Southern trajectories risk flying over Iran) and fast recovery and return of payloads. Transatlantic flights from the American continent to Europe during (northern) winter might be an option, but would require a launch base on the American continent and further study.

In the Southern hemisphere, around-the-year flight opportunities for *Orison Light* and *Orison Heavy* might exist over Australia. This option would also require further study, however.

For a next iteration step, it may thus be beneficial to reduce RF1 to only aim at launching once a week during summer for flights in the northern hemisphere.

RF12: Downlinking of all Science Data Before Landing

As the communication system analysis showed, it is not possible to downlink all scientific data expected to be generated by an instrument such as the MCI with currently available S-band communication systems. It might be possible with Ka or Ku band systems, however, at the expense of additional power usage and, maybe more importantly, development effort.

It is thus recommended to consider only occasional downlink of scientific data while planning for sufficient protection and retrieval of the full data after landing.

RF14: Use of an Accessible Mid-Latitude Launch Site

Suitable candidate flight trajectories for *Orison Light* and *Orison Heavy* are available from mid-latitude sites in the Northern hemisphere, particularly from Spain and from Italy. While no active permanent balloon-base exists there at the moment, it does appear that launches could be carried out from the (at the moment closed) base on Sicily or from suitable airfields in Spain. It might be better to use an established base (such as Esrange) for the first flights, but an operational base in Spain or Italy seems realistic. The considered trajectory for *Orison Infinity* in the northern hemisphere would require launching in Kiruna (a second option might be Norway).

The possibility of launching *Orison Infinity* flights from more central or southern European sites pends further analysis of transatlantic trajectories from these sites.

4.4 ORISON PATHFINDER MISSIONS

ORISON will be a multi-purpose low-cost balloon program. During the development of the project several experiments have been carried out to check the feasibility of some of the science cases.

Among the tests carried out, we have tested two of the piggyback scientific cases as there are hundreds of possible low weight programs (<4 kg) that can benefit from this kind of platform. These two cases are the detection of meteors from the stratosphere and remote sensing of the earth at night.

One low weight experiment that was under development before the beginning of the ORISON project was a PRO-AM collaboration to detect meteors from the Stratosphere between the Departamento de Astrofísica y Ciencias de la Atmósfera of the Universidad Complutense de Madrid and the Daedalus Group. During the ORISON project, this collaboration has been expanded to the Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía and the Daedalus Group for the operation of the missions, and the analysis of the data carried out by the Departamento de Astrofísica y Ciencias de la Atmósfera of the Universidad Complutense de Madrid. In this section we present a summary of this program called “Orison Pathfinders” and its scientific results. The first section is part of the doctoral thesis of Francisco Ocaña [82], who has performed an analysis of the scientific potential of future stratospheric meteor research.

4.4.1 Meteor Observations from the Stratosphere

Above the troposphere the extinction is very limited, which allows us to increase the area surveyed and to maximize the detection rates of meteors. In order to reach the stratosphere, we study balloon-borne missions and the expected meteor detection performance in order to select the adequate instrumentation.

Since the end of the 18th century astronomers have been involved in balloon-borne observations.

The first observations were casual stargazing without instruments. And therefore one of the first phenomena to be observed was meteors and fireballs. The first account of a meteor sighting is as early as 1807 ([53], [54]), while the first observational campaigns were organized for the forecast storm of the Leonids 1899 [54]. Almost one hundred years later, the Leonids 1998 outburst was observed from a balloon with modern instruments [55]. Apart from balloon-borne campaigns, meteor storms have been studied in several airborne campaigns ([56], [57], [58]), but the cost of these is some orders of magnitude larger than low-cost balloon flights and they still suffer from some extinction [59].

In the last 6 years we have participated in a total of 11 nighttime missions. The scientific payloads for these stratospheric flights were designed for light pollution and meteor research. The first of these nighttime flights, Daedalus 2, took place in 2010 as an instrumental test to monitor light pollution. The same year a second flight over the city

of Jaén successfully took the first images for scientific use [60]. In 2014 the project was repeated over the city of Madrid, acquiring images of quality comparable to the ones from airborne instruments at a hundredth of the cost. The data of some of these missions for light pollution were used in the thesis of Sánchez de Miguel [61].

The other scientific objective of these night flights was the estimation of meteoroid influx at Earth through the observation of meteor showers. Observing meteors from the stratosphere improves detection efficiency thanks to much lower extinction and less background brightness. Other teams had already demonstrated the benefits of airborne observations for these objects. Thanks to the low cost of balloons and high-sensitivity cameras there is already a number of other groups using stratospheric balloons to record meteors ([62], [63]).

Since 2016 the payloads have flown on-board the ORISON Pathfinder missions.

Observing from the stratosphere yields larger effective area in comparison to ground level for all the usual values of the population index r . The analysis of this data confirms our hypothesis that the largest effective areas are surveyed from the stratosphere while pointing from the horizon up to 5 degrees of elevation. In order to select the instrumentation, we take into account the other constraints that arise from the observational platform:

- The instrument should have a large FoV (tens of degrees) in order to ensure that the desired pointing is achieved despite the movements. The first flights would be tests to determine the amplitude of the movements.
- The plate scale should minimize the spread of the light due to the movements of the pointing direction, therefore rotation speed of the probe should be in the range of the meteor relative speed. We calculate an average value for ω considering an average speed $V_{\infty} = 45$ km/s and $D_{\text{radiant}} = 45$ deg at 20 km and for an elevation of 0 deg over the horizon, which gives us $\omega \sim 0.03$ s⁻¹.
- From equation 3.23 for the usual video rate of 25 fps the resolution element should be 4 arcmin. For 50 fps it would be 2 arcmin. Therefore, the resolution element (pixel size or PSF) should be larger than those values to avoid trailing losses because of the light spreading. For fast short-focal lenses the PSF is going to be in the range of arcminutes as well, therefore the pixel size should be in the range of the PSF.
- At the same time the plate scale should be enough to allow accurate astrometric analysis. As for the cameras from Observatorio UCM we set the goal in the order of 7 arcmin/pixel, and at least better than 10 arcmin/pixel.

As discussed above, we need a video stable up to the angular speed of the meteors of 0.03 s⁻¹. The result for this configuration is that we consider it stable when the rotation rate of the balloon is under 1 rotation every 6 minutes (i.e., 1 deg/s or 0.017 s⁻¹).

Note that there is no available software to automatically process the video data even for airborne videos, as the meteor detection algorithms are based on the detection of changes in consecutive images. Several rounds of visual inspection proved to be the most effective way to count the number of meteors detected [64].

Quadrantids Campaign 2016. The weather was very bad on the Iberian Peninsula during the Quadrantids 2016, so the balloon observation could provide unique information. The launch took place at 01h42m UT of the 4th of January, under moderate wind and drizzle. Unfortunately, the mission ended prematurely due to a balloon malfunction, probably caused by the rain becoming ice and damaging the balloon. The flight was only 90 minutes long and the ground track was 150 km. Maximum height was 22 km, and the stable phase of the mission was limited to 7 minutes. Preliminary results confirm that 12 Quadrantids were recorded in these 7 minutes in the magnitude range from +1 to +6 ([65], [66]). Despite the reduced length of the period (according to the mission plan it should have been between 40 to 60 minutes), we could analyze the performance of the new color full-HD data.

The limiting magnitude of the frames was 6.5. More than 400 stars were detected, providing enough references for an astrometric resolution of 1 arcmin. In April 2016 and August 2016 we carried out another two missions to record the Lyrids meteor shower [67] and Perseid meteor shower respectively. The missions were successful and the analysis lead to some improvements of the instrument settings.

For the peak of the Geminids 2016 we carried out the last mission to the date and we have analyzed in detail the meteors recorded.

Geminids Campaign 2016. The Geminids annual meteor shower has been observed since the mid-1860s and is a very interesting stream because of its parent body: the asteroid 3200 Phaethon. Moreover, its level of activity in the last decades made it the most active of the annual showers, and therefore one of the better studied ones [68]. The meteoroids have larger bulk density than average, and the light curves of the Geminids agree with the single-body theory. The mechanism for the release of meteoroids from the asteroid surface is not completely understood, but thermal-fracture model and/or thermal decomposition of surface minerals when near perihelion are the most probable [69].

The flux density time profile was the main input to calculate the meteoroid stream mass in the 10^{16} to 10^{18} g range [70]. The flux density profile feeds the models to estimate the age and evolution of the stream [71]. Moreover, the Geminid stream is considered a potential meteorite-dropper stream [72] and therefore is monitored in detail by the Spanish Meteor & Fireball Network (SPMN).

The Geminids have a broad maximum centered at solar longitude 262:20, i.e. at 2 h UT in 2016. The mission was designed to observe at the maximum elevation of the radiant (located at $\alpha = 112$ deg, $\delta = +33$ deg in the sky). Ground-based observing conditions for the peak of Geminids in 2016 were bad because of the scattered moonlight (Moon

illuminated fraction >95%). This atmospheric scattering is produced by air-molecules and aerosols, consequently a balloon-borne mission is practically not affected by the moonlight.

The instrument used for this mission was a Sony 7S in video mode recording full-HD-1080p color frames (1920 x 1080 pixels), at 30 fps with 1/50 s exposure time and sensitivity of 60000 ISO. The lens is a Samyang with a focal length of 24 mm and f/number 1.5, which produces a slight vignetting in the corners of the full format chip.

We have analyzed the astrometry of the images splitting the video in all the frames, and each frame in the R, G, B channels. Using the suite astrometry.net [73], we calculated the plate constants. The plate scale of the system in video mode is 153 arcsec/pixel.

The measured PSF for the stars in the FoV has a full width half maximum (FWHM) of 460 arcsec on average, in the range of a critical sampling frequency according to the Nyquist theorem. The field of view is 82 deg x 46 deg with the center at $hf = 0$ deg.

In the beginning we mentioned that Geminid meteoroids penetrate more than other showers, and it indeed has a lower average middle point for meteors, on average it is $H=92$ km [74] but it is highly dependent on the absolute magnitude of the meteor. We calculate the average apparent magnitude of our meteors in order to estimate the expected middle point height. For a population with a population index $r=2.2$ and a limiting magnitude $lm=6.5$, we obtain an average magnitude of 2.3 [75]. The absolute average magnitude, considering the meteors are at a distance of 1000 km is -0.2. For that value we find a middle point height in the range of 80-90 km in the literature, so we chose $H = 85$ km.

The launch took place at 23h17m UT on the 13th of December 2016 and the burst took place at 01h50m UT. In total the mission lasted 276 minutes as the probe landed at 03h55m UT. The first visual inspection of the video shows stable and unstable phases. We have used the data from the 3-axis accelerators to identify these phases using the Lomb method for frequency analysis ([76], [77]). Along the whole mission we find a constant 1-second vertical tilt and 3 to 8-second roll movement (partial rotation along the optical axis). The other movement present is the rotation around the vertical axis of the probe, which results in a panning movement of the camera along the whole range of azimuth. The period of this movement changes during the different phases, and we define the stable phases when it is larger than 6 minutes, which corresponds to a movement of 1deg/s. This selection yields a useful period of 5 consecutive clips, for a total of 8 minutes and 40 seconds, from 01h40m UT on.

The video is analyzed by visual inspection and only the upper half of the frame is considered (elevation approx. 0 deg), yielding an effective field of view of 82 deg x 23 deg. For the meteor count we followed the visual analysis method as described in [64]. As Jenniskens states. the researcher only detects $70\% \pm 30\%$ during the first visualization, and up to 3 viewings were needed for our video clips. Star limiting

magnitude was calculated measuring frames in G band with V magnitudes from catalogue, and meteor magnitudes were derived by visual comparison with stars.

The star limiting magnitude is 6.0 for the period analyzed, and we get the same value for the meteor video limiting magnitude v_{lm} as the magnitude loss due to the meteor speed is < 0.1 magnitudes thanks to the slow speed of meteors when pointing to the horizon.

We used the algorithm introduced in the thesis of Francisco Ocaña [82] to calculate the density flux. The area monitored was 525729 km^2 and the correction factors yielded an effective area $A_{red} = 26110 \text{ km}^2$. For the full period we get an average value of $(15 \pm 3) 10^3$ meteoroids $\text{km}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$ producing meteors brighter than magnitude 6.5 (meteoroid mass $> 0.6 \text{ mg}$). There are no published results available for the Geminids 2016, but the shower is stable over years and we can compare with other values from literature for solar longitude 261.1 deg , which range between 15 to 60 meteoroids $\text{km}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$ ([78], [79], [80], [81]). Therefore, our results for the Geminids 2016 from balloon-borne observations are in agreement with the values from previous years.

4.4.2 Conclusions for Meteor Observation from the Stratosphere

Note: This chapter has been extracted from F. Ocaña's thesis [82].

Balloon-borne observations have proven to be an excellent solution for meteoroid flux determination, overcoming troposphere handicaps like weather or extinction. We have studied the practical implementation of the idea. First with a low-cost black and white camera that proved the concept and played the role of test-bed for our instrumental development for the stratosphere. And then with a professional camera that allowed us to calculate the meteoroid flux.

The lack of stabilization in the platform prevents the automatic analysis of the data and furthermore, it deteriorates the quality of the data when the rotation angular speed is larger than meteor angular speed, causing trailing losses. We have designed and tested instrumentation for balloon-borne missions, and analyzed the most stable part of the video of the Geminids 2016 campaign, providing for the first time flux density values from a balloon-borne Instrument.

In brief, interplanetary matter distribution models will benefit from more flux determination at different mass ranges from 1 AU and the results of this work constitute an important contribution to the instrumentation for this field.

The instrumental setups designed for meteors have been tested in real scenarios and have been used to calculate the particle fluxes for showcases. The balloon-borne campaign for flux determination is a break-through in meteor research.

5 LEGAL FEASIBILITY

Particularly when considering potential flight routes differing from the established ones, it is important to have a fundamental understanding of the underlying legal and regulatory restriction. A study on these topics was therefore conducted during the ORISON project, the results of which are presented in this chapter. They will help the ORISON consortium judge the feasibility of options and to judge the technical and formal effort associated with different options originating from regulations.

5.1 GENERAL FINDINGS

5.1.1 Findings with Regard to the Various Forms of Regulation

It is apparent that not all countries under current review have specific regulatory regime applicable to flights and uses of the stratospheric balloons or other types of balloons generally. In the majority of jurisdictions it is the generic legislative act (maybe called (Civil) Aviation Code, or (Civil) Aviation Act, or Code of Navigation) applicable to the aviation activities that defines the basic rules for flights and uses of any types of balloons. As a rule, such Acts are complemented by Rules and Regulations (again the exact names or titles may vary) that further detail the principles and overarching rules of the higher Act and establish the specific procedures that apply for carrying out of specific aviation activities, including flight and uses of balloons.

The rules regarding radio frequencies that may be used for specific communication services provided with the help of balloons are harmonized at the ITU and the regional level. At the national level, they are contained in specific regulatory sources, and the authorities responsible for radio spectrum use are different to those administering use of airspace in general, for flights or other purposes.

5.1.2 Findings with Regard to the Extent of Harmonization of the Content of Applicable Rules Across Jurisdictions Under Review

There is some degree of harmonized rules, above all due to the adherence of many countries to the Chicago Convention on International Civil Aviation and its Annex 2 that contains rules specifically applicable to balloons. In Europe, entry into force of the Regulation (EU) N° 923/2012 “Standardised Rules of the Air” contributed to further harmonization of applicable rules and procedures. However, due to the fact that in a number of jurisdictions there is not a specific act governing activities related to balloons flights and uses, the rules are to be looked for in various disconnected regulatory sources and it is not always easy to get a clear picture as to the set of principles and procedures governing activities related to balloons flights and uses.

5.2 FINDINGS REGARDING PARTICULAR AREAS

5.2.1 Common European Union Legislation

5.2.1.1 Restrictions on Stratospheric Balloon Flights in EU Countries

There is no sufficient definition for ‘stratospheric balloons’ in EU legal framework. Nevertheless, an ‘unmanned free balloon’ is defined as ‘a non-power driven, unmanned, lighter-than-air aircraft in free flight’ under Article 2, 138 EU No. 923/2012.

In Annex I (6) to the Draft Commission Regulation, ‘balloon’ is defined as ‘lighter-than-air aircraft which is not power-driven and sustains flight through the use of either gas or an airborne heater. For the purpose of this Regulation, balloons include gas balloons, hot-air balloons, mixed balloons and, although power-driven, hot-air airships’.

The main provisions regarding balloon flight and uses are to be found in EU No 923/2012 and its Annexes. As stated Art. 2, 138 defines the unmanned free balloon. In Annex I, Section 3, Chapter 1, SERA 3140 it is stated that an ‘unmanned free balloon shall be operated in such manner as to minimize hazards to persons, property or other aircraft and in accordance with the provisions specified in Appendix II’.

SERA is short for the Standardised European Rules of the Air. The right of way is set in SERA 3210 (c) (2) inter alia for balloons.

Appendix II (SERA) to EU No 923/2012 contains the provisions applicable for unmanned free balloons. First, Appendix II, 1 states that unmanned free balloons shall be classified in either (a) light, (b) medium or (c) heavy according to their payloads. A combined payload of less than 4kg qualifies as light, between 4kg and 6kg as medium and inter alia payload more than 6kg as heavy. This classification is followed by legal consequences stated in the SERA (e.g. notification to the appropriate air traffic services unit for heavy/medium balloons but not for light balloons).

1. CLASSIFICATION OF UNMANNED FREE BALLOONS under EU Regulation No 923/2012, Appendix II, 1.1

1.1 Unmanned free balloons shall be classified as (see Figure AP2-1¹):

- (a) light: an unmanned free balloon which carries a payload of one or more packages with a combined mass of less than 4 kg, unless qualifying as a heavy balloon in accordance with (c)(2),(3) or (4); or*
- (b) medium: an unmanned free balloon which carries a payload of two or more packages with a combined mass of 4 kg or more, but less than 6 kg, unless qualifying as a heavy balloon in accordance with (c)(2), (3) or (4) below; or*
- (c) heavy: an unmanned free balloon which carries a payload which:*
 - (1) has a combined mass of 6 kg or more; or*
 - (2) includes a package of 3 kg or more; or*
 - (3) includes a package of 2 kg or more with an area density of more than 13 g per square centimetre, determined by dividing the total mass in grams of the payload package by the area in square centimetres of its smallest surface; or*
 - (4) uses a rope or other device for suspension of the payload that requires an impact force of 230 N or more to separate the suspended payload from the balloon.*

Concerning the operational rules, Appendix II, 2.1 states that an unmanned free balloon shall not be operated without authorization from the State from which the launch is made.

¹ In the original document, EU Regulation No 923/2012, Appendix II, 1.1

2.1 An unmanned free balloon shall not be operated without authorisation from the State from which the launch is made (EU Regulation No 923/2012, Appendix II, 2.1).

Under Appendix II, 3, operational limitations and equipment requirements are set out. It is stated in which situations unmanned free balloons shall not be operated (missing flight-termination devices/systems for heavy classified balloons).

3. OPERATING LIMITATIONS AND EQUIPMENT REQUIREMENTS

- 3.1. A heavy unmanned free balloon shall not be operated without authorization from the ANSP(s) at or through any level below 18,000 m (60,000 ft) pressure-altitude at which: (a) there are clouds or obscuring phenomena of more than four oktas coverage; or (b) the horizontal visibility is less than 8 km.*
- 3.2. A heavy or medium unmanned free balloon shall not be released in a manner that will cause it to fly lower than 300 m (1,000 ft) over the congested areas of cities, towns or settlements or an open-air assembly of persons not associated with the operation.*
- 3.3. A heavy unmanned free balloon shall not be operated unless: (a) it is equipped with at least two payload flight-termination devices or systems, whether automatic or operated by telecommand, that operate independently of each other; (b) for polyethylene zero-pressure balloons, at least two methods, systems, devices, or combinations thereof, that function independently of each other are employed for terminating the flight of the balloon envelope;
(c) the balloon envelope is equipped with either a radar reflective device(s) or radar reflective material that will present an echo to surface radar operating in the 200 MHz to 2,700 MHz frequency range, and/or the balloon is equipped with such other devices as will permit continuous tracking by the operator beyond the range of ground-based radar.*
- 3.4. A heavy unmanned free balloon shall not be operated under the following conditions:
(a) in an area where ground-based SSR equipment is in use, unless it is equipped with a secondary surveillance radar transponder, with pressure-altitude reporting capability, which is continuously operating on an assigned code, or which can be turned on when necessary by the tracking station; or
(b) in an area where ground-based ADS-B equipment is in use, unless it is equipped with an ADS-B transmitter, with pressure-altitude reporting capability, which is continuously operating or which can be turned on when necessary by the tracking station.*
- 3.5. An unmanned free balloon that is equipped with a trailing antenna that requires a force of more than 230 N to break it at any point shall not be operated unless the antenna has coloured pennants or streamers that are attached at not more than 15 m intervals.*
- 3.6. A heavy unmanned free balloon shall not be operated below 18,000 m (60,000 ft) pressure-altitude at night or during any other period prescribed by the competent authority, unless the balloon and its attachments and payload, whether or not they become separated during the operation, are lighted.*

3.7. *A heavy unmanned free balloon that is equipped with a suspension device (other than a highly conspicuously coloured open parachute) more than 15 m long shall not be operated during night below 18,000 m (60,000 ft) pressure-altitude unless the suspension device is coloured in alternate bands of high conspicuity colours or has coloured pennants attached (EU Regulation No 923/2012, Appendix II, 3).*

In Appendix II, 4 it is set out in which situations the operator of a heavy unmanned free balloon shall activate the appropriate termination devices that are required under 3.

4. TERMINATION

4.1. *The operator of a heavy unmanned free balloon shall activate the appropriate termination devices required by 3.3(a) and (b):*

- (a) when it becomes known that weather conditions are less than those prescribed for the operation;*
- (b) if a malfunction or any other reason makes further operation hazardous to air traffic or to persons or property on the surface; or*
- (c) prior to unauthorised entry into the airspace over another State's territory. (EU Regulation No 923/2012, Appendix II, 4.)*

Important before the flight of an unmanned free balloon are the pre-flight notifications set out in App. II, 5. Such notification shall be made to the appropriate air traffic services unit not less than seven days before the date of the intended flight according to 5.1.1. This notification shall include inter alia the following information (required by the appropriate air traffic services unit according to 5.1.2.):

(a) balloon flight identification or project code name; (b) balloon classification and description; (c) SSR code, aircraft address or NDB frequency as applicable; (d) operator's name and telephone number; (e) launch site; (f) estimated time of launch (or time of commencement and completion of multiple launches); (g) number of balloons to be launched and the scheduled interval between launches (if multiple launches); (h) expected direction of ascent; (i) cruising level(s) (pressure-altitude).

Other than the pre-flight notification, immediately after a medium/heavy balloon is launched the operator shall notify the appropriate air traffic services unit with inter alia the following information according to 5.2.1:

(a) balloon flight identification; (b) launch site; (c) actual time of launch.

European operational rules for balloons are laid down in EU Regulation No 965/2012.^u This is not only for balloons but also technical requirements and administrative procedures relating to air operations for all aircraft. The regulation is criticised regarding balloons for different issues, such as: The regulation is too complex to handle with different parts and paragraphs for different balloon operations. Further some balloon issues are overregulated as they are simply downgraded from rules for large passenger

^u COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) No 965/2012 of 5 October 2012 laying down technical requirements and administrative procedures related to air operations pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 216/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council.

airplanes. Also it is not always clear whether rules are applicable to balloons. Inter alia for these reasons, the EASA proposed a revision of the European operational rules for balloons.^v With this opinion the EASA proposes the extraction of the operational rules for balloons from EU No 965/2012 with the goal of a single balloon book. With this draft regulation, the rules shall become less complex, maintain safety and reduce the regulatory burden to operators. Although EU No 379/2014^w amends EU No 965/2012 and adds more precision regarding to balloons there seems to be action required from EASA point of view.

5.2.1.2 Restrictions on Overflight of Stratospheric Balloons Launched in an EU Country

Under Appendix II, 2.2 SERA it is stated that a balloon shall not be operated across the territory of another State without the authorization from the other State concerned: “An unmanned free balloon, other than a light balloon used exclusively for meteorological purposes and operated in the manner prescribed by the competent authority, shall not be operated across the territory of another State without authorization from the other State concerned.” This authorization shall be obtained prior to the launching of the balloon (might also be obtained for a series of flights/particular type of recurring flight like atmospheric research balloon flights (2.3).

2.3 The authorization referred to in 2.2 shall be obtained prior to the launching of the balloon if there is reasonable expectation, when planning the operation, that the balloon may drift into airspace over the territory of another State. Such authorisation may be obtained for a series of balloon flights or for a particular type of recurring flight, e.g. atmospheric research balloon flights (EU Regulation No 923/2012, Appendix II, 2.3).

Further, an unmanned free balloon shall be operated in accordance with conditions specified by the State of Registry and the State(s) expected to be overflown according to 2.4 SERA.

2.4 An unmanned free balloon shall be operated in accordance with conditions specified by the State of Registry and the State(s) expected to be overflown (EU Regulation No 923/2012, Appendix II, 2.4).

A special permit for each member state is inter alia not needed if the aircraft is registered in a member state of the European Union and has airworthiness according to Art. 5 EC No.216/2008. The registration in a MS and airworthiness are general operation permits, excluding the need for a special permit when entering the airspace of a different MS.

^v European Aviation Safety Agency Opinion No 01/2016 - Revision of the European operational rules for balloons RELATED NPA/CRD: N/A — RMT.0674 — 6.1.2016.

^w Commission Regulation (EU) No 379/2014 of 7 April 2014 amending Commission Regulation (EU) No 965/2012 laying down technical requirements and administrative procedures related to air operations pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 216/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council.

5.2.1.3 Recovery of Stratospheric Balloons

EU No 379/2014 states under CAT.IDE.B.145 that balloons operated over areas in which search and rescue would be especially difficult shall be equipped with such signaling devices as appropriate to the area overflown.

CAT.IDE.B.145 Survival equipment

Balloons operated over areas in which search and rescue would be especially difficult shall be equipped with such signaling devices and life-saving equipment as appropriate to the area overflown (EU Regulation No 374/2014, CAT.IDE.B 145)

5.2.2 Regulations in Germany

5.2.2.1 Restrictions on Stratospheric Balloon Flights in Germany

In 2015 there was an estimated total of 30 918 balloon flights in Germany from which 24 600 were commercial and 6318 were non-commercial. There were 289 operators with 492 commercial balloons and 702 non-commercial balloons, making a total of 1194 balloons active in Germany in 2015.^x By these numbers, Germany had the most flights, number of balloons and operators from the EASA Member States in 2015. Additionally, about a quarter of flights from EASA Member States took place in Germany.

Generally stratospheric balloons are qualified as ‘free balloons’ other than ‘captive balloons’ that are both qualified as ‘aircraft’ under § 1(2)6 LuftVG^y (German Air Traffic Act). Stratospheric balloons fall under that qualification especially since spacecraft and rockets are also qualified as ‘aircraft’ as long as they are in airspace. The question of the demarcation between airspace and outer space comes into play, whereas this question is not resolved in German law. The Fédération Aéronautique Internationale (FAI) accepted the so called ‘Kármán line’ at 100km above sea level as boundary between the Earth’s atmosphere and outer space. Nevertheless, this is not relevant or binding in international law.

Other than in German law, EU Regulation No. 923/2012^z defines an ‘unmanned free balloon’ as ‘a non-power driven, unmanned, lighter-than-air aircraft in free flight’ under Art. 2, 138. According to §21(1)4 LuftVO^{aa} unmanned free balloons are classified in heavy and medium (§21(1)4. a) LuftVO) and light (§21(1)4. b) LuftVO). This is based on the classification in Appendix 2, 1.1 EU No. 923/2012 where there is a classification in light (a), medium (b) and heavy (c). The classification follows the payload. Payload

^x European Aviation Safety Agency Opinion No 01/2016 - Revision of the European operational rules for balloons RELATED NPA/CRD: N/A — RMT.0674 — 6.1.2016, 25.

^y Luftverkehrsgesetz (LuftVG) – Air Traffic Act, Version of 10 May 2007 (BGBl. I p. 698), amended 23 February 2017 (BGBl. I p. 298).

^z COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING REGULATION (EU) No 923/2012 of 26 September 2012 laying down the common rules of the air and operational provisions regarding services and procedures in air navigation and amending Implementing Regulation (EU) No 1035/2011 and Regulations (EC) No 1265/2007, (EC) No 1794/2006, (EC) No 730/2006, (EC) No 1033/2006 and (EU) No 255/2010.

^{aa} Luftverkehrsordnung (LuftVO) – Air Traffic Regulations, 29 October 2015 (BGBl. I p. 1894, amended 30 March 2017 (BGBl. I p. 683).

under 4kg (light), payload more than 4kg but less than 6kg (medium) and combined mass of more than 6kg (heavy). (for the details of the regulation, see section 5.2.1.1)

The most important entity/designated body responsible for dealing with issues regarding to balloons is the ‘Luftfahrt-Bundesamt’^{bb} (German Federal Aviation Authority). It is under the authority of the German Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure according to §1(1) LFBAG^{cc} and is primarily a technical examination office and regulatory authority according to §2 LFBAG. The granting of ascent permissions for free balloons is ‘Ländersache’ (governed by the Federal States) in Germany though. This is set out in § 31(2) LuftVG by being stated that the Federal States perform the tasks of the LuftVG on behalf of the federal government. These tasks include the granting of the use of the airspace for inter alia free- and captive balloons under §31(2)16e LuftVG. Unmanned aerospace systems/unmanned free balloons are subject to approval in Germany and an ascent permission is needed for every launch (in case of the system having a payload more than 0,5kg) according to §20 (1)8 LuftVO. The application for the ascent permission needs to be filed with the regional aviation authority (Landesluftfahrtbehörde) for each State and has to contain the following documents:

- informal application incl. names and address of the schedulers
- validation of safe handling with the system (not needed by all regional authorities)
- data sheet of the unmanned aerospace system
- justification of the necessity
- certificate of insurance
- data protection declaration (provided by the regional authority)
- date, time, operation site, duration of use, characteristics

Furthermore, an air traffic control clearance needs to be obtained from the Deutsche Flugsicherung (DFS)²⁶ (German Air Traffic Control). This is necessary for unmanned balloons with a total mass of more than 0,5kg. Two weeks prior to the launch the DFS demands information about the planned period of time, date of the ascent and exact place of the ascent (address/geographic coordinates). The application should further include the ascending rate, rate of descent, maximum height as well as technical data about the balloon itself. The application is free of costs.

As free balloons are qualified as ‘aircraft’ under §1(2)6 LuftVG, they need a permission for civilian air traffic according to §2(1) LuftVG. For that a type certification (§2(1)1 LuftVG), an evidence of traffic safety (§2(1)2 LuftVG) and a liability insurance (§2(1)3 LuftVG) is needed. Aircrafts that are not registered within the jurisdiction are only allowed to enter the German airspace if they have a permit. This permit is inter alia not

^{bb} Luftfahrt-Bundesamt, http://www.lba.de/DE/LBA/Aufgabe/Aufgaben_node.html.

^{cc} Gesetz über das Luftfahrt-Bundesamt (LFBAG) – Act on the German Federal Aviation Authority, 30 November 1954 (BGBl. I p. 354), amended 23 February 2017 (BGBl. I p. 298).

needed if the aircraft is registered in a member state of the European Union and has airworthiness according to Art. 5 EC No.216/2008.^{dd}

1. *Aircraft referred to in Article 4(1)(a), (b) and (c) shall comply with the essential requirements for airworthiness laid down in Annex I.*
2. *Compliance of aircraft referred to in Article 4(1)(b), and of products, parts and appliances mounted thereon shall be established in accordance with the following:*
 - (a) *products shall have a type-certificate. The type-certificate, and certification of changes to that type-certificate, including supplemental type-certificates, shall be issued when the applicant has shown that the product complies with a type-certification basis as specified in Article 20, established to ensure compliance with the essential requirements referred to in paragraph 1, and when it has no feature or characteristic making it unsafe for operation. The type-certificate shall cover the product, including all parts and appliances fitted thereon.*

5.2.2.2 Restrictions on Overflight of Stratospheric Balloons Launched from other Countries

Companies or other entities from member states of the European Economic Area (EEA) have to apply for an entry permit for commercial flights for ‘other purposes’. Other purposes include inter alia balloon rides. The application is an informal application that needs to be requested at least two days prior to the approach to Germany. The application has to include information about the purpose of the overflight, the planned date as well as start location and planned landing site. Just as for the ascent permission, the application for an entry permit needs to be filed with the regional aviation authority.

As to requirements (technical, certification), aircrafts that are not registered within the jurisdiction of the LuftVG are only allowed to enter the German airspace if they have a permit. This permit is inter alia not needed if the aircraft is registered in a member state of the European Union and has airworthiness according to Art. 5 EC No.216/2008.

5.2.2.3 Recovery of Stratospheric Balloons

It is important to acknowledge that it is not predictable where balloons/components land. In Germany §25(1) LuftVG states that aircrafts can only land other than on their approved airfield if they have a permission by the property owner and the aviation authority. This general permission to land is not needed if the location of landing is not predictable due to the characteristics of the aircraft according to §25(2) LuftVG. This is especially the case with balloons. Therewith balloons have a general permission to land. The owner of the property is then entitled to receive information regarding name and place of residence of the owner and insurance of the aircraft (balloon). After being given this information the property owner is not allowed to block the recovery of the balloon

^{dd} REGULATION (EC) No 216/2008 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 20 February 2008 on common rules in the field of civil aviation and establishing a European Aviation Safety Agency, and repealing Council Directive 91/670/EEC, Regulation (EC) No 1592/2002 and Directive 2004/36/EC.

in any way. This means there are no restrictions to access and recover landed balloons/components when the owner information is given.

5.2.2.4 Radiofrequencies and Telecommunications Provisions

The designated body in Germany dealing with radio frequency issues is the ‘Bundesnetzagentur’ (Federal Network Agency).^{ee} It is a federal government agency of the German Ministry of Economics and Technology and is the regulatory office for electricity, gas, telecommunications, post and railway markets. The Telecommunications Act (TKG)^{ff} deals with frequencies and its allocation, as in §57 TKG, where the frequency allocation for broadcasting, aviation and shipping is established.

5.2.2.5 Impact of EU Regulation No 923/2012

As can be seen, § 20(1)8 the German Air Traffic Regulations (LuftVO) refers to EU Regulation No 923/2012, Appendix II (SERA) with unmanned free balloons needing permission for the operation:

(1) Die folgenden Arten der Nutzung des Luftraums bedürfen im Übrigen der Erlaubnis:
8. *der Betrieb von unbemannten Freiballonen nach Anlage 2 der Durchführungsverordnung (EU) Nr. 923/2012 im Hoheitsgebiet der Bundesrepublik Deutschland.*

It can be seen that the provisions of EU Reg. No 923/2012, Appendix II are followed in LuftVO. Further, §21(1)4 LuftVO (classification of unmanned free balloons) follows Appendix 2, 1. of EU Reg. No 923/2012 (SERA) with slight changes. In the German LuftVO there is a classification in heavy and medium (§21(1)4 (a) LuftVO) and light (§21(1)4 (b) LuftVO) whereas SERA classifies in light (1.1 a.), medium (1.1 b.) and heavy (1.1 c.). Still it can be seen that SERA provision are being followed both in the LUftVG (Air Traffic Act) and LuftVO (Air Traffic Regulations).

5.2.3 Regulations in Spain

5.2.3.1 Restrictions on Stratospheric Balloon Flights in Spain

In Spain, since 4 December 2014, air regulations and common operational provisions for air navigation services and procedures are set out in Royal Decree 552/2014 of 27 June. This decree adopts the implementing and development provisions of SERA in those areas in which the Community rule allows scope for action by the Member States.

^{ee} Bundesnetzagentur,
<https://www.bundesnetzagentur.de/DE/Allgemeines/DieBundesnetzagentur/UeberdieAgentur/ueberdieagentur-node.html>.

^{ff} Telekommunikationsgesetz (TKG) – Telecommunications Act, 22 June 2004 (BGBl. I p. 1190), amended 13 April 2017 (BGBl. I p. 872).

As of the 4th of December 2014 the Regulation (EU) N° 923/2012 “Standardised Rules of the Air” (SERA) shall be effective within Spain, in accordance with Article 11 of SERA Regulation and Royal Decree 552/2014.

Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) N° 923/2012 of 26 September 2012 laying down the common rules of the air and operational provisions regarding services and procedures in air navigation (SERA) has been jointly developed by Eurocontrol, the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) on behalf of the European Commission and the EU Member States.

It is intended to introduce a harmonized set of operational rules of air when flying in European airspace. SERA is based on International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) requirements.

Furthermore, this Royal Decree whereby develops the Rules of the Air and the common operational arrangements for services and air navigation procedures develops and modifies the Royal Decree 57/2002 of 18 January, by which approves the Air Traffic Regulation, complete national regulation in those matters that SERA allows the Member States to develop and regulate and also adapts the national legislation on other matters relating to air navigation and already regulated by EU regulations.

This way, as of the 4th of December 2014, SERA in conjunction with the Royal Decree allows to have a single, integrated, and harmonized regulatory framework with European Union provisions on air traffic, taking a further step towards the regulatory convergence established at the Single European Sky initiative.

This Royal Decree does not regulate activities with unmanned free balloons, leaving the provisions of the SERA to regulate these activities in Spain. Therefore, since December 2014, all activities that require unmanned free balloons, must comply with the provisions of SERA.

It is important to clarify that there is not a specific regulation for stratospheric balloons, but there is for unmanned free balloons. Therefore, this entire research will always refer to unmanned free balloons.

According to the Royal Decree 384/2015^{gg}, of 22 May, which approves the Regulations for the registration of civil aircraft, unmanned free balloons are those aerostats not capable of being manned or controlled.

According to the Order FOM / 1687/2015, of July 30, establishing additional provisions on the marks of nationality and registration of civil aircraft, unmanned aircrafts include unmanned free balloons.

Before we see the existing restrictions on unmanned free balloons, we need to know how they are classified. As mentioned before all activities carried out in Spain that require unmanned free balloons, must comply with the provisions of SERA. According to SERA Appendix II, unmanned free balloons are classified in three different categories: light, medium, and heavy (for the detailed criteria, see section 5.2.1.1.).

^{gg} (See Chapter I, Art. 3 h) Real Decreto 384/2015.)

5.2.3.2 Restrictions on Overflight of Stratospheric Balloons

There are different restrictions depending on the altitude of unmanned free balloons^{hh}. Most of these restrictions are focused on heavy and medium balloons. Apparently, for light unmanned free balloons there are no restrictions depending on the altitude.

We can find two main restrictions depending on the altitude:

The first restriction establishes that a heavy unmanned free balloon shall not be operated without authorisation from the ANSP(s)ⁱⁱ at or through any level below 18,000 m (60,000 ft) pressure-altitude at which: there are clouds or obscuring phenomena of more than four oktas^{jj} coverage; or the horizontal visibility is less than 8 km. It is important to highlight that this restriction only applies for heavy unmanned free balloons.

The second restriction applies for heavy and medium unmanned free balloons and says that a heavy or medium unmanned free balloon shall not be released in a manner that will cause it to fly lower than 300 m (1,000 ft) over the congested areas of cities, towns or settlements or an open-air assembly of persons not associated with the operation.

There are three different rules on the equipment that unmanned free balloons must carry^{kk}. These rules only apply for heavy unmanned free balloons and if they are not met, a heavy unmanned free balloons shall not be operated.

A heavy unmanned free balloon shall not be operated unless:

- It is equipped with at least two payload flight-termination devices or systems, whether automatic or operated by telecommand, that operate independently of each other;
- For polyethylene zero-pressure balloons, at least two methods, systems, devices, or combinations thereof, that function independently of each other are employed for terminating the flight of the balloon envelope;
- The balloon envelope is equipped with either a radar reflective device(s) or radar reflective material that will present an echo to surface radar operating in the 200 MHz to 2,700 MHz frequency range, and/or the balloon is equipped with such other devices as will permit continuous tracking by the operator beyond the range of ground-based radar.

There are two areas where an unmanned free balloon shall not be operated^{ll}: an area where ground-based SSR equipment^{mmm} is in use and an area where ground-based ADS-B equipmentⁿⁿⁿ is in use. Although, there are exceptions in the restrictions of these areas that would allow to carry out activities with unmanned free balloons.

^{hh} See Appendix 2, Art. 3.3, Regulation (UE) N. 923/2012.

ⁱⁱ An air navigation service provider (ANSP) is a public or a private legal entity providing Air Navigation Services. It manages air traffic on behalf of a company, region or country.

^{jj} A unit used in meteorology to measure cloud cover, equivalent to a cloud cover of one eighth of the sky.

^{kk} See Appendix 2, Art. 3.3, Regulation (UE) N. 923/2012.

^{ll} (See Appendix 2, Art. 3.4, Regulation (UE) N. 923/2012)

^{mmm} Secondary surveillance radar (SSR) is a radar system used in air traffic control (ATC), that not only detects and measures the position of aircraft i.e. bearing, but also requests additional information from the aircraft itself such as its identity and altitude.

ⁿⁿⁿ Automatic dependent surveillance – broadcast (ADS-B) is a surveillance technology in which an aircraft determines its position via satellite navigation and periodically broadcasts it, enabling it to be tracked. The

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- A heavy unmanned free balloon shall not be operated in an area where ground-based SSR equipment is in use, unless it is equipped with a secondary surveillance radar transponder, with pressure-altitude reporting capability, which is continuously operating on an assigned code, or which can be turned on when necessary by the tracking station.
 - A heavy unmanned free balloon shall not be operated in an area where ground-based ADS-B equipment is in use, unless it is equipped with an ADS-B transmitter, with pressure-altitude reporting capability, which is continuously operating or which can be turned on when necessary by the tracking station.

In addition, there are three extra regulations that are a combination between altitude and equipment:

- An unmanned free balloon that is equipped with a trailing antenna that requires a force of more than 230 N to break it at any point shall not be operated unless the antenna has coloured pennants or streamers that are attached at not more than 15 m intervals^{oo}.
- A heavy unmanned free balloon shall not be operated below 18,000 m (60,000 ft) pressure-altitude at night or during any other period prescribed by the competent authority, unless the balloon and its attachments and payload, whether or not they become separated during the operation, are lighted^{pp}.
- A heavy unmanned free balloon that is equipped with a suspension device (other than a highly conspicuously coloured open parachute) more than 15 m long shall not be operated during night below 18,000 m (60,000 ft) pressure-altitude unless the suspension device is coloured in alternate bands of high conspicuity colours or has coloured pennants attached^{qq}.

Before launching a free unmanned balloon, a number of notifications must be made. These notices apply only to medium and heavy unmanned free balloons. No mention is made of light balloons.

There are three different types of notifications:

- The first is the notification that must be made prior to the flight. (pre-flight notification)
- The second consists of the launch notification of the balloon. (notification of launch)

These two are mandatory.

- The third, annulment notification, should only be carried out if the release of a medium or heavy balloon is to be cancelled. (Notification of cancelation)

Early notification of the intended flight of an unmanned free balloon in the medium or heavy category shall officially be made to the appropriate air traffic services unit not less

information can be received by air traffic control ground stations as a replacement for secondary radar. It can also be received by other aircraft to provide situational awareness and allow self-separation.

^{oo} See Appendix 2, Art. 3.5, Regulation (UE) N. 923/2012

^{pp} See Appendix 2, Art. 3.6, Regulation (UE) N. 923/2012

^{qq} See Appendix 2, Art. 3.7, Regulation (UE) N. 923/2012

than seven days before the date of the intended flight^{tr}. Since 2016, the Spanish authorities have indicated, however, that processing of notifications can only be guaranteed if they are made at least 20 days in advance of the flight.

This notification shall include the following information, which can be requested by the Spanish air authorities:

- a) balloon flight identification or project code name;
- b) balloon classification and description;
- c) SSR code, aircraft address or NDB^{ss} frequency as applicable;
- d) operator's name and telephone number;
- e) launch site;
- f) estimated time of launch (or time of commencement and completion of multiple launches);
- g) number of balloons to be launched and the scheduled interval between launches (if multiple launches);
- h) expected direction of ascent;
- i) cruising level(s) (pressure-altitude);
- j) the estimated elapsed time to pass 18,000 m (60,000 ft) pressure-altitude or to reach cruising level if at or below 18,000 m (60,000 ft), together with the estimated location. If the operation consists of continuous launchings, the time to be included shall be the estimated time at which the first and the last in the series will reach the appropriate level (e.g. 122136Z–130330Z);
- k) the estimated date and time of termination of the flight and the planned location of the impact/recovery area. In the case of balloons carrying out flights of long duration, as a result of which the date and time of termination of the flight and the location of impact cannot be forecast with accuracy, the term 'long duration' shall be used. If there is to be more than one location of impact/recovery, each location shall be listed together with the appropriate estimated time of impact. If there is to be a series of continuous impacts, the time to be included shall be the estimated time of the first and the last in the series (e.g. 070330Z–072300Z).

If there is any possible change in the pre-launch information, the balloon operator shall forward this change to the air traffic services unit concerned not less than 6 hours before the estimated time of launch, or in the case of solar or cosmic disturbance investigations involving a critical time element, not less than 30 minutes before the estimated time of the commencement of the operation.

After a free unmanned balloon is launched, its operator shall notify the Spanish air authorities with this information^{tt}:

^{tr} See Appendix 2, Art. 5.1, Regulation (UE) N. 923/2012

^{ss} A non-directional (radio) beacon (NDB) is a radio transmitter at a known location, used as an aviation or marine navigational aid. As the name implies, the signal transmitted does not include inherent directional information, in contrast to other navigational aids such as low frequency radio range, VHF omnidirectional range (VOR) and TACAN. NDB signals follow the curvature of the Earth, so they can be received at much greater distances at lower altitudes, a major advantage over VOR.

^{tt} See Appendix 2, Art. 5.2, Regulation (UE) N. 923/2012

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- balloon flight identification;
 - launch site;
 - actual time of launch;
 - estimated time at which 18,000 m (60,000 ft) pressure-altitude will be passed, or the estimated time at which the cruising level will be reached if at or below 18,000 m (60,000 ft), and the estimated location; and
 - any changes to the information previously notified.

Once again, this obligation to notify the authorities applies only for medium and heavy balloons.

If the launch of a medium or heavy unmanned free balloon has been cancelled, the operator shall notify the Spanish air authorities immediately^{uu}.

Unmanned free balloons, whose maximum take-off weight is less than 6 kg are exempt from the registration requirement in the Aircraft Registration^{vv}.

This means that light and medium unmanned free balloons are exempt from being registered. However, this exemption does not apply always to heavy unmanned free balloons, since its definition includes different weight conditions. Any unmanned free balloon that exceeds the weight of 6 kg must be registered according to the Royal Decree 384/2015, of 22 May, which approves the Regulations for the registration of civil aircraft.

5.2.3.3 Recovery of Balloons

If we talk about the surface that travels an unmanned free balloon that has been launched from Spain, we find a series of obligations that the operator of the balloon has to follow. These obligations come from section 6, Appendix 2 of SERA and apply in the Spanish Air regulation. All the operators of a heavy unmanned free balloon shall be aware of their duties regarding the tracking and recording of the unmanned free balloon and also the continuous provision of information regarding the balloon.

Some of these obligations only apply to heavy unmanned free balloons. Others, apply for both heavy and medium unmanned free balloons. However, it seems that operators of a light unmanned free balloon have no obligation to track it.

If a heavy unmanned free balloon is flying at or below 18,000 m (60,000 ft) pressure-altitude the operator shall monitor the flight path of the balloon and forward reports of the balloon's position as requested by air traffic services. Unless air traffic services require reports of the balloon's position at more frequent intervals, the operator shall record the position every 2 hours^{ww}.

In case a heavy unmanned free balloon is flying above 18,000 m (60,000 ft) pressure-altitude, the operator shall monitor the flight progress of the balloon and forward reports

^{uu} See Appendix 2, Art. 5.3, Regulation (UE) N. 923/2012

^{vv} See Chapter I, Art. 3, Real Decreto 384/2015, de 22 de mayo, por el que se aprueba el Reglamento de matriculación de aeronaves civiles

^{ww} See Appendix 2, Art. 6.1, Regulation (UE) N. 923/2012

of the balloon's position as requested by air traffic services. The operator shall record the position of the balloon every 24 hours^{xx}.

If in the two previous cases the position cannot be recorded the operator shall immediately notify the appropriate air traffic services unit. This notification shall include the last recorded position. The appropriate air traffic services unit shall be notified immediately when tracking of the balloon is re-established^{yy}.

Only operators of heavy unmanned free balloons beginning the descent are obliged to forward to the appropriate air traffic services unit the following information regarding the balloon:

- the current geographical position;
- the current level (pressure-altitude);
- the forecast time of penetration of 18,000 m (60,000 ft) pressure-altitude, if applicable;
- the forecast time and location of ground impact. This information shall be forward one hour before the beginning of planned descent.

The operator of a heavy or medium unmanned free balloon shall notify the appropriate air traffic services unit when the operation is ended.

In Spain there is no specific regulation for the recovery of fallen unmanned free balloons. However, there is general regulation applicable to all aircraft. As we have seen before, unmanned free balloons have to be considered unmanned aircraft, therefore this regulation should be applied in case of unmanned free balloon accident.

This general regulation is called Law 48/1960, Navegación Aérea (Air Navigation) and in its articles 134-141 regulates the procedure to follow in the event of an accident.

The assistance and rescue of injured or endangered aircraft are of public interest. They will be carried out under the direction of the aeronautical authorities, who will also be responsible for the investigation and determination of responsibilities in the case of accidents^{zz}. The discovery of an abandoned aircraft or its remains shall be notified to the owner^{aaa}, if known, and shall be returned to the latter, after payment of the legitimate expenses, plus a prize of one third of its value to the discoverer. The aircraft or its remains shall be considered abandoned when it is unmanned and it is not possible to determine its legitimate ownership by the aircraft's documents, registration marks or other means of identification, or when the owner expressly expresses his desire to abandon the aircraft.

5.2.3.4 Other Regulations

According to the Spanish Air Traffic Regulation, when a medium or heavy unmanned free balloon is expected to cross international boundaries, the relevant ATS^{bbb} unit will

^{xx} See Appendix 2, Art. 6.2, Regulation (UE) N. 923/2012

^{yy} See Appendix 2, Art. 6.3, Regulation (UE) N. 923/2012

^{zz} See Chapter XVI, Art 134, Law 48/1960, Navegación Aérea

^{aaa} See Chapter XVI Art 137, Law 48/1960, Navegación Aérea

^{bbb} Air traffic service (ATS) is a service which regulates and assists aircraft in real-time to ensure their safe operations.

take the necessary steps to ensure that pre-launch and post-launch notifications are sent to the ATS unit or units of the State (s) concerned. by using a NOTAM.

A Notice to Airmen (NOTAM) is a notice filed with an aviation authority to alert aircraft pilots of potential hazards along a flight route or at a location that could affect the safety of the flight. NOTAMs are unclassified notices or advisories distributed by means of telecommunication that contain information concerning the establishment, conditions or change in any aeronautical facility, service, procedure or hazard, the timely knowledge of which is essential to personnel and systems concerned with flight operations. NOTAMs are created and transmitted by government agencies and airport operators under guidelines specified by Annex 15: Aeronautical Information Services of the Convention on International Civil Aviation (CICA).

If there is an agreement between the Spanish State and other States, the launch notification may be transmitted orally by direct ATS radiotelephone circuits between the area control centres or flight information centres of the case.

The air traffic services units shall maintain radar surveillance of heavy and medium unmanned free balloons as far as possible and, if necessary, the request of the pilot of an aircraft shall provide for the separation of aircraft and balloons identified by radar or whose exact location is known.

There is a draft of a Royal Decree that develops the Air Regulation and Common operational provisions for Air navigation and amending Royal Decree 57/2002, of 18 January, by which approves the Regulation of Aerial Circulation.

The main goal of this Royal Decree is to introduce the necessary changes to the National legislation to bring it into line with the amendments made by SERA, as well as others as a result of the application of the current provisions of SERA.

There are several novelties in this decree. Some of them are the following ones:

It establishes a general regime for unmanned free balloons launches. The release of unmanned free balloons shall be conducted at a minimum distance of 8 km from the aerodrome reference point published in the Publication of Aeronautical Information (AIP) and outside the zone of easements Aeronautics, unless expressly coordinated with the manager or responsible for the Aeronautical infrastructure and, where applicable, subject to the application of Procedures for the identification and management of risks through the Human activities or land use in the airport environment. For this purpose, whoever intends to launch or release in these areas shall inform the infrastructure manager or manager, prior to the carrying out the activity.

Another important and necessary novelty is the operational coordination of the air traffic service provider. The launching of medium or heavy unmanned free balloons will be subject to the operational coordination by ENAIRE. The launching of a light unmanned free balloon will be subject to the operational coordination by ENAIRE only when it is launched in a Controlled Traffic Region, Aerodrome Traffic Zone or in a Flight Information Zone close to an airport.

ENAIRE is also in charge of the establishment of the forms to be completed by those responsible for the launch, as well as the coordination procedures and those whose purpose is to establish the conditions that avoid hazards for aircraft operating in accordance with the rules of general or operational air traffic.

This Royal Decree introduce a clear distinction for unmanned free balloons launched for

meteorological activities. If a meteorological office based on an airport launches an unmanned free balloon, it will not have to comply with the minimum distance mentioned before.

In October 2016, Spain, Portugal, France and Germany reached an agreement that would mean safer, more sustainable and more efficient air traffic management in their airspace. The agreement has been made through the companies that manage en-route air navigation in these four countries. ENAIRE (Spain), NAV (Portugal), DSNA (France) and DFS (Germany) have set up a joint working group to analyze the long-range direct routes through the airspace of the Madrid, Lisbon and Brest control centers, extending to the German airspace of Karlsruhe. This agreement will allow airline pilots and airlines to conduct more direct routes regardless of national borders in order to increase the quality of service and reduce travel time and lower operating costs of the flight. However, there is no reference to balloons in this agreement.

5.2.3.5 Radiofrequencies and Telecommunications Provision

The radio electric spectrum is a public domain property^{ccc}, whose ownership, management, planning, administration and control correspond to the State. Such management shall be carried out in accordance with the provisions of this title and the international treaties and agreements to which Spain is a party, in accordance with the rules applicable in the European Union and the resolutions and recommendations of the International Telecommunication Union and other bodies Countries.

For civil uses related to aerial activities such as balloons, the following frequency bands are reserved^{ddd}:

122,000 - 123,050 MHz

123,150 - 123,675 MHz

129,700 - 130,875 MHz

5.2.4 Regulations in Italy

5.2.4.1 Restrictions on Stratospheric Balloon Flights in Italy

Applicable Italian regulatory sources use the term balloons (palloni), without providing any definition thereof. The Code of Navigation^{eee} contemplates instead, in its second part dedicated to air navigation (Della navigazione aerea) a definition of airmobile within which balloons fall.

Under the title “Nozione di aeromobile” art. 743 states that:

“Per aeromobile si intende ogni macchina destinata al trasporto per aria di persone o cose. [...] Le distinzioni degli aeromobili, secondo le loro caratteristiche tecniche e

^{ccc} See Preamble, Ley 9/2014 General de Telecomunicaciones.

^{ddd} See UN - 102 Usos civiles del servicio móvil aeronáutico (OR), Orden IET/787/2013, Cuadro nacional de atribución de frecuencias.

^{eee} The Code of navigation was approved with R.D. 30 March 1942, n. 327, and modified in 2006, with legislative decree n. 151.

secondo il loro impiego, sono stabilite dall'ENAC con propri regolamenti e, comunque, dalla normativa speciale in materia”.

According to this article, being it manned or not, every machine is an airmobile as long as it is intended to transport by air people or things. Apparently, this definition is broad enough to encompass balloons.

It is possible to deduce that those Code of Navigation norms which apply to airmobiles in general, they also apply to balloons, unless special norms have been enacted. Indeed, according to the principle *lex specialis derogat generali*, in case of antinomy the rules which specifically apply to balloons prevail against the rules which in general apply to airmobiles. Given the great amount of special regulation enacted so far^{fff}, the application of the Code of Navigation to balloons ends up to be a residual hypothesis. The second part of the article says that the distinctions between airmobiles, according to their technical features and their use, are established through regulations by the National Authority for Civil Aviation (Ente Nazionale per l'Aviazione Civile, ENAC) and, in any case, through those special norms which already exist in the subject matter. ENAC is indeed the authority in charge to regulate, to issue certifications and to carry out the necessary control in the sector of civil aviation in Italy^{ggg}. It is also competent for the registration of airmobiles, including balloons^{hhh}.

Although the present report is focused on the Italian legal order, one needs to keep in mind that a relevant part of the balloons regulation is enacted at the European Union level, and as such it is binding upon all EU Member States, including Italyⁱⁱⁱ. Contrarily to Italian law, EU law also offers a specific definition of balloon as “a lighter-than-air aircraft which is not engine-driven and sustains flight through the use of either gas or an airborne heater”ⁱⁱⁱ.

Worth of note, in a *de iure condendo* perspective, a proposal of the European Aviation Safety Agency “to establish a simpler, ‘lighter’ and proportionate air operations regulatory framework for balloons”, in short a single EU “balloon book”^{kkk}. In EU law

^{fff} See *infra*

^{ggg} ENAC was established on 25 July 1997 with legislative decree n. 250/97.

^{hhh} Art. 750 Code of Navigation

ⁱⁱⁱ It is so in particular as far as the EU regulations is concerned. Indeed, according to art. 288 TFEU, a regulation “shall have general application. It shall be binding in its entirety and directly applicable in all Member States”.

For example, the technical requirements and procedures related to civil aviation aircrew is established by a EU Commission regulation. See Commission regulation (EU) No 1178/2011 of 3 November 2011 laying down technical requirements and procedures related to civil aviation aircrew pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 216/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council, as amended by 290/2012, 70/2014 and 245/2014.

Italian legislation regulating licensing, which is not covered by Regulation (EU) 1178/2011 (with its amendments), refers to: DPR 566 of 1988 and DM 467/T of 1992. This national legislation only remains in force for the purpose of obtaining *inter alia* a pilot license for free balloons.

^{jjj} FCL.010 (Definitions), Commission Regulation (EU) No 1178/2011 of 3 November 2011 laying down technical requirements and administrative procedures related to civil aviation aircrew pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 216/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council

^{kkk} European Aviation Safety Agency Opinion No 01/2016 Revision of the European operational rules for balloons. Related NPA/CRD: N/A — RMT.0674 — 6.1.2016

as it stands, indeed, many operational rules for balloons are “downgraded”, e.g. from the rules for large passenger aeroplanes. This resulted in an overregulation for balloons which, compared to large passenger aeroplanes for example, are simple aircraft. Furthermore, from the way the rules are written it is not always clear whether they are applicable to balloons, and in cases they are, to which extent.

5.2.4.2 Restrictions on Overflight of Stratospheric Balloons

ENAC defines the national air space as a common resource which as such necessarily has to be managed according to appropriate procedures, taking into consideration the needs of all concerned entities, administrations, organizations and users (circular ATM-03)^{lil}. Circular ATM-03 specifies that one of the fundamental principles regulating the subject matter is the safeguard of the flexible use of airspace, in compliance with the explicitly recalled Commission Regulation (EC) No 2150/2005 of 23 December 2005 laying down common rules for the flexible use of airspace^{mmmm}. It implies that the needs of users, being them civil or military, shall be satisfied to the greatest extent possibleⁿⁿⁿ.

Against this general principle, however, specific exceptions may be adopted. According to art. 793 of the Code of Navigations, ENAC can impose restrictions on the use of certain areas of the airspace for reasons of security, military, or public order, and this norm represents the legal basis for whatever restriction ENAC adopts on the use of the airspace, including the ones which are adopted for operative reasons of safety of air operations.

In order to coordinate air traffic ENAC, in virtue of its regulatory powers, has issued a number of regulations, and some of them apply to balloons. The result of an overall assessment is that the use of balloons is regulated in a detailed, although fragmentary and sometimes confused manner. It is preliminarily necessary to draw a distinction between tethered balloons and free balloons, free balloons then may be unmanned or manned: every category of balloons is submitted to a special regulation^{ooo}.

ENAC has issued a regulation which is specifically applicable to tethered balloons (in Italian palloni frenati): Norme tecniche e condizioni di esercizio per palloni frenati destinati al trasporto di persone (Technical regulations and operating conditions for tethered balloons used for the transport of people)^{ppp}, while regulation Certificato di operatore aereo per imprese di trasporto aereo di passeggeri con palloni liberi ad aria

^{lil} Circular ATM-03B, Istituzione, modifica o cancellazione di zone soggette a restrizioni, adopted on 15 December 2016, (Serie Air Traffic Management).

^{mmmm} Commission Regulation (EC) No 2150/2005 of 23 December 2005 laying down common rules for the flexible use of airspace, OJ L 342, 24.12.2005, pp. 20–25.

ⁿⁿⁿ Circular ATM-03B, *ibidem*, par. 5.1.

^{ooo} These distinctions are also relevant at the EU level. For example, Commission Regulation (EU) No 965/2012 applies *inter alia* to air operations with balloons, but it excludes tethered balloons from its scope of application (art. 1). See Commission Regulation (EU) No 965/2012 of 5 October 2012 laying down technical requirements and administrative procedures related to air operations pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 216/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council (OJ L 296, 25.10.2012, p. 1)

^{ppp} Norme tecniche e condizioni di esercizio per palloni frenati destinati al trasporto di persone, adopted with Delibera Consiglio di Amministrazione n. 14/99, 23 June 1999).

calda (Certificate of Air Operator for transport companies of passengers through hot air free balloons) sets out the norms which apply to manned free balloons^{qqq}.

Finally, as far as unmanned free balloons is concerned, the general framework is provided by Annex 2 to the Chicago Convention on International Civil Aviation, and by the Regulations of the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) No 923/2012 of 26 September 2012 laying down the common rules of the air and operational provisions regarding services and procedures in air navigation^{rrr}.

As a general rule, the launch of unmanned free balloons and the launch of tethered balloons requires a NOTAM to be issued by the Italian aeronautical authorities. In particular, Circular ATM-05A sets forth the procedure to follow in order to obtain a temporary restriction, within a specific area, of the airspace. In case of positive assessment of the request, a NOTAM will be issued^{sss} (temporary restriction means a restriction with a duration of **90 days maximum**, which is renewable for an additional period of 30 days).^{ttt} Among the events or the special activities which make it necessary to follow that procedure we recall to our purposes the launch of unmanned free balloons^{uuu} and the launch of tethered balloons.^{vvv}

The procedure to comply with is the following:

1. Compilation of the “Special Bulletin” model, with the opinion of the competent Air Traffic Services (ATS), and payment of a fixed amount on-line^{www}. In accordance with Annex 2 to the Chicago Convention on International Civil Aviation, in case of unmanned free balloons, it is necessary to declare in the Special Bulletin also the colour, the maximum weight and other data which are specifically listed^{xxx}. As far as tethered balloons is concerned, their launch can only be carried out as long as they do not enter the buffer zone (superficie di rispetto)^{yyy} of the airports concerned and they do not

^{qqq} Certificato di operatore aereo per imprese di trasporto aereo di passeggeri con palloni liberi ad aria calda, adopted on 18 July 2011.

^{rrr} Regulations of the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) No 923/2012 of 26 September 2012 laying down the common rules of the air and operational provisions regarding services and procedures in air navigation and amending Implementing Regulation (EU) No 1035/2011 and Regulations (EC) No 1265/2007, (EC) No 1794/2006, (EC) No 730/2006, (EC) No 1033/2006 and (EU) No 255/2010

^{sss} In case no specific prescriptions and conditions are established and the tethered balloon does not fly over 40 m, the issue of a NOTAM is not necessary.

Except in case of urgency, a NOTAM shall be issued at least 7 days before the event, in order to give the air users (utenti aeronautici) concerned the possibility to know in due time the restrictions they are called upon to respect. See Regolamento servizio informazioni aeronautiche, adopted on 24 May 2007.

^{ttt} Circular ATM-05A, Eventi e attività speciali interessanti il traffico aereo, issued on 23 July 2013 (Serie Air Traffic Management).

^{uuu} Art. 3 par. 2 e), ibidem.

^{vvv} Art. 3 par. 2 g), ibidem.

^{www} See further

http://www.enac.gov.it/la_regolazione_per_la_sicurezza/spazio_aereo/tariffa_per_segregazione_spazio_aereo/info970212640.html)

^{xxx} See Attachement A (Notiziario speciale) to circolare ATM-05A

^{yyy} See, for a description of a buffer zone, the Regulation for the construction and operation of airports, 21 October 2003.

interfere with the procedures of approaching, taking-off and circling. These circumstances shall be properly evaluated and declared by the applicant (art. 4 par. 7).

2. Presentation of the Special Bulletin to the territorially competent Enac Office at least 45 calendar days before the launch. Once verified that documents are complete, the competent Enac office reviews the application and evaluates, taking also in consideration the opinion expressed by the ATS, the compatibility of the activity or event with the civil aviation activity in the area, and it eventually establishes special requirements or conditions. On the basis of this assessment it decides to request or not a NOTAM to the Airspace Coordination Unit (ACU). Thus, in case of positive assessment, the request for a temporary air space restriction becomes a NOTAM^{zzz}.

Finally, the applicant shall ask for the cancellation of the NOTAM as soon as it is no longer necessary.

When the duration of the requested restriction is longer than 90 days, circular ATM-03 applies. The procedure set forth in this circular shall be followed inter alia to establish, modify or cancel a restricted zone for launching weather balloons with radiosondes (innalzamento palloni sonda per radiosondaggi) (art. 3.3 g).^{aaaa}

5.2.4.3 Recovery of Stratospheric Balloons

In Italy there are no specific rules applicable to rescue and recovery of fallen balloons. As a consequence, those (mainly) European Union norms which regulate those issues in general for civil aviation, they also apply to balloons.

In case of accident within the EU, regulation No 996/2010 applies, which contemplates the possible joint involvement of more States in safety investigations^{bbbb}. Any person involved who has knowledge of the occurrence of an accident or serious incident shall notify the competent safety investigation authority of the *State of Occurrence* thereof. The latter in its turn shall notify the Commission, EASA, the International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO), the Member States and third countries concerned of the occurrence of the accident or serious incident of which it has been notified^{cccc}. Upon receipt of the notification the Member States which are the State of Registry, the State of the Operator,

^{zzz} In case no specific prescriptions and conditions are established and the tethered balloon does not fly over 40 m, the issue of a NOTAM is not necessary.

Except in case of urgency, a NOTAM shall be issued at least 7 days before the event, in order to give the air users (utenti aeronautici) concerned the possibility to know in due time the restrictions they are called upon to respect. See Regolamento servizio informazioni aeronautiche, adopted on 24 May 2007.

^{aaaa} Circular ATM-03B, Istituzione, modifica o cancellazione di zone soggette a restrizioni, adopted on 15 December 2016, (Serie Air Traffic Management). See also par. 6.2.

^{bbbb} Regulation (EU) No 996/2010 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 October 2010 on the investigation and prevention of accidents and incidents in civil aviation and repealing Directive 94/56/EC Text with EEA relevance OJ L 295, 12.11.2010, pp. 35–50. The Regulation was amended by Regulation (EU) No 376/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 3 April 2014 on the reporting, analysis and follow-up of occurrences in civil aviation. OJ L 122, 24.4.2014, pp. 18–43. See, for the implementation of this regulation in Italy: Decreto legislativo 14 gennaio 2013, n. 18 Disciplina sanzionatoria per la violazione delle disposizioni del regolamento (UE) n. 996/2010 sulle inchieste e la prevenzione degli incidenti e inconvenienti nel settore dell'aviazione civile, nonché abrogazione della direttiva 94/56/CE. (13G00056) (GU Serie Generale n.48 del 26-2-2013)

^{cccc} Ibidem, art. 9 (Obligation to notify accidents and serious incidents)

the State of Design and the State of Manufacture shall, as soon as possible, inform the Member State or third country in the territory of which the accident or serious incident occurred whether they intend to appoint an accredited representative^{dddd}.

The same Regulation (EU) No 996/2010 deals with the issue of assistance to the victims of air accidents and their relatives and prescribes that “in order to ensure a more comprehensive and harmonised response to accidents at EU level, each Member State shall establish a civil aviation accident emergency plan at national level. Such an emergency plan shall also cover assistance to the victims of civil aviation accidents and their relatives”^{eeeee}. According to this Regulation the territorial State apparently plays the main role in the procedures of rescue and recovery.

5.2.4.4 Other Regulations

Art. 3 of the Italian Code of Navigation, under the title “Spazio aereo soggetto alla sovranità dello Stato”, specifies that Italian State sovereignty covers the air space above the national territory, and above the territorial waters^{ffff}. As a consequence, foreign balloons shall comply with Italian law as long as they are within the so defined airspace, subject to Italian jurisdiction.

To their purposes, ATM-03 (art. 3 par. 1) and ATM-05A (art. 3 par. 1) also apply to those events and special activities which take place over international waters as long as the services of air navigation are there provided by Italy.

Shifting the focus to another issue, it is worth of note that hot air balloons operators holding a valid Air Operator Certificate for passenger transportation granted by the Civil Aviation Authority of a EU member State, which aim to obtain the permission for temporary operation into the Italian territories, shall submit a written request according to art. 35 of the ENAC Regulation “Certificato di operatore aereo per imprese di trasporto aereo di passeggeri con palloni liberi ad aria calda” (Certificate of Air Operator for transport companies of passengers through hot air free balloons) and operate in accordance with the requirements established therein.

There is no legal definition of the upper limit of airspace in Italy.

5.2.4.5 Radiofrequencies and Telecommunications Provisions

The application of stratospheric balloons falls within the radio service of “meteorological aids service”, so that it must operate in the frequency bands assigned to this service by the National Plan of Frequencies Distribution (Piano nazionale di Ripartizione delle Frequenze, PNRF). To this purpose, we quote the definition of meteorological aids service (servizio di ausili meteorologici) contained therein: “Servizio di ausili meteorologici (meteorological aids service): Servizio di radiocomunicazione destinato

^{dddd} Ibidem, art. 10 (Participation of the Member States in safety investigations)

^{eeeee} See further ibidem, art. 21 (Assistance to the victims of air accidents and their relatives)

^{ffff} See also art. 2 (Definizioni), Regolamento regole dell’aria, Third Edition, 22 December 2016.

alle osservazioni ed ai sondaggi utilizzati per la meteorologia ivi compresa l'idrologia.”^{eggg}

The frequency bands assigned to the meteorological aids service by the PNRF are:^{hhhh}

2,025 kHz – 2,045 kHz

27,500 kHz - 28 MHz

400.15 MHz - 401 MHz

401 MHz - 402 MHz

402 MHz - 403 MHz

403 MHz - 406 MHz

1,668.4 MHz – 1,670 MHz

1,670 MHz – 1,675 MHz

1,675 MHz – 1,700 MHz

35.2 GHz - 35.5 GHz

35.5 GHz - 36 GHz

Since the outlined bands are exclusively or jointly managed by the Ministry of Defense, in order to use them it is preliminarily necessary to obtain an authorization by the latter. To this purpose the following station’s technical characteristics are to be submitted:

- frequency band;
- radiated power;
- height of the stratospheric balloon;
- area of interest in receiving data;
- period of use

As long as an application cannot be classified under the “meteorological aids service”, it is in any case necessary to submit the listed parameters in order to classify the service and to identify the corresponding frequency bandsⁱⁱⁱⁱ.

5.2.4.6 Findings

While the general definition of airmobile offered by the Italian Code of Navigation is such to encompass balloons, a specific definition of balloon is not contemplated. ENAC is the authority in charge to regulate, to issue certifications and to carry out the necessary control in the sector of civil aviation in Italy. It is also competent for the registration of airmobiles, including balloons.

Art. 3 of the Italian Code of Navigation specifies that Italian State sovereignty covers the air space above the national territory, and above the territorial waters. As a consequence, foreign balloons shall comply with Italian law as long as they are within the so defined airspace, subject to Italian jurisdiction. However, to their purposes some Italian

^{eggg} <http://www.mise.gov.it/index.php/it/comunicazioni/radio/pnrf-piano-nazionale-di-ripartizione-delle-frequenze>

^{hhhh} <http://www.efis.dk/views2/compare-allocations.jsp>

ⁱⁱⁱⁱ The aeronautic radio on board of the balloon needs to be certified every two years, in order to prevent that the setting of frequencies is altered (ramp test).

normative instruments also apply to those events and special activities which take place over international waters as long as the services of air navigation are there provided by Italy.

An analysis of Italian relevant legislation suggests to draw a distinction between different types of balloons, namely between tethered balloons and free balloons, free balloons then may be unmanned or manned: every category of balloons is submitted to a special regulation which is mainly issued by ENAC. As a general rule, the launch and flight of balloons in Italy requires an administrative authorization issued by the Italian aeronautical authorities.

Finally, specific norms do not exist in Italy regulating rescue and recovery of fallen balloons. EU regulations, which apply in general to air accidents or incidents, also apply to balloons.

5.2.5 Regulations in Sweden

5.2.5.1 Restrictions on Stratospheric Balloon Flights in Sweden

Stratospheric balloons are important for the Swedish space activities and Sweden is important for stratospheric balloons, as the geography of the country provides good opportunities for launching. The first balloons were launched from Esvinge in Kiruna in northern Sweden in 1974 and since then more than 550 balloons have been launched.^{jjjj} Esvinge has a well-developed infrastructure for balloon launches, used by Swedish and foreign users, primarily researchers. Due to its geographical location, Esvinge is unique in Europe, as sounding rockets can land on earth and the large area without nearby aviation permits balloon launches without risks of possible interference with aviation. Many Esvinge activities, including balloon activities, are coordinated and financed by what is called the Esvinge Andøya Special Project (EASP) which is a part of ESA (European Space Agency) activities. The member states of EASP are France, Germany, Switzerland, Norway and Sweden.^{kkkk}

In addition, balloon launches from Esvinge are handled for other parties by the Swedish Space Corporation (SSC). SSC was formed by the Swedish government in 1972 and has been an important component of Swedish space activities since its inception. It has undergone important changes in recent years. From having been primarily engaged in delivering space services to the Swedish public sector, SSC is now active globally as a space technology provider. This includes balloon technology.^{llll} Sounding rocket and stratospheric balloon launches from Esvinge can be performed either by individual countries and organisations with permission from SSC, or by EuroLaunch – a collaboration between SSC and the German Space board DLR providing what is called a “flight ticket” approach, a kind of full service approach.^{mmmm}

^{jjjj} <http://www.sscspace.com/Products-Services/rocket-balloon-services/balloon-missions>

^{kkkk} Mattias Abrahamsson, Anna Rathsmann “Esvinge Space Centre - meeting future needs for advanced space services” 33rd Space Symposium, Technical Track, Colorado Springs, Colorado, United States of America Presented on April 3, 2017, p. 2.

^{llll} SOU 2015:75 Eb rymdstrategi för nytta och tillväxt p 95

^{mmmm} Abrahamsson & Rathsmann 2017, p. 2

SCC is responsible for such aspects of balloon launches as contacts with the customers (institutions or commercial customers), IT issues and other mission-specific details. The Swedish state is responsible for security issues concerning third parties, application of any relevant rules and regulations, bilateral cooperation and similar matters.ⁿⁿⁿⁿ Currently, the State responsibility is primarily handled via the work of the Swedish Transport Agency (Transportstyrelsen)^{oooo}, but current developments point to a larger role for the Swedish National Space Board (SNSB)^{pppp}.

According to Chapter 1 Section 1 of the Swedish Aviation Act (2010:500)^{qqqq} any aviation within Swedish territory may only be carried out in accordance with this law or other statute, unless otherwise stipulated in EU Regulations. The preparatory material for the law stipulates that it applies to any form of aircraft. There is however no definition in the law of aircraft, but this should be understood according to generally accepted interpretation of the term. For guidance, it is possible to refer to the Chicago Convention and ICAO definitions:

Aircraft. Any machine that can derive support in the atmosphere from the reactions of the air other than the reactions of the air against the earth's surface.

As the Aviation Act is intended for traditional aircraft but nevertheless is applicable to all kinds of aircraft, there may be a need to modify the rules on occasion. Such a possibility is given by Chapter 1 Section 9 first paragraph of the Aviation Act:

Regarding aircraft which have no pilot on board or are not engine-driven or which are otherwise of a special type, the government or public authority appointed by the government may issue regulations on, or in individual cases decide on, exceptions to the provisions in Chapter 1, Section 6, paragraph 1 and Chapters 2-8, and otherwise issue any necessary regulations.

Exceptions and regulations may not be formulated such that they conflict with flight safety or the public interest. Administrative tasks in connection with regulations may, if the government so prescribes, be delegated by the public authority to some other entity, even if the tasks include

the exercise of public authority.

In the preparatory works, balloons are mentioned as examples of such aircraft that are of a special nature. Thus, we conclude that balloons are such aircraft that are covered by the Aviation Act. Whether this applies to stratospheric balloons depends on the extent to which they are using airspace.

According to Chapter 7 Section 8 of the Aviation Act it is necessary to have a permit for aerial work conducted by way of aircraft. The Section mentions aerial work involving aircraft, such as lifting, towing, inspections and surveillance. Thus, examples of aerial work include geological and other measurements conducted with the help of aircraft. The reason for special permits for aerial work is that work with aircraft normally entails higher work-related risks.

ⁿⁿⁿⁿ <http://www.snsb.se/Global/Remissvar%20rymdutredningen%20Rymdstyrelsen.pdf>

^{oooo} <http://transportstyrelsen.se/en/About-us/>

^{pppp} <http://www.snsb.se/en/Home/Home/>

^{qqqq} Available in English at

<http://transportstyrelsen.se/globalassets/global/regler/luftfart/regulations/swedish-aviation-act.pdf>

This is the reason for a requirement of aerial work permits also for aerial activities for one's own purposes or without any remuneration. Thus it would appear that the balloons in question would need a permit for aerial work to the extent they would operate in Swedish airspace.

The Swedish Transport Agency is responsible for balloon permits in general. It publishes a price list for permits for aerial work and balloons. In some cases, the type of balloons is unspecified and in some cases the term "hot air balloon" is used. For annual permits, the prices differ for up to three hot air balloons or more than four. There is also a small fee for monitoring of foreign providers of aerial works. The release of unmanned free balloons with a payload is subject to a fee of 6,000 SEK^{tmr}, Section 3 of Chapter 16 of the Transport Agency regulation.^{ssss}

The fee for guaranteeing the airworthiness of aircraft ranges from an annual fee of 1,000 SEK for balloons (types not defined) and sailplanes to 57,000 SEK for the largest kind of aircraft.^{ttt}

Sweden has space legislation in the form of the 1982 Act on Space Activities (1982:963), which sets out the system for granting licences for space activities. There is also a Decree 1982:1069 on space activities and an ordinance 1996:80 with instructions for the Space Board.^{uuuu} There is no definition of space activities in the very short law, which basically only stipulates that no-one can conduct space activities in Sweden without a permit from the government. Details for permits can be decided by the government. Launching of sounding rockets is excluded from the law according to Section 1. According to the Decree, the task of dealing with permits is handled by the SNSB, which makes the initial evaluation and prepares the material for any space activities to be licenced under the Space Act. SNSB consults with the telecommunications regulator and any other relevant bodies when deciding on permits for space activities. There is a list in the Decree on what kind of information about planned activities that needs to be submitted. There is no definition of space objects. Although the activities and competence of SNSB is defined so that it could include stratospheric balloons, in practice the system for permits for balloons is not handled by SNSB but instead by the Transport Agency.^{vvv} Sounding rockets are explicitly excluded from the licensing activities of the SNSB and instead handled only (from security aspects) by the regional authority of Norrland^{wwww} – the region of Esrange – while balloons are not mentioned explicitly in the Space Act but have been handled within the competence of the Transport Agency. However, a major Swedish space strategy report from 2015^{xxxx} mentions that new types of space activities

^{tmr} About 617 Euro, 1000 SEK about 103 Euro (exchange rate on 26 May 2017).

^{ssss} <http://transportstyrelsen.se/sv/Om-transportstyrelsen/Finansiering-och-avgifter/Avgifter/Luftfart/Flygoperativ-verksamhet/Flygoperativa-tillstand-for-bruksflyg-och-luftballong/> Chapter 16.

^{ttt} Ibid, Chapter 12, Section 3. In some cases, interest organisations can deal with the airworthiness in which case there is a fee for balloons of 3600 SEK, Section 10. There are also fees for import and for environmental control, the fees range between a few 1000 and up to about 6000 SEK.

^{uuuu}

http://www.esa.int/About_Us/ECSL_European_Centre_for_Space_Law/National_Space_Legislations

^{vvv} SOU 2015:275 En rymdstrategi för nytta och tillväxt p. 106

^{wwww} Länsstyrelsen i Norrbotten

^{xxxx} SOU 2015:275 En rymdstrategi för nytta och tillväxt

will mean that the Swedish legislation and systems for licensing will need an overhaul and modernization.^{yyyy} This may lead to a more coordinated approach with an increased mandate for SNSB.

One of the conclusions of the 2015 strategy analysis is that the SNSB should be given an increased mandate to be a coordinating authority for all space activities in Sweden. At the moment, SNSB is not involved in rule-making, discussions on international conventions or similar. Its role has not included technology transfers and participation in development of new issues like space tourism for example.^{zzzz} Furthermore, the roles of SNSB and the Transport Agency for giving permissions for balloon activity could potentially overlap or the work of SNSB could in any event be restricted if they cannot take part in strategy development for different activities, including what forms of permissions or licensing processes that are the most suitable.

The space strategy report does not deal specifically with stratospheric balloons, although they are included in the general analysis. The report states that it makes a broad definition of what activities to include in the analysis for the strategy, in order to concretise and limit the extent of activities covered throughout the report, as is suitable in the different contexts. In the initial wide definition, balloons are mentioned but without any specification of types of balloons or other criteria.^{aaaaa} The report lists different ways in which balloons can be used for research and also mentions that Sweden has recently (via the SSC) entered into agreements with e.g. NASA about launch from Esrange of high-altitude balloons.^{bbbbb}

In addition to mentioned research programs or clients arranging launches via SCC, the SNSB together with ESA and the German space agency DLP offers possibilities for students from Europe to design and build experiments that are launched by balloons and sounding rockets from Esrange. This includes the student project Rexus Bexus. In addition, there is a research balloon project PoGoLite (The Polarised Gamma-ray Observer) at Esrange.^{ccccc}

5.2.5.2 Restrictions on Overflight of Stratospheric Balloons

There are no special rules on restrictions for overflight of special types of balloons or similar. There is a requirement of permits for aerial work, as mentioned above, and penal provisions related to this (for engaging in activities without a permit) are found in Chapter 13 Section 4 points 15 and 17 of the Aviation Act (a sentence of fines or prison for a maximum of six months).

The Aviation Ordinance (2010:770)^{dddd} provides further rules to complement the Aviation Act, Chapter 1 Section 1 of the Aviation Ordinance. This provision like the Aviation Act proclaim that the rules are applicable unless EU regulations prescribe

^{yyyy} Ibid. p 123

^{zzzz} SOU 2015 :75 pp 106-107.

^{aaaaa} 122 Ibid. p. 34

^{bbbbb} Ibid. p. 103

^{ccccc} <http://www.snsb.se/sv/Rymdteknik/Ballonger/>

^{dddd} Available in English at <http://transportstyrelsen.se/globalassets/global/regler/luftfart/regulations/swedish-aviation-ordinance.pdf>

otherwise. According to Chapter 7 Section 2 Aviation Ordinance the Swedish Transport Agency may issue regulations on aerial work permits and review matters concerning aerial work permits. The agency may delegate the review to some other entity. The Swedish Transport Agency may issue regulations on, or in individual cases decide on, exceptions to the requirement for an aerial work permit, provided the activity is not on a large scale or if there are other special reasons, under Chapter 7 Section 2 third paragraph of the Aviation Ordinance.

It appears such exceptions are based on Chapter 1 Section 9 of the Aviation Act as well as Chapter 7 Section 8 third paragraph of the Aviation Act. In this latter Section, it is stipulated that the government or the authority decided by the government may in individual cases decide about exceptions from the requirement of permits for aerial work, for activities that are not on a large scale or if there are other special reasons.

The preparatory work to Chapter 7 Section 8 third paragraph provide examples of what is meant with the activities not being on a large scale and there being special reasons.

As for the scale, the following is to be considered: That the activities are for private purposes only and not offered to the public for remuneration, provided that the risk level is generally seen as low and that aviation safety is met in an acceptable manner, will be taken to indicate that the activities are not on a large scale in the meaning of the law.

Another example given is that an aviation company that has a permit for other activities will conduct some limited aerial works a few times per year.

Special reasons can be that in some circumstances it should be possible to give permits for work with aircraft from an EU country that does not have aerial work permits or similar in their national law, provided that reasonable aviation security standards are met.

There does not appear to be any special guidance to Chapter 7 Section 2 of the Aviation Ordinance. Thus, it appears reasonable that the statements on the extent of the activities and the special reasons can be interpreted in a similar manner as what has been mentioned regarding the provisions of the law.

As mentioned above, the space legislation does not define types of space activities. The question of whether balloons are in airspace or outer space is not explicitly stated. In practice, however until now balloons and sounding rockets are not included in the system under the Space Act, although only sounding rockets are excluded in the law itself.

As mentioned, balloon launches from Esrange are handled by the Swedish Space Corporation (SSC).^{eeeee} The SSC is a full-service provider on commercial terms, to institutional and commercial customers from any country. Stratospheric balloon missions are mentioned among the services of SSC. The company provides all different aspects of the mission.

It has not been possible to find any published rules about characteristics of the balloon but it appears – due to the nature of the system for allowing launches – that this is handled in each case. According to Abrahamsson and Rathsmann of the SSC, the balloons launched from Esrange range in size from 500 cubic meters (17 000 cubic feet) to over one million cubic meters (40 million cubic feet). Such balloons can carry a 2 ton gondola to 40 km altitude and fly for several weeks.^{fffff}

^{eeeee} <http://www.sscspace.com/about-the-ssc-group>

^{fffff} Abrahamsson & Rathsmann 2017 p.2.

The SCC publishes so called Preliminary Announcements regarding all planned launches, with details of the launch, presumed impact points, information about frequencies on which information is given over radio during the launch and any additional necessary security information.^{egggg}

One of the major research projects with balloons in Sweden was the PoGOLite project. The balloon travelled over Greenland and Canada, to land somewhere in Canada. The exact path depends on winds and many other factors. Permissions were asked and received by the Space Boards of all countries concerned and even if the balloons were at such a height that there was no risk for aviation, there was a website on which aviation authorities could find information about the whereabouts of the balloon.

In 2005 NASA launched large helium balloons from Esrange, which allowed – based on calculations of winds etc. – to ensure that the balloons would not enter Russian airspace, as Russia did not give permission for such overflight. These examples indicate that the Swedish authorities responsible for Esrange seek permission from any potentially affected countries even if there is not always an established framework for which authorities in different countries that are responsible (air or space authorities).^{hhhhh}

Abrahamsson and Rathsman describe how depending on the season, the prevailing winds at altitude will take the balloons in different directions from Esrange. From mid-May to mid-August the high-altitude winds will take a balloon westwards, in a trans-Atlantic trajectory and the landing sites most likely will be in Canada or Alaska. From mid-September to the end of April, the winds at the relevant altitude are likely to take a balloon eastwards and it will land in eastern Sweden, Finland or Russia. The least predictable time is the beginning of May, late August and early September, in which period the winds at high altitude will change from easterly to westerly direction. This is called the “turn-around period” and balloons move slowly and erratically over northern Sweden, Norway and Finland. This period is used for long (up to two day) flights over Esrange.ⁱⁱⁱⁱ The time of launch will thus determine which other states that should be contacted for possible landings. As opposed to sounding rockets, stratospheric balloon payloads do not necessarily have to land in the designated Impact Area. They have to land in this area (a designated area around Esrange) if they are free falling without parachute.

In other cases, balloon payloads can land outside the area somewhere else in Norway, Sweden and Finland or with special permission in Canada or even Russia^{jjjj} although Russia has been more restrictive with permitting overflight. Permissions are asked each time, ad hoc.

5.2.5.3 Recovery of Stratospheric Balloons

There are no special rules in Sweden for recovery of balloons. The ownership of the balloon will remain with the original owner if the owner is known. Sweden has a law on

^{egggg} For an example of such an announcement: <http://www.sscspace.com/file/documents/science-services-1/rocket/forberedande-meddelande-nr-189-for-mapheus-6.pdf>

^{hhhhh} Overview Of The Scientific Balloon Activity in Sweden 2014-2016. Abrahamsson, Mattias; Lockowandt, Christian; Andersson, Kent <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2016cosp...41E..25A>

ⁱⁱⁱⁱ Abrahamsson & Rathsman 2017 p. 2

^{jjjj} Ibid. p. 3

found objects (Lagen om hittegods) from 1938^{kkkkk} that sets out general rules for found objects. If a person takes possession of a found object, there is a duty to report such objects to the authorities (the police) or the owner, if known. There is normally no duty to take possession of found objects (unless this would follow from some other law) but if a person decides to do so, certain obligations follow. The law on found objects stipulates a right to get ownership of the objects if the owner is not found within three months or does not claim the object one month after being notified. The finder may have to pay costs that the authorities have had for the object if he or she gets possession of it. If the owner is found and claims the goods, the owner may be liable to pay for costs as well as pay a finder's fee. There is no definition of what is covered by the law, but the only case decided by the Swedish Supreme Court related to balloons refers to this law.^{lllll}

The law contains special provisions^{mmmmmm} referring to found objects that have a connection to such accidents that should be examined under the law (1990:712) on examination of accidents. This law (Section 2 point 1) lists accidents with aircraft that have resulted in death or serious injury, serious damage to the aircraft or good transported on it or to environment or when the aircraft is unreachable or has been lost during flight. The law in Section 11 stipulates that found objects that have connection to an investigation under the law on investigation of accidents cannot be touched or moved without permission from the police or the organ investigating the accident. Furthermore, there is an obligation of notification if such goods have nevertheless been taken into possession. The body investigating accidents is in most cases the Swedish Accident Investigation Authority (Statens Haverikommission).ⁿⁿⁿⁿⁿ They have examined a number of accidents or risks of accidents involving balloons. As for the only case in the Supreme Court about balloons, the case deals with a British military balloon that in 1940 flew over Sweden and was partially caught in a tree, following which it was tied down by some private individuals that reported their find to the authorities. The Swedish state took possession of the balloon once they had been notified. In a series of dramatic events (that as such do not have anything to do with the content of the case) the balloon as well as some persons nearby were struck by lightning. Two people were killed and the balloon destroyed. The essence of the case is however about application of the law on found objects on the balloon and the question of compensation for those who spotted and rescued it. Without going into details that are not relevant and very old, the basic content was that an object such as a balloon that has drifted in from another country can be seen as a found object and finding it can give raise to a claim of a finder's fee and compensation for costs. The responsibility for the balloon as such would normally remain with the owner – the British military in this case – but special wartime rules made the matter more complex in this particular case.^{ooooo}

There is no law on recovery of balloons, although in cases of investigation of accidents the above-mentioned law 1990:712 on investigation of accidents may be applicable, if the situation is such that is mentioned in that law (serious injury etc.). There is a law from

^{kkkkk} Lag 1938:121 om hittegods

^{lllll} NJA 1952:29 p 177.

^{mmmmmm} Section 7 first paragraph

ⁿⁿⁿⁿⁿ <http://www.havkom.se/search?q=ballong>

^{ooooo} Ibid.

1984^{ppppp} which sets out the procedure for getting exclusive rights for recovery of shipwrecks, from the regional authorities. However, this law mentions only sunken wrecks.^{qqqqq}

According to the Penal Code (Chapter 8) it is illegal to use land owned by anyone else - private or public - for activities that are not permitted by law. The provisions are mainly aimed at installations. Temporary permission to use land can be given (normally) by the local authorities.

In addition, it is allowed in Sweden to use private and public land to some extent for recreational activities and similar, including walking or otherwise moving over it with some restrictions, even if there are no marked paths. This is popularly called “every man’s right” (allmansrätten) and is protected by the Swedish Constitution.^{rrrrr} It is specified in environmental law (miljöbalken) and limitations to it may also follow from criminal law. Chapter 24 Section 4 of the Penal Code stipulates that activities undertaken in an emergency are normally not criminal if the damages caused by it or other circumstances make it unacceptable. However, for such exclusion from penal provisions there has to be a danger for life, health or property.

Depending on what the recovery activities may amount to and where they take place^{sssss} the general right to use land may be sufficient. The right to land or take off with balloons has been seen as being covered by the right to use land, provided no damage is caused (although in practice it is common to ask permission beforehand), so it follows that the right to rescue should also be covered. In any event, if such work is undertaken in an emergency, even provisions that may otherwise make it illegal would not be applicable.

5.2.5.4 Other Regulations

The Swedish Space Act does not define space. Sweden has not in any other context adopted a definition of outer space. Nor is airspace defined in law. There is no case law that defines these concepts.

Balloon activities in Sweden tend to be part of activities in the framework of special projects, which is why it is not possible to find general cases of what is applicable for different types of activities. Instead, special rules are linked to projects.

The SNSB includes stratospheric balloons in space research, as a type of research that uses space technologies to collect data.^{ttttt} SNSB in late 2016 (with deadline 14 February 2017) opened an open call to researchers in Sweden, meaning that the principal applicant is required to be, or be eligible to become, affiliated to a Swedish University or research establishment in Sweden where the project work is to be carried out, to apply for funding for Balloon and Rocket projects to be launched from Esrange. The instructions state^{uuuuu}:

^{ppppp} Lag (1984:983) om ensamrätt till bärgning

^{qqqqq} Another analogy, which however also does not fit so well, is the law on taking possession of abandoned cars, which gives the right to remove abandoned and not functional vehicles in certain circumstances, including from private land, Lag (1982:129) om flyttning av fordon.

^{rrrrr} Chapter 2, Section 15, paragraph 4.

^{sssss} The right to use land does not extend to the vicinity of residential property and some other restrictions.

^{ttttt} Rymdstyrelsen strategi p.

^{uuuuu} <http://www.snsb.se/Global/Forskare/Utlysningar/2016-BR/INSTRUCTIONS%202016-BR.PDF>

The purpose of the programme is to offer rocket and balloon flights for high quality research experiments and to ensure a continuity in the national programme at Esrange. The call is open for balloon- and rocket-born research in various thematic areas, such as:

- Astronomy and Astrophysics;
- Space Physics, Solar System Physics;
- Fundamental Physics;
- Astrobiology;
- Atmospheric Research;
- Life and Physical Sciences;
- Earth Observation;
- Technology Research for Space Applications.

5.2.5.5 Radiofrequencies and Telecommunications Provisions

In Sweden, the Post and Telecom Authority (Post och Telestyrelsen)^{vvvv} monitors electronic communications and the postal sector as well as deals with radio frequencies. This includes radio frequencies for aircraft. In 2016, a study was made of use of the frequency band 1427-1518 MHz, which e.g. has been used for repeated but temporary telemetry for balloons in northern Sweden.^{wwwww} Such applications for frequencies are made by SSC. In the study, it is concluded that these uses can be collected in another frequency band which would be just as suitable, given the various conditions that determine balloon launches (dependent on weather, differing number per year and so on). Part of the 2300-2400 MHz band is mentioned. The reason for the analysis was a study on what frequencies could be used for mobile broadband without harming other frequency uses. The Post and Telecom Authority points for the negative impact for balloon launches from Esrange if the issue of frequencies for them is not handled well.^{xxxxx}

There may be possibilities to change the current frequency use as the bands in use are not utilise constantly, but the Authority stresses the uses although temporary are recurring and need to be accommodated.

5.2.6 Regulations in the U.S.

5.2.6.1 Restrictions on Stratospheric Balloon Flights in the U.S.

Definition of (Stratospheric) Balloon

The US defines balloons generally in the Code of Federal Regulations. “Balloon means a lighter-than-air aircraft that is not engine driven, and that sustains flight through the use of either gas buoyancy or an airborne heater.” 14 CFR § 1.1

Altitude is not an element of the definition, hence there is no distinction for balloons designed to fly in the stratosphere.

^{vvvv} 143 <http://www.pts.se/en-GB/>

^{wwwww} <http://www.pts.se/upload/Remisser/2016/forstudie-1427-1518-MHz-Remissversion.pdf>

^{xxxxx} Ibid. p 24.

Distinction Between Different Types of Balloons

The above-referenced regulation defines balloons as a general class. However, significant distinctions are made between moored balloons, unmanned free balloons, and manned free balloons. This paper limits inquiry to discussion of free unmanned balloons.^{yyyyy}

Additional definition of balloons subject to US regulatory reach can be found in the subpart of regulations that pertain to air traffic and the general operating rules for unmanned free balloons.

Taxonomy of unmanned balloons can relate to weight and volume, as articulated in 14 CFR Part 101 and provided below:

(4) Except as provided for in § 101.7,^{zzzzz} [rules apply to govern the operation of] any unmanned free balloon that -

- (i) Carries a payload package that weighs more than four pounds and has a weight/size ratio of more than three ounces per square inch on any surface of the package, determined by dividing the total weight in ounces of the payload package by the area in square inches of its smallest surface;*
- (ii) Carries a payload package that weighs more than six pounds;*
- (iii) Carries a payload, of two or more packages, that weighs more than 12 pounds;*
or
- (iv) Uses a rope or other device for suspension of the payload that requires an impact force of more than 50 pounds to separate the suspended payload from the balloon.^{aaaaa}*

Unmanned balloons that do not meet these minimum requirements are not subject to Subpart D of 14 CFR Part 101.

Designated Bodies or Entities that are Responsible for Dealing with Issues Related to Balloons

Two entities are responsible for balloon-related regulation. The Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) located within the Department of Transportation is the entity responsible for regulatory oversight of the national airspace, including inter alia airspace use, management, safety, and air traffic control. This statutory authority includes regulation of balloon activity.^{bbbbb}

^{yyyyy} See comment in introduction regarding World View and the availability of technology allowing manned balloons above FL600. Should this classification of balloon activity become a focus of a follow-on study, the US contains a separate set of regulations for manned free balloons.

^{zzzzz} 14 CFR §101.7 relates to hazardous operations and the full text is provided in a subsequent section of this paper.

^{aaaaa} 14 CFR 101.1 (a)(4)

^{bbbbb} Congress directs the FAA to “develop plans and policy for the use of the navigable airspace and assign by regulation or order the use of the airspace necessary to ensure the safety of aircraft and the efficient use of airspace.” 49 U.S.C. § 40103(b)(1).

Currently, balloons are regulated by the FAA. The Federal Communications Commission is responsible for communications with high-altitude unmanned balloons. The relevant regulations will be addressed in the subsequent section about spectrum.

Permissions/Licences/Permits for Launch and Flight of Balloons

Although no license per se is required to launch a high-altitude balloon in the United States, some regulations found in the Title 14 of the United States Code of Federal Regulations (Aeronautics and Space) still apply to actual operations. These regulations can be found in 14 CFR Part 101 Subpart D.

This section begins with a high-level summation of rules pertaining to high-altitude weather balloon flight. The relevant regulations are provided after this brief list.

1. Cell phones are not permitted to track high-altitude weather balloons in flight.
2. Payloads cannot exceed a package weight/size ratio of three ounces per square inch.
3. No payload package can exceed 6 lb. in weight.
4. Entire weight of all payloads cannot exceed 12 lb. in total weight (excludes weight of balloon)
5. No rope or cable should be used which requires more than 50 lb. of force to separate payload packages from balloon.
6. No one may launch a high-altitude weather balloon which creates a hazard to other people and property (i.e. incorrect parachute, faulty rigging, inappropriate launch location)
7. No one may use a high-altitude weather balloon to drop objects (i.e. gliders and projectiles)^{ccccc}

Some provisions within Part 101 Subpart D may either be waived or alternate procedures authorized by the FAA if official requests are submitted to the appropriate FAA Service Center.

The weight criteria within § 101.1 “Applicability” cannot be waived. Requests can be submitted using FAA Form 7711-2, Application for Certificate of Waiver or Authorization.

In addition to the regulatory practices listed above, high-altitude balloon operators include as a practice the use of Skyvector in setting up flight plans.^{dddd}

Relevant Regulations^{eeeee}

§ 101.7 Hazardous operations

^{ccccc} “Weather Balloon Frequently Asked Questions” available at: <http://www.stratostar.net/faq.html> (date accessed: 30 May 2017); see also

https://www.faa.gov/aircraft/air_cert/design_approvals/balloons/balloons_regs/;

<http://community.balloonchallenge.org/t/regulations-overview-including-contacting-the-us-faa/676> (date accessed: 20 May 2017)

^{dddd} <https://skyvector.com/> (date accessed: 25 May 2017)

^{eeeee} 14 CFR Part 101, available at: <https://www.ecfr.gov/cgi-bin/text-idx?rgn=div5&node=14:2.0.1.3.15#sp14.2.101.d> (date accessed: 20 May 2017)

-
- (a) *No person may operate any moored balloon, kite, amateur rocket, or unmanned free balloon in a manner that creates a hazard to other persons, or their property.*
- (b) *No person operating any moored balloon, kite, amateur rocket, or unmanned free balloon may allow an object to be dropped therefrom, if such action creates a hazard to other persons or their property.*

Authority: (Sec. 6(c), Department of Transportation Act (49 U.S.C. 1655(c))) [Doc. No. 12800, 39 FR 22252, June 21, 1974, as amended at 74 FR 38092, July 31, 2009]

§ 101.33 Operating limitations

No person may operate an unmanned free balloon -

- (a) *Unless otherwise authorized by ATC, below 2,000 feet above the surface within the lateral boundaries of the surface areas of Class B, Class C, Class D, or Class E airspace designated for an airport;*
- (b) *At any altitude where there are clouds or obscuring phenomena of more than five-tenths coverage;*
- (c) *At any altitude below 60,000 feet standard pressure altitude where the horizontal visibility is less than five miles;*
- (d) *During the first 1,000 feet of ascent, over a congested area of a city, town, or settlement or an open-air assembly of persons not associated with the operation;*
or
- (e) *In such a manner that impact of the balloon, or part thereof including its payload, with the surface creates a hazard to persons or property not associated with the operation.*

Authority: [Doc. No. 1457, 29 FR 47, Jan. 3, 1964, as amended by Amdt. 101-5, 56 FR 65662, Dec. 17, 1991]

§ 101.35 Equipment and marking requirements

(a) *No person may operate an unmanned free balloon unless -*

- (1) *It is equipped with at least two payload cut-down systems or devices that operate independently of each other;*
- (2) *At least two methods, systems, devices, or combinations thereof, that function independently of each other, are employed for terminating the flight of the balloon envelope; and*
- (3) *The balloon envelope is equipped with a radar reflective device(s) or material that will present an echo to surface radar operating in the 200 MHz to 2,700 MHz frequency range.*

The operator shall activate the appropriate devices required by paragraphs (a) (1) and (2) of this section when weather conditions are less than those prescribed for operation under this subpart, or if a malfunction or any other reason makes the further operation hazardous to other air traffic or to persons and property on the surface.

- (b) *No person may operate an unmanned free balloon below 60,000 feet standard pressure altitude between sunset and sunrise (as corrected to the altitude of*

operation) unless the balloon and its attachments and payload, whether or not they become separated during the operation, are equipped with lights that are visible for at least 5 miles and have a flash frequency of at least 40, and not more than 100, cycles per minute.

(c) No person may operate an unmanned free balloon that is equipped with a trailing antenna that requires an impact force of more than 50 pounds to break it at any point, unless the antenna has colored pennants or streamers that are attached at not more than 50 foot intervals and that are visible for at least one mile.

(d) No person may operate between sunrise and sunset an unmanned free balloon that is equipped with a suspension device (other than a highly conspicuously colored open parachute) more than 50 feet along, unless the suspension device is colored in alternate bands of high conspicuity colors or has colored pennants or streamers attached which are visible for at least one mile.

Authority: (Sec. 6(c), Department of Transportation Act (49 U.S.C. 1655(c))) [Doc. No. 1457, 29 FR 47, Jan. 3, 1964, as amended by Amdt. 101-2, 32 FR 5254, Mar. 29, 1967; Amdt. 101-4, 39 FR 22252, June 21, 1974]

§ 101.37 Notice requirements. [NOTAM]

(a) Prelaunch notice: Except as provided in paragraph (b) of this section, no person may operate an unmanned free balloon unless, within 6 to 24 hours before beginning the operation, he gives the following information to the FAA ATC facility that is nearest to the place of intended operation:

(1) The balloon identification.

(2) The estimated date and time of launching, amended as necessary to remain within plus or minus 30 minutes.

(3) The location of the launching site.

(4) The cruising altitude.

(5) The forecast trajectory and estimated time to cruising altitude or 60,000 feet standard pressure altitude, whichever is lower.

(6) The length and diameter of the balloon, length of the suspension device, weight of the payload, and length of the trailing antenna.

(7) The duration of flight.

(8) The forecast time and location of impact with the surface of the earth.

(b) For solar or cosmic disturbance investigations involving a critical time element, the information in paragraph (a) of this section shall be given within 30 minutes to 24 hours before beginning the operation.

(c) Cancellation notice: If the operation is canceled, the person who intended to conduct the operation shall immediately notify the nearest FAA ATC facility.

(d) Launch notice: Each person operating an unmanned free balloon shall notify the nearest FAA or military ATC facility of the launch time immediately after the balloon is launched.

§ 101.39 Balloon position reports

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- (a) *Each person operating an unmanned free balloon shall:*
- (1) *Unless ATC requires otherwise, monitor the course of the balloon and record its position at least every two hours; and*
 - (2) *Forward any balloon position reports requested by ATC.*
- (b) *One hour before beginning descent, each person operating an unmanned free balloon shall forward to the nearest FAA ATC facility the following information regarding the balloon:*
- (1) *The current geographical position.*
 - (2) *The altitude.*
 - (3) *The forecast time of penetration of 60,000 feet standard pressure altitude (if applicable).*
 - (4) *The forecast trajectory for the balance of the flight.*
 - (5) *The forecast time and location of impact with the surface of the earth.*
- (c) *If a balloon position report is not recorded for any two-hour period of flight, the person operating an unmanned free balloon shall immediately notify the nearest FAA ATC facility. The notice shall include the last recorded position and any revision of the forecast trajectory. The nearest ATC facility shall be notified immediately when tracking of the balloon is re-established.*
- (d) *Each person operating an unmanned free balloon shall notify the nearest FAA ATC facility when the operation is ended.*

Potentially Relevant Equipment and Regulation

Currently, in the United States, 14 CFR §91.225 contains a requirement that aircraft be outfitted with ADS-B equipage by 2020. This does not now apply to balloons. However, current discussions within FAA directorates contemplate treatment of the national airspace system (NAS) from the standpoint of all users, as opposed to specified users. This would potentially include any and all users that transit NAS during their missions. Technology is available that can be used on high-altitude balloons – uAvionix Corp.’s Ping200S ADS-B-capable Mode S transponder – should this shift in paradigm result in application of §91.225 to balloons.^{fffff}

5.2.6.2 Restrictions on Overflight of Stratospheric Balloons

At present, the Code of Federal Regulations is silent regarding rules for overflight of foreign balloons over the United States. This is likely because of its geography, despite the fact that Canada does regulate balloon activity to the north and Mexico is involved

^{fffff} Rob Mark, “uAvionix Ping200S ADS-B/Mode S Transponder Approved by FCC for Drones, Balloons and Gliders” (6 January 2017) Flying Magazine, available online at: <http://www.flyingmag.com/uavionix-ping200s-ads-b-mode-s-transponder-approved-by-fcc-for-drones-balloons-and-gliders> (date accessed: 26 May 2017).

in balloon activity to the south.^{ggggg} Right-of-way rules provide some guidance, however marginal.

Right-of-Way Rules

Right-of-way rules are found within 14 CFR Part 91, Flight Rules, which, in accord with the scope defined within the section (“Applicability”), attach to manned air flight activities. In particular, the rule for converging specifies that when aircraft of different categories are converging at approximately the same altitude, a balloon has the right-of-way over all other air traffic.^{hhhhh}

5.2.6.3 Recovery of Balloons

The CFR does not contain specific rescue and recovery protocols for unmanned free balloons. In the absence of specific flight regulations denoting appropriate procedures for rescue and recovery, it may be inferred that norms found in aviation and maritime could attach.

For the descent phase of balloon flight, rules of thumb for manned balloon activity are found in Advisory Circular 91-71, “Operation of Hot Air Balloons with Airborne Heaters.” However, these are not on point. Better guidance for descent of high-altitude balloons equipped with telemetry can be found in Project Loon’s Information Briefs. Unplanned descents are described as very rare.ⁱⁱⁱⁱⁱⁱ For balloons without telemetry and maneuvering capability, small parachutes are used to control descent. This represents practice, not regulation.

5.2.6.4 Radiofrequencies and Telecommunications Provisions

The Federal Communications Commission (FCC) regulates frequency and spectrum use in the United States^{jjjjj}; regulations are found in Title 47 Code of Federal Regulations Part 22. There is an absolute prohibition against using cellular telephones installed in or carried on balloons of any kind while they are airborne.

Radiosondes transmit data from high-altitude balloons. They are small instrument packages suspended below the balloon containing sensors that measure pressure, temperature, and relative humidity. An attached radio transmitter sends the data to a ground receiver. The radio frequencies range from 1,668.4 – 1,700.0 MHz. Observations of wind are called rawinsonde.

^{ggggg} Elliott Williams, “Mexican High Schoolers Launch 30 High-Altitude Balloons” (5 December 2016) available online at: <http://hackaday.com/2016/12/05/mexican-highschoolers-launch-30-high-altitude-balloons/> (date accessed: 30 May 2017).

^{hhhhh} 14 CFR § 91.113(d)(1).

ⁱⁱⁱⁱⁱⁱ June 2016: Project Loon Briefing Sheet Attachment to ICAO Letter, IFALPA Safety Bulletin (21 June 2016) at 3.

^{jjjjj} 47 CFR §22.925

5.2.7 Regulations in Canada

5.2.7.1 Restrictions on Stratospheric Balloon Flights

Definition of (Stratospheric) Balloon

The Canadian Aviation Regulations (CAR) SOR/96-433 Aeronautics Act provide definitions for both balloons and balloon operators:

“balloon means a non-power-driven lighter-than-air aircraft; (ballon) balloon operator means the holder of a special flight operations certificate — balloons issued under section 603.18; (exploitant de ballons).”^{kkkkkk}

Balloons are a listed classification of aircraft under the definition of category, also found in the CAR.^{lllll} As in the United States, altitude is not an element of the definition, nor is it used to denote a category or classification of balloon activity.

The Canadian Aviation Regulations derive their statutory authority from the Aeronautics Act, R.S.C., 1985, c. A-2.

Distinction Between Different Types of Balloons and Regulatory Impact

Whether a balloon activity is manned or unmanned and the amount of gas capacity of a balloon are the two most notable distinctions with regulatory impact. Payload is not a regulatory issue in Canada.

As in the United States, altitude or destination are not elements of the regulatory definitions.

Designated Bodies or Entities Responsible for Dealing with Balloon-Related Issues

Transport Canada is the entity regulating unmanned (or unoccupied, to mirror the regulatory language) balloon launches with a gas-carrying capacity of more than 115 cubic feet (3.256 m³).^{mmmmmm} Transport Canada is the civil aviation directorate in Canada.

There are no mandatory regulatory requirements for launch of unmanned balloons with a gas-carrying capacity of less than 115 cubic feet. Practice suggests that most operators are encouraged to notify Nav Canada and provide NOTAM information as described infra. NAV Canada is the private sector provider of civil air navigation services to Canada.

Permissions/Licenses/Permits for Launch and Flight of Balloons

Canada has a well-developed body of regulations regarding occupied balloons, particularly with fare-paying passengers, requiring a special flight operations certificate for balloons under Balloons required by Part VI, Subpart 3, Division II of the CARs. This section will instead remain focused upon unmanned balloons.

While the scope of the immediate study includes smaller high-altitude balloons, Canadian regulations only apply to large unoccupied free balloons. Small (under

^{kkkkkk} Canadian Aviation Regulations Part I General Provisions, Subpart I Interpretation 101.01(1).

^{lllll} Ibid.

^{mmmmmm} CAR 602.42

115 cubic feet of gas capacity) unmanned balloons are not regulated. Regulations pertinent to large unmanned balloons are included below.

Regulations Pertaining to Large Unmanned Balloonsⁿⁿⁿⁿⁿⁿ

Large Unoccupied Free Balloons 602.42

No person shall release an unoccupied free balloon having a gas-carrying capacity of more than 115 cubic feet (3.256 m³) except in accordance with an authorization issued by the Minister pursuant to section 602.44.

Flight Authority 605.03

- (1) No person shall operate an aircraft in flight unless*
- (a) a flight authority is in effect in respect of the aircraft;*
 - (b) the aircraft is operated in accordance with the conditions set out in the flight authority; and*
 - (c) subject to subsections (2) and (3), the flight authority is carried on board the aircraft.*
- (2) Where a specific-purpose flight permit has been issued pursuant to section 507.04, an aircraft may be operated without the flight authority carried on board where*
- (a) the flight is conducted in Canadian airspace; and*
 - (b) an entry is made into the journey log indicating*
 - (i) that the aircraft is operating under a specific-purpose flight permit, and*
 - (ii) where applicable, any operational conditions that pertain to flight operations under the specific-purpose flight permit.*
- (3) A balloon may be operated without the flight authority carried on board where the flight authority is immediately available to the pilot-in-command*
- (a) prior to commencing a flight; and*
 - (b) on completion of the flight.*

Division IV — Technical Records

Requirement to Keep Technical Records 605.92

- (1) Every owner of an aircraft shall keep the following technical records in respect of the aircraft:*
- (a) a journey log;*
 - (b) subject to subsections (2) and (3), a separate technical record for the airframe, each installed engine and each variable-pitch propeller; and*
 - (c) except where otherwise provided under the terms of a fleet empty weight and balance program referred to in subsection 706.06(3), an empty weight and balance report that meets the applicable standards set out in Chapter 571 of the Airworthiness Manual.*

ⁿⁿⁿⁿⁿⁿ <http://www.tc.gc.ca/eng/acts-regulations/regulations-sor96-433.htm>

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- (2) *The technical records required by paragraph (1)(b) may consist of separate technical records for each component installed in the airframe, engine or propeller.*
- (3) *In the case of a balloon or glider, or an aircraft operated under a special certificate of airworthiness in the owner-maintenance or amateur-built classification, all entries in respect of the technical records referred to in paragraphs (1)(b) and (c) may be kept in the journey log.*

Small Unmanned Balloon Practice

In the absence of mandatory regulation of small unmanned balloon launches, operators are encouraged to communicate with NAV Canada, providing launch date and time, launch location (latitude and longitude), payload system length, payload weight, balloon diameter at launch, approximate rate of ascent, approximate burst altitude, payload description during descent, estimated landing location, and estimated duration of ascent and descent.^{ooooo} This information can be given as much in advance as a week before launch but 2 – 3 days can be sufficient.

The day of the launch, 30-60 minutes prior, it is recommended that the operator contact the local Flight Information Center (FIC), either by telephone or via email, to coordinate the launch.

5.2.7.2 Restrictions on Overflight of Stratospheric Balloons

Canadian regulation is silent as to overflight of foreign balloons as a class of aircraft. It could be inferred that rules governing overflight of foreign aircraft could apply to all classes of aircraft falling within the purview of the CARs. In this case, this would apply to aircraft operations requiring an air operator certificate.^{ppppp} In Canada, only manned balloons require such a certificate.

Right-of-Way Rules

Canada's right-of-way rules impose on pilots of aircraft the duty to give way to balloons. These aircraft are defined to include aircraft that are power-driven and heavier-than-air, airships, and gliders. As between two balloons at different altitudes, the higher altitude gives right-of-way to the lower altitude.

Right of Way — General 602.19

- (1) *Notwithstanding any other provision of this section,*
- (a) *the pilot-in-command of an aircraft that has the right of way shall, if there is any risk of collision, take such action as is necessary to avoid collision; and*
- (b) *where the pilot-in-command of an aircraft is aware that another aircraft is in an emergency situation, the pilot-in-command shall give way to that other aircraft.*

^{ooooo} Information on the Amateur Radio Astronomy and Weather Reporting website, available at: <http://www.arawr.ca/?page=legal> (date accessed: 25 May 2017).

^{ppppp} CAR Division III Subpart I Foreign Air Operations

(2) *When two aircraft are converging at approximately the same altitude, the pilot-in-command of the aircraft that has the other on its right shall give way, except as follows:*

(a) *a power-driven, heavier-than-air aircraft shall give way to airships, gliders and balloons;*

(b) *an airship shall give way to gliders and balloons;*

(c) *a glider shall give way to balloons; and*

(d) *a power-driven aircraft shall give way to aircraft that are seen to be towing gliders or other objects or carrying a slung load.*

(3) *When two balloons operating at different altitudes are converging, the pilot-in-command of the balloon at the higher altitude shall give way to the balloon at the lower altitude.*

5.2.7.3 Recovery of Stratospheric Balloons

Canadian regulations are silent regarding the rescue and recovery of fallen balloons. It can be inferred that general norms for rescue and recovery could be extrapolated to apply.

5.2.7.4 Radiofrequencies and Telecommunications Provisions

Frequency and bandwidth for amateur operations are managed by Industry Canada and available in RBR-4 – Standards for the Operation of Radio Stations in the Amateur Radio Service.⁹⁹⁹⁹⁹⁹

5.2.8 Findings on Regulations in the U.S. and Canada

While the United States and Canada both have regulatory definitions for balloons, neither distinguishes stratospheric balloons/operations from balloons and operations as a general class. Altitude is not an element of either regulatory definition.

United States

Distinctions in the US are made between moored and free balloons and between manned and unmanned balloons. Regulations attach according to payload size (weight and volume). Balloons with payloads not meeting the regulatory threshold are not regulated.

- Two sets of regulations govern launching and tracking high-altitude balloons in the United States.
 - launches are regulated by the FAA
 - monitoring/tracking by the FCC
- The issue of responsibility for some high-altitude activities in the United States is not entirely settled. Two directorates of the FAA are currently involved with different aspects of high-altitude balloon activities and regulations are not completely aligned within the Code of Federal Regulations.
 - No license is required as per 14 CFR Part 91 Flight Rules

⁹⁹⁹⁹⁹⁹ Available online at: <http://www.ic.gc.ca/eic/site/smt-gst.nsf/eng/sf01226.html> (date accessed: 30 May 2017).

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- A launch operator license would be required as per 14 CFR Part 400 Commercial Space Transportation
 - United States includes balloon operations in right-of-way rules.
 - United States regulations are silent regarding rules for overflight of foreign balloons.
 - United States regulations are silent regarding specific rescue and recovery protocols.
 - The FCC regulates frequency and spectrum use in the United States. Regulations are found in 47 CFR Part 22.
 - No cellular phones can be used on balloons while they are airborne.

Canada

- Canada has invested \$4M in balloon launch infrastructure.
- Canada distinguishes between balloon sizes based upon gas capacity, not payload.
- Canada distinguishes between unoccupied and occupied balloons and between occupied balloons with fare-paying passengers.
- In Canada, regulations govern the launch of large unmanned balloons and are administered by Transport Canada. Operators of small, unmanned balloons utilize practices that encourage interfacing with NAV Canada.
- Canada includes balloons in its right-of-way rules.
- Canadian regulations are silent as to overflight of foreign balloons.
- Canadian regulations are silent regarding rescue and recovery of balloons.
- Industry Canada manages spectrum and frequency use. Standards applicable to amateur radio stations (as with radiosondes) are found in RBR-4.

5.2.9 Regulations in Chile

5.2.9.1 Restrictions on Stratospheric Balloon Flights in Chile

The unmanned free balloon activities in Chile have not been very common, reason why its regulation is scarce. However, the advance of technology and the increase of these activities has forced the general direction of civil aeronautics of Chile to create a regulation that regulates the activities and operations carried out with Captive Balloons, Comets, Unmanned Rockets and Balloons Free unmanned. This regulation is called DAR-101. DAR 101 was approved on 2nd April 2003. In Chile. DARs are provisions that establish rules of a general regulatory nature aimed at providing security and various services to air navigation. Their numbering and format are derived from the Annexes to the Convention of International Civil Aviation.

The purpose of this regulation is to achieve a greater degree of uniformity in standards and global standardization of safety requirements. To this end, the Directorate General of Civil Aeronautics has proposed to harmonize the rules on Airworthiness Directives, as regulated by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) of the United States of America. What surprises me most when investigating the DAR 101 regulation is that it

does not define unmanned free balloon. The only definition that can be found on free balloons is in the DAR 31 regulation that defines these objects as, apparatus of a light gas that can rise in the atmosphere and move by the space following the current of the winds. The funny thing is that this regulation that contains the definition of free balloon was repealed on June 19, 2008.

The DAR 101 regulation regulates the operations of unmanned free balloons in the national territory when they fulfil the following requirements^{rrrrr}:

- Unmanned free balloons carrying cargo weighing no more than 2 kg and having a weight / size ratio of more than 13.23 grams per cm² on any surface of the container.
This is determined by dividing the total weight of the load by the area of the smaller surface of the container.
- Unmanned free balloons carrying a payload weighing more than 2.72 kg.
- Unmanned free balloons carrying a payload of 2 or more packages weighing more than 5.45 kg.
- Unmanned free balloons using a rope or other suspension device that requires an impact force of more than 22.72 kg to separate the balloon from the suspended payload.

This regulation establishes prohibitions on areas where unmanned free balloons operations cannot be carried out. The first prohibition applies to prohibited or restricted areas. Nobody can operate unmanned free balloon in a prohibited or restricted area^{sssss}. According to the DAR 15, "Regulation of Aeronautical Information Services", and DAN 91, "Rules of the Air", which establishes the technical regulation of competition of the DGAC, which derives from DAR 91, "Regulation of Transit Services Aerial", the following zones of airspace are distinguished^{ttttt}:

- Prohibited zone: consisting of airspace of defined dimensions over the national territory, within which the flight of aircraft is prohibited for national security or military reasons;
- Restricted area: airspace of defined dimensions over the national territory, within which the flight of aircraft is restricted, in accordance with certain specified conditions;
- Hazardous area: the airspace of defined dimensions in which dangerous activities for the flight of aircraft may be deployed at certain times.

The second prohibition applies to dangerous operations. This prohibition is divided into two different sub-prohibitions, and although they look the same, they have a great difference in their applications.^{uuuuu} This prohibition derives in two different, that although they look the same, they have a great difference in its application. The first one establishes a prohibition for everybody to operate unmanned free balloons in a manner that would create danger to persons or cause damage to property on the surface.

^{rrrrr} See §101.1, Sub-part A, DAR-101.

^{sssss} See §101.5, Sub-part A, DAR-101.

^{ttttt} See §91.101 e), Chapter B, DAR-91.

^{uuuuu} See §101.7, Sub-part A, DAR-101.

The second one establishes a prohibition for unmanned free balloons operators to allow the release of an object from them, if such action creates danger to persons or causes damage to property on the surface.

It is important to pay attention to the content of both prohibitions because if you launch an unmanned free balloon, or if you authorize its launch knowing that it can cause some harm to people or damage to property on the surface, you will be responsible in the same way.

The DAR 101 regulation establishes different operational limitations in terms of altitude, equipment and identification. In terms of altitude, no person may operate unmanned free balloons^{vvvvv}:

- Unless authorized by the appropriate air traffic control unit, under 2,000 feet AGL (Above Ground Level), within the lateral boundaries of designated Class B, C, D and E airspace areas;
- At any altitude where clouds or phenomena prevail that obstruct the visibility of more than 4/8 of covered sky;
- At any altitude below 60,000 feet where the horizontal visibility is less than 8 km;
- During the first 1,000 feet of ascent over a congested area of a city, town, settlement, or gathering of non-operation-related outdoor persons;
- In such a way that the impact of the balloon or part of it, including its load, creates a danger to people or buildings not related to the operation.

With regard to the first point above, it is necessary to know the classification and division of air space in Chile. The airspace in Chile is classified and designated as provided in DAR-11 and in accordance with the following:

- 1 CLASS A. Only IFR flights are allowed; Is provided to the air traffic control service flights and are separated from each other.
- 2 CLASS B. IFR and VFR flights are permitted; Is provided to the air traffic control service flights and are separated from each other.
- 3 CLASS C. IFR and VFR flights are permitted; Air traffic control service is provided to flights and IFR flights are separated from other IFR flights and VFR flights. VFR flights are separated from IFR flights and receive traffic information regarding other VFR flights.
- 4 CLASS D. IFR and VFR flights are permitted; Air traffic control service is provided to flights; IFR flights are separated from other IFR flights and receive traffic information regarding VFR flights. VFR flights receive traffic information on all other flights.
- 5 CLASS E. IFR and VFR flights are permitted; IFR flights are provided to air traffic control service and are separated from other IFR flights. All flights receive traffic information to the extent practicable.
- 6 CLASS G. IFR and VFR flights are permitted and receive flight information, if requested.

The Visual Flight Rules (VFR) are the set of rules that establish the conditions sufficient for the pilot to be able to direct his aircraft, navigate and maintain the safety separation

^{vvvvv} See §101.33, Sub-part D, DAR-101.

with any obstacle with the only aid of the visual observation. Under VFR, the pilot directs his aircraft while maintaining visual contact with the terrain at all times, but is allowed to use the flight instruments on board as supplementary aid.

The Instrument Flight Rules (IFR) are the set of rules and procedures that regulate the flight of aircraft based on the use of navigational instruments, which implies that they must not necessarily have visual contact with the terrain.

In order to be able to operate unmanned free balloons, they must comply with a series of equipment requirements^{wwwwww}:

- The unmanned free balloon to be operated must be equipped with at least two load release systems or devices operating independently of one another.
- At least two methods, systems, devices, which operate independently of each other, must be employed to cancel the flight of the balloon.
- The cover of the balloon must be equipped with a radar reflecting device or a material that echoes to a surface radar operating in a frequency range of 200 to 2,700 Mhz.

The unmanned free balloon operator shall activate the appropriate device required in paragraph (2) of this section when the weather conditions are lower than those mentioned above in the section "Operational limitations in terms of altitude", or if a failure or any other reason does the operation dangerous for other air traffic or for people or cause property damage to the surface.

Unmanned free balloons may not be operated under 60,000 feet altitude between sunset and sunrise unless the balloon, its harnesses and cargo, whether or not separated during operation, are equipped with lights which make it visible at least 8 km and have a flashing frequency of at least 40 and not more than 100 cycles per minute.

Unmanned free balloons may not be operated when they are equipped with a hanging antenna that requires an impact force of more than 23 kg (50 lb) to be cut at any point, unless the antenna has colored ribbons and flags that are tied at intervals of not more than 20 meters and are visible at a distance of 1,600 meters.

No person may operate, between sunrise and sunset, unmanned balloons equipped with a suspension device (other than an open parachute, with easily visible colours in the air) of more than 20 meters in length, unless this suspension device is painted with alternating bands of visible colours or Have attached tufts or hanging banners of colour that are visible at least 1,600 meters.

When the operation with unmanned free balloons has ended, the operator shall notify the nearest air traffic control unit about the completion of the operation.

5.2.9.2 Restrictions on Overflight of Stratospheric Balloons

The DAR 101 regulation also includes a section, which specifies the different notifications to be made^{xxxxxx}: the Pre-launch Notification, Notification of Cancellation, Launch Notification and the Balloon Position Notification.

^{wwwwww} See §101.35, Sub-part D, DAR-101.

^{xxxxxx} See §101.37, Sub-part D, DAR-101.

No person may operate unmanned free balloons unless, within 6 to 24 hours prior to commencement of operation, provide the following information to the air traffic control unit closest to the location of the operation being attempted (Pre-launch Notification):

1. Identification of the balloon;
2. The estimated date and time of the launch, corrected as necessary for it to take place within a 30 minute range of the estimated time;
3. The location of the launch site;
4. The cruising altitude;
5. The predicted trajectory and the estimated time to reach the cruising altitude or 60,000 feet of altitude, whichever is lower;
6. The length and diameter of the balloon, the length of the suspension device, the weight of the load and the length of the hanging antenna;
7. The duration of the flight;
8. Estimated time and location of impact with the earth's surface.

The time interval of 6 to 24 hours will not apply for investigations of solar or cosmic disturbances involving a critical time element. For these investigations, the information must be provided to the air traffic control unit closest to the location of the operation being attempted, within 30 minutes to 24 hours before the commencement of the operation.

If the operation is cancelled, the operator of the unmanned free balloon shall immediately notify the nearest air traffic control unit about the cancellation of the operation. (Notification of Cancellation)

Any person who launches a free unmanned balloon shall report to the nearest air traffic control unit the time of launch immediately after the balloon has been launched (Launch Notification).

It is not clear what immediately means, as this regulation does not provide an exact time frame. In my opinion, immediately means as soon as it is possible to report the nearest traffic control unit.

Any person operating an unmanned free balloon shall monitor the course of the balloon and record its position at least every 2 hours and whenever the air traffic control unit does not require it otherwise and Provide any balloon position required by the air traffic control unit. (Balloon Position Notification)

One hour before commencement of descent the operator shall provide the nearest air traffic control unit with the following information regarding that balloon:

1. The current geographical position;
2. The altitude;
3. The hour of penetration estimated from 60,000 feet of altitude, if it is applicable;
4. The expected path for the rest of the flight;
5. Estimated time and place of impact with land surface.

If the balloon position notification is not recorded during a 2-hour flight period, the person operating the unmanned free balloon shall immediately notify the nearest air traffic control unit.

The notification shall include the last registered position and any.

5.2.9.3 Recovery of Stratospheric Balloons

The DAR-13 (Reglamento sobre investigación de accidentes e incidentes de aviación) regulation sets out the procedure for carrying out the investigation in case of aviation accidents and incidents.

This regulation will apply to^{yyyyyy}:

1. Research activities arising as a result of accidents and incidents of any aircraft occurring in the territory and national airspace and those occurring on Chilean aircraft in waters or territories not subject to the sovereignty of another State, except for military aircraft of the Republic of Chile.
2. To the research activities that are generated as a result of Air Traffic Incidents that occur in the territory and national airspace with respect to all the aircraft.

This regulation should also apply to unmanned free balloon accidents, since they are considered aircraft.

The investigation of the cause of the accident or incident will be carried out by the Directorate General of Civil Aviation (Dirección General de Aviación Civil)^{zzzzzz}. The DGCA will take the necessary measures to coordinate with the Judicial or Police Authority the protection of the evidence, for the period of time that is required to carry out the Investigation.

The DGAC will return evidence that is no longer necessary for the investigation. Such internal reimbursement may be made to the national owners or operators. In the case of foreign aircraft, the evidence may be given to the person or persons duly appointed by the State of registry or by the State of the airline, as the case may be. For this purpose, the competent aeronautical authority shall provide them with access to the aircraft.

Any person who has knowledge of an aviation accident or incident occurring within the national territory or the existence of remains or debris of an aircraft shall notify the nearest police authority as soon as possible and by the fastest means available^{aaaaaaa}. It is the duty of the pilot-in-command, operator or owner of an aircraft to communicate to the DGAC, as soon as possible and by the fastest means, the occurrence of an aviation accident suffered by a Chilean registered aircraft in a foreign country. The notification shall contain at least the following information:

- Type of aircraft, model and license plate.
- Pilot and / or crew affected
- Passengers on board.
- Geographical location.
- Local time of the event and brief review of it.

The DAR-13 regulation establishes a difference between accidents occurring in the national territory and those occurring in a foreign territory.

The investigation carried out in national territory will be conducted by an investigator in charge, except in the case of accidents involving aircraft of more than 5,700 kg, in which

^{yyyyyy} See Chapter 2, DAR-13

^{zzzzzz} See Chapter 3, DAR-13

^{aaaaaaa} See Chapter 4, DAR 13

case the DGAC will carry out the investigation by means of an Aviation Accident Investigation Board^{bbbbbb}.

It is important to distinguish between accidents and incidents. According to the DAR-13 regulation, accident is any event related to the use of an aircraft occurring within the period between the time a person enters the aircraft with the intention of making a flight and the time when all persons have performed the landing operation^{cccccc}. An incident is an event of casual characteristics that happens in the course of the operation of an aircraft, regardless of the human action that causes or can cause slight damage. According to this definition, In case an activity performed with unmanned free balloons goes wrong, it will be considered an incident, since they are not manned. Those events classified as incidents, because they have little transcendence from a technical-operational point of view and do not necessarily require a formal investigation, will be recorded with a Brief Report on Prevention and Statistics. In case an aircraft involved in an accident or aviation incident occurred in the airspace of another State lands in national territory, the investigation will be carried out and for this purpose the collaboration and the antecedents of the case will be requested to the State of the Company and the State of registry.

For accidents occurring in a foreign territory, Chapter 5 of this regulation states that in the event of an aircraft accident involving a Chilean registered aircraft in another Contracting State of the International Civil Aviation Convention, the DGCA may nominate such Investigators as it considers necessary to participate in the investigation as accredited representatives. In the event of an accident to an aircraft of national registration in a non-Contracting State to the International Civil Aviation Convention, the DGCA shall attempt to carry out the investigation in collaboration with the State of the event.

5.2.9.4 Other Regulations

The sovereignty of the State of Chile extends to the airspace overlying its territory and its territorial sea, in accordance with international law. This space is determined by the presence of gases, especially oxygen, which allow the flight of sustained aircraft in the aerodynamic resistance that opposes the gases and a mobile moving at predetermined speeds. The upper limit of this space, which lies in the range of 80 to 100 km in altitude, constitutes the border with outer space, universal heritage of humanity.

For purposes of air traffic control, the International Civil Aeronautics Organization (ICAO) recognizes Chile as having jurisdiction and responsibility in an area which generally extends from the northern boundary (latitude 18°21 'N) to the South Pole, and from the international political boundary to the east to the 131 ° 00 'W meridian. In total, the airspace controlled by Chile covers an area of 26.8 million km², which includes its continental and insular territory, its jurisdictional waters and The high seas included.

5.2.9.5 Radiofrequencies and Telecommunications Provisions

The radio spectrum is regulated in the General Telecommunications Law (Ley General de Telecomunicaciones). According to this law, telecommunications shall mean any

^{bbbbbb} See Chapter 5, DAR-13

^{cccccc} See Chapter 1, Definitions, DAR-13

transmission, emission or reception of signs, signals, writings, images, sounds and information of any nature, by physical line, radio electricity, optical media or other electromagnetic systems^{dddddd}.

Article 2 establishes the right of free and equal access to telecommunications for all inhabitants of the Republic of Chile. Moreover, any person may opt for concessions and permits in the form and conditions established by law.

The radio spectrum is a national good, whose domain belongs to the whole Nation. Consequently:

- no natural or juridical person can be attributed or claim the dominion of all or part of the radio electric spectrum,
- concessions granted to natural or legal persons are, in essence, temporary and
- those benefiting from a concession may pay the State for the use and enjoyment thereof in accordance with this law.

The application and control^{eeeeee} of this law will be carried out by the Ministry of Transport and Telecommunications, through the Subsecretaría de Telecomunicaciones (no translation).

The aeronautical telecommunications services, whether fixed or mobile, referred to in the International Radio Regulations of the International Telecommunication Union, shall be installed, operated, authorized or controlled as the case may be, by the Directorate General of Civil Aeronautics, as long as it is an Agency Dependent on the Commander-in-Chief of the Air Force of Chile^{ffffff}.

5.2.10 Regulations in Russia

5.2.10.1 Summary

The Russian Federation doesn't have a dedicated regulatory source applicable to exploitation of balloons. The general and overarching Air Code doesn't specifically codify the notion of the balloon. However, the Federal Rules on the use of Russian airspace (from March 11 2010, with amendments) specify that an "aerostat" (balloon) is a flying apparatus the carrying power of which is based on aerostatic or simultaneously aerostatic and aerodynamic principles. The Rules further classify piloted, automated, tethered and free balloons (aerostats). Furthermore, the Rules bring up the notion of the pilot-balloons or balloons-probes in conjunction with activities regarding gathering of meteorological information.

With regard to the division of airspace, the Rules specify the division of lower and upper airspace at 8100 meters.

The use of balloons requires acquisition of appropriate permissions as well as radio frequencies from the designated authorities, in particular with the Russian Federal agency of air traffic. Any crossing of Russian airspace apart from an emergency one requires a prior permission to use the Russian airspace.

^{dddddd} See Art. 1, Ley General de Telecomunicaciones

^{eeeeee} See Art. 6, Ley General de Telecomunicaciones

^{ffffff} See Art. 11, Ley General de Telecomunicaciones

The permissions for the use of balloons (piloted or not) are issued by the Centre of the Unified system, regional and zonal centres of the Unified system or the regional centres of the Unified system.

Around five years ago some of the specific provisions in the regulatory basis governing use of balloons over the territory of the Russian Federation were nullified. For this reason, today the regulatory sources are represented by the generic air law sources as well as regulatory sources of the Ministry of Defense that are not always publicly available. The underlying rule however is to seek the permission for any activity to be undertaken in the Russian airspace.

5.2.10.2 Restrictions on Stratospheric Balloon Flights in Russia

Principles for Carrying out Aviation Activities

The main regulatory act that applies to use of balloons within the territory of Russian Federation is the Air Code ("Воздушный кодекс Российской Федерации" от 19.03.1997 N 60-ФЗ (ред. от 06.07.2016) that specifies that the Russian air law applies to the relationships and activities regarding use of airspace within its territory, as well as outside its territory by air fleet of Russian Federation unless specified otherwise in applicable international treaties (Article 5).

According to Article 8 of the Air Code non-piloted civil aviation systems or their elements (Article 8 2.1), as well as companies that undertake development of air vehicles, their elements, other types of aviation equipment (Article 8 3), as well as other aviation activities have to be certified and attested in accordance with the special procedures.

Some activities within the field of civil aviation can be carried out only with a licence issued in accordance with the legislation of the Russian Federation (Article 9 Air Code). Such activities include for example development of the air vehicles, including dual use vehicles, repairing air vehicles, use of aviation in various sectors of economy, as well as their testing (Commentary to Article 9 Air Code).

Aviation activities in the Russian Federation are subdivided into three categories: civil, state and experimental aviation (Article 20 Air Code). Experimental aviation includes aviation activities for the purposes of experimental, scientific and technical activities, as well as testing of air vehicles and equipment (Article 23 Air Code).

An air vehicle is allowed to carry out flights when it has a state registration or other prescribed authentication, as well as undergone appropriate testing and in possession of required documentation (Article 66 1. Air Code). It is worth noting that the procedure of allowing experimental air vehicles is set up and carried out by a designated institution within the Ministry of Defence (Article 66 3.).

Aviation activities are subject to compulsory insurance (Article 131 Air Code) that covers damage to third parties' life, health or property as a consequence of using an air vehicle. When international flights of air vehicles are undertaken the insurance is calculated based on the insurance rates and requirements of the responsible foreign state (Article 131 3).

Definition of a Stratospheric Balloon

The Air Code doesn't contain a definition of a balloon ("aerostat" transliterated from the

Russian term), while only defining the “air vehicle” that is maintained in the atmosphere by virtue of its interaction with the air that is different from the interaction between the air and the surface of the earth or water (Article 32 Air Code). It provides for classification of air vehicles into several categories: light (up to a mass of 5700 kg, for helicopters up to 3700 kg) and ultralight (with the maximum mass of 495 kg excluding rescue equipment), piloted and non-piloted air vehicles. These categories often have different authorisation, certification and other procedures necessary to undergo in order to acquire permission to fly.

Several other regulatory sources do provide for a definition of a balloon, albeit none of them refers or distinguishes stratospheric balloons specifically.

The first source to mention are Federal Rules regarding Use of Airspace of the Russian Federation (Rules on Use of Airspace)^{§§§§§§§§} that are developed in accordance with the principles within the Air Code and the Chicago Convention (Article 1) specify that “aerostat” (balloon) is a flying apparatus the carrying power of which is based on aerostatic or simultaneously aerostatic and aerodynamic principles. The Rules further classify piloted, automated, tethered and free balloons (aerostats). Furthermore, the Rules bring up the notion of the pilot-balloons or balloons-probes in conjunction with activities regarding gathering of meteorological information (Article 2).

Another source that contains an identical definition of a balloon are Federal Rules on Aviation Flights within the Airspace of the Russian Federation in their Article 10(7) (Приказ Минобороны РФ, Минтранса РФ и Российского авиационно - космического агентства от 31 марта 2002 г. N 136/42/51 "Об утверждении Федеральных авиационных правил полетов в воздушном пространстве Российской Федерации").

In addition to the definition of the balloon, both sources also define a specimen of a balloon called “dirigible” airship (in Russian “дирижабль”). It is essentially an aerostat (balloon) that is moved in airspace by virtue of a power installation that is navigated by height, direction, velocity, distance and duration of the flight (Article 7(39) of the Rules on Aviation Flights.

Interestingly, the other source, the Rules on Use of Airspace in Section I(2) only refers to navigation parameters of height, direction and velocity.

Last but not least, the the Rules on Use of Airspace in Section I(2) define “pilotless air vehicle” as an air vehicle that flies without the pilot aboard and is navigated in flight automatically, by an operator from a control centre, or both.

Division of Airspace

With regard to the division of airspace, for the purposes of controlling air traffic and establishing flight plans, etc., Article 7 of the Rules on Use of Airspace specifies the division of lower and upper airspace at 8100 meters. In addition, the Aviation Rules on

^{§§§§§§§§} Приложение к Постановлению Правительства РФ от 11 марта 2010 г. N 138 Федеральные правила использования воздушного пространства Российской Федерации (утв. постановлением Правительства РФ от 11 марта 2010 г. N 138) С изменениями и дополнениями от: 5, 27 сентября 2011 г., 19 июля 2012 г., 8 июля, 4 августа 2015 г., 18 февраля, 12 июля 2016 г., 14 февраля 2017 г.

Flights specify that in terms of height/altitude the flights can be classified as stratospheric if they are carried out at the altitude of 12000 metres (Section II. 8ж).

5.2.10.3 Restrictions on Overflight of Stratospheric Balloons

Acquisition of the Permission to Carry Out Balloon Flights

If an air vehicle is not categorised as light or ultralight, persons who fly such vehicles need to acquire certificate of air operator in accordance with the rules laid down in the Federal Aviation Rules „Preparation and Execution of Civil Aviation Flights in the Russian Federation“ (Утверждены Приказом Минтранса России от 31 июля 2009 г. N 128 ФЕДЕРАЛЬНЫЕ АВИАЦИОННЫЕ ПРАВИЛА "ПОДГОТОВКА И ВЫПОЛНЕНИЕ ПОЛЕТОВ В ГРАЖДАНСКОЙ АВИАЦИИ РОССИЙСКОЙ ФЕДЕРАЦИИ" (в ред. Приказов Минтранса России от 21.12.2009 N 242, от 22.11.2010 N 263, от 16.11.2011 N 284, от 27.12.2012 N 453), as well as in the Federal Rules "Operators of general aviation. Requirements for the operator of general aviation, procedures regarding registration and control of the activities of operators of general aviation" (Приказ Минтранса России от 18.06.2003 N 147 (ред. от 10.11.2015) "Об утверждении Федеральных авиационных правил "Эксплуатанты авиации общего назначения Требования к эксплуатанту авиации общего назначения, процедуры регистрации и контроля деятельности эксплуатантов авиации общего назначения"). The obligation to acquire an operator certificate equally applies to air vehicles owned by the operator, leased or otherwise legally made available to him (Section I(2)).

Application for registration as an operator shall be submitted to a responsible territorial authority of Federal Agency of Air Transport in accordance with the requirements laid down in Section III (19). It has to be submitted at least 45 days prior to the execution of planned flights.

In addition to the procedures established for „mass-produced“ air vehicles, special rules that might be relevant to some stratospheric or other types of balloons apply to air vehicles produced in numbers less or equal to three. In particular, the Order of authorising exploitation of single exemplars of air vehicles of general aviation (Утверждены Приказом Минтранса России от 17 апреля 2003 г. N 118 ФЕДЕРАЛЬНЫЕ АВИАЦИОННЫЕ ПРАВИЛА "ПОЛОЖЕНИЕ О ПОРЯДКЕ ДОПУСКА К ЭКСПЛУАТАЦИИ ЕДИНИЧНЫХ ЭКЗЕМПЛЯРОВ ВОЗДУШНЫХ СУДОВ АВИАЦИИ ОБЩЕГО НАЗНАЧЕНИЯ"). The main step for such air vehicles to be used is acquisition of airworthiness certificate (Section I(1) of the Order). The rules within the Order apply to balloons with the volume of the dome not more than 3500 cubic metres and a mass without payload, fuel, gas and people of not more than 450 kg. The person who intends to carry out flight activities using such air vehicle(s) submits an application to the certification authority (Section II(10) that within two weeks from the submission date notifies the applicant as to whether the application will be accepted for assessment, and if the answer is positive orders a certification centre to assess whether the requirements of airworthiness are met (section II (11, 12). In accordance with the Appendix 2 to the Ordinance the following parameters are assessed: the ability to fly, strength or durability, design and structure, equipment, exploitation restrictions, identification of the air vessels, as well as some additional parameters for dirigibles.

In addition, special permissions to carry out any types of remote sensing from aboard the balloon have to be acquired following procedures established by the government of the Russian Federation (Article 75 Air Code). The Federal Aviation Rules „Preparation and Execution of Civil Aviation Flights in the Russian Federation“ while not specifying how such a permission can be obtained, contains in its sections 7.12-20 some technical specifications as to how remote sensing activities shall be carried out from aboard of air vehicles. Most of remote sensing activities do not require a licence, but for activities for federal purposes that have country-wide or inter-sectoral implications (Постановление Правительства РФ от 07.12.2011 N 1016, Положение о лицензировании геодезических и картографических работ федерального назначения, результаты которых имеют общегосударственное, межотраслевое значение, Ordinance regarding licensing of geodesic and cartographic work for federal purposes that have country-wide or inter-sectoral implications, Section 2). If the licence is necessary, the responsible authority is the Federal Service for state registration, cadastre and cartography.

Flight Plans

Once the necessary documents are acquired and gathered by the air operator, flight plans have to be developed and submitted to the responsible authority from the Single System for management of air traffic, and the flights have to be carried out in accordance to such plans (Article 70(1) Air Code). Articles 52, 53 and 109 of the Rules on Use of Airspace further approve that all air(borne) non-piloted vehicles, including balloons, have to approve flight plans of the vehicle in order to have the permission to execute the flight (see also Article 116 of the Rules on Use of Airspace). In addition, there are special rules with regard to the balloons and other air vehicles that gather meteorological information (Article 54 Rules on Use of Airspace).

The one-at-a-time (i.e. non-systematic) use of the sonde-balloons are based on the plans for using the airspace of the Russian Federation, while the placement of stationed points of launching balloons have to be coordinated with the Russian Agency for Air Transport (Article 53 Rules on Use of Airspace).

The permission to use airspace is issued by the maincentre of the Single system, its regional and zonal centres, as well as district centres (Article 117 of the Rules on Use of Airspace). The permission to use airspace states the following: the time of the start and finish of the activity, the borders of the district where the activity is undertaken and the range of use altitudes.

Rules for International Flights

The Air Code lays down specific rules for international flights of air vehicles that imply flight within airspace of more than one country (Article 79(1)). Such flights have to be carried out in accordance with the legislation of the Russian federation, common principles and norms of international law and with the international agreements of the Russian Federation. International flights of air vehicles are carried out on the basis of international agreements to which the Russian Federation is a party or permits issued in accordance with applicable procedures (Article 79(4)). Aircraft markings of air vehicles of foreign countries (Article 79(5)) and information about insurance (Article 79(6)) have

to be communicated by the operators to the designated authorities of the civil aviation before the start of the flight.

The overflight of the state border takes place through special corridors (Article 85 Rules on Use of Airspace) after the permission to use airspace of the Russian Federation is obtained (Article 87 Rules on Use of Airspace). The permission is not necessary in the situations of distress, e.g. when the air vehicle is damaged, is caught by a natural disaster, etc. (Article 96 Rules on Use of Airspace).

5.2.10.4 Recovery of Balloons

The Russian Federation does not specifically regulate the issue of rescue and recovery of balloons but has a set of rules that are applicable to air vehicles in general. The main principles and basic rules are laid down in the Air Code. Its Article 86 differentiates between air vehicle in distress and distressed vehicle. An air vehicle in distress is in danger that cannot be eliminated by the crew, or communications with it are lost and its location is unknown. A distressed air vehicle has suffered serious damage or is completely destroyed or was forced to land outside an aerodrome. Such air vehicles are subject to immediate search and rescue. Article 88(1) specifies that search and rescue of unmanned air vehicles in distress or distressed vehicles shall be organised and carried out by the owner of such air vehicles.

The Rules on Aviation Flights in section XXI lay down more details rules with regard to actions of various persons and authorities when they learn to know about an air vehicle in distress or distressed. Such rules apply to commanders of any air vehicle that notices an air vehicle in distress or a distressed air vehicle, as well as indicated responsible authorities. Applicable regulatory sources do not contain rules with regard to ownership of rescued parts of air vehicles or equipment on board collected by search and rescue team.

5.2.10.5 Radiofrequencies and Telecommunications Provisions

The Air Code specifies in Article 76 that in support of flights of air vehicles persons entitled to provide communication services have to provide in accordance with contracts with designated responsible authorities required communication channels. Such provision has a priority over services to entities undertaking activities other than air flights. Furthermore, in accordance with Article 78 the designated authority within the Ministry of Defence secures radiotechnical support for air vehicles and communication with them by allocating radiofrequencies protected from interference.

5.3 ITU REGULATIONS ON FREQUENCIES FOR STRATOSPHERIC BALLOON APPLICATIONS

By contrast to the aeronautical regulations, radio regulations deal with the use of the radio spectrum by stratospheric balloons and aim to prevent harmful interference between, on the one hand, HAPS and their ground stations and, on the other hand, other users of the same frequencies.

At the international level, the International Telecommunications Union (ITU), more specifically the Radiocommunication Sector, regulates the allocation of frequency bands

for specific uses. For the ITU purposes, no distinction is made regarding manned, unmanned or any other type of the balloon. What matters is what type of telecommunication service will be used by the balloon or provided if the balloon is used as a station.

The ITU regulations and recommendations are rendered more precise by regional telecommunications organisations and, ultimately, implemented by nation states via national laws and regulations.

5.3.1 High Altitude Platform Stations

The stratospheric balloons typically fall under the ITU definition of High Altitude Platform Stations (HAPS), which are stations located on an object at an altitude of 20 to 50 km and at a specified, nominal, fixed point relative to the Earth (Article 1.66A of the ITU-R^{hhhhhh}, definition included at the WRC-97). HAPS are also termed “stratospheric repeaters” in telecommunications regulations.

Article 1.66A ITU-R: high altitude platform station: A station located on an object at an altitude of 20 to 50 km and at a specified, nominal, fixed point relative to the Earth.

This categorization has been criticized by some scholars as restrictive and too removed from reality because most balloons (will) fly lower, at the height of 15 km to 20 km.ⁱⁱⁱⁱⁱⁱ Therefore, the developed ITU regulations would not apply to such balloons. Instead such balloons may be considered as a different object, which would significantly increase the potential range of frequency bands that can be used.^{jjjjjj} This is supported by the history of the stratospheric balloon flight: over the years a variety of suitable frequency bands has been used for communication and data transmission purposes, including amateur frequency bands and license-exempt spectrum,^{kkkkkk} as well as for control and operation of balloons.^{llllll}

Due to the developments of new technologies of mobile communications in the condition of spectrum scarcity, in the 1990s the ITU worked on the designation of specific frequency bands for allocation to stratospheric balloons (HAPS) in order to prevent

^{hhhhhh} ITU Radio Regulations Articles, 2016 edition. A balloon may also be considered the object that carries the HAPS.

ⁱⁱⁱⁱⁱⁱ Grace, David and Mohorcic, Mihael (2010). Broadband Communications via High-Altitude Platforms. Wiley, p. 14.

^{jjjjjj} Grace, David and Mohorcic, Mihael (2010). Broadband Communications via High-Altitude Platforms. Wiley, p. 14.

^{kkkkkk} See a chronological list of stratospheric balloons’ launches since 1947 compiled at <http://stratocat.com.ar/globos/indexe.html>. The database documents about 50% of all launches and gives a decent overview of various uses of balloons as well as, in many cases, of the frequency bands that were used.

^{llllll} VHF and UHF are typically used to control and operator balloons from distant locations. See Michailidis, Emmanouel and Kanatas, Athanasios (2016). Stratospheric channel models, in: Kanatas, Athanasios and Panagopoulos, Athanasios. Radio Wave Propagation and Channel Modeling for Earth–Space Systems, p. 300.

harmful interference. The first respective regulations were adopted at the World Radio Conference in 1997 (WRC-97).

Radio frequencies available to the HAPS differ only slightly in different ITU Members because some of them joined (introduced) exemptions permitted by the ITU Radio Communications Conferences.

HAPS can be used for fixed services, which are radiocommunication services between specified fixed points (Article 1.20 ITU-R). To specify further, a radiocommunication service involves the transmission, emission and/or reception of radio waves for specific telecommunication purposes (Article 1.19 ITU-R).

Article 1.19 ITU-R: radiocommunication service: A service as defined in this Section involving the transmission, emission and/or reception of radio waves for specific telecommunication purposes.

Article 1.20 ITU-R: fixed service: A radiocommunication service between specified fixed points.

Since the WRC-12 HAPS can also be used for delivering International Mobile Telecommunications (so called IMT-2000) systems. Mobile services are those between mobile and land stations, or between mobile stations (Article 1.24 ITU-R), and the IMT systems provide telecommunication services on a worldwide scale regardless of location, network or terminal used.^{mmmmmmmm} Specifically, IMT-2000 systems provide 3G/UMTS mobile communications services and data transfer services (HSDPA).

Article 1.24 ITU-R: mobile service: A radiocommunication service between mobile and land stations, or between mobile stations.

5.3.2 License-Exempt Spectrum

Worldwide certain frequency bands have been reserved for industrial, scientific and medical purposes (so called ISM bands for uses other than telecommunications), but have been increasingly employed for non-ISM uses recently. The list of these frequency bands can be found in Art. 5 ITU-R. Specifically for HAPS the bands 2.4 GHz and 5.8 GHz are of interest.ⁿⁿⁿⁿⁿⁿⁿ

These bands are available for use by anyone on the “no interference, no protection” basis. Besides the frequency bands that are universally licence-free, there is a number of frequency bands that can be exempted from licensing by national administrations (for examples see Art. 5 ITU-R).

The rest of the radio spectrum is licensed by national administrations for specific use to specific users.

^{mmmmmmmm} Resolution 223 (WRC-15), available at <http://search.itu.int/history/HistoryDigitalCollectionDocLibrary/4.297.43.en.100.pdf>.

ⁿⁿⁿⁿⁿⁿⁿ Google’s Project Loon uses them.

5.3.3 Frequencies for Fixed Services

Article 4.23 ITU-R limits the transmission to and from HAPS to specific bands. On the global basis (in all countries) the bands 47.2-47.5 GHz and 47.9-48.2 GHz are designated for the allocation of fixed services by HAPS (Article 5.552A ITU-R).

Article 5.552A ITU-R: The allocation to the fixed service in the bands 47.2-47.5 GHz and 47.9-48.2 GHz is designated for use by high altitude platform stations. The use of the bands 47.2-47.5 GHz and 47.9-48.2 GHz is subject to the provisions of Resolution 122 (Rev. WRC-07).

Resolution 122 (Rev. WRC-07)^{oooooooo} contains specific provisions on the use of the bands 47.2-47.5 GHz and 47.9-48.2 GHz by HAPS for fixed services. Specifically, it deals with the promotion of the use of the named frequencies by pointing to the studies conducted by the ITU on the use of these frequencies, indicating practical steps that can be taken by national administrations to promote the use and sharing of these frequencies, establishing Effective Isotropic Radiated Power (EIRP) density levels and power flux-density levels and setting other parameters.

In addition to this, Recommendation ITU-R F.1500^{ppppppp} contains preferred characteristics of systems in the fixed service using HAPS in the bands 47.2-47.5 GHz and 47.9-48.2 GHz. It is applicable to HAPS in a fixed location in the stratosphere at the height of 21 to 25 km. Because these frequency bands may be shared with the fixed satellite service, provided by satellites in the geostationary orbit, Recommendation ITU-R SF.1481 contains technical requirements to prevent harmful interference.

5.3.4 Complementary Bands for Fixed Services

Because of the sensitivity of the bands 47.2-47.5 GHz and 47.9-48.2 GHz to rain, additional bands were designated to allocation of fixed service.

In several Region 1 and Region 3 countries^{qqqqqqq}, the allocation to the fixed service in the band 27.9-28.2 GHz may also be used for a fixed downlink (HASP-to-ground) for the HAPS within the territory of these countries (Article 5.537A ITU-R). Such use of 300 MHz of the fixed-service allocation by HAPS shall not cause harmful interference to other types of fixed services and not claim protection from them.

Article 5.537A ITU-R: In Bhutan, Cameroon, Korea (Rep. of), the Russian Federation, India, Indonesia, Iran (Islamic Republic of), Iraq, Japan, Kazakhstan, Malaysia, Maldives, Mongolia, Myanmar, Uzbekistan, Pakistan, the Philippines, Kyrgyzstan, the Dem. People's Rep. of Korea, Sudan, Sri Lanka, Thailand and Viet Nam, the allocation to the fixed service in the band 27.9-28.2 GHz may also be used by high altitude platform stations (HAPS) within the territory of these countries. Such use of 300 MHz of the fixed-

^{oooooooo} Available at: <http://search.itu.int/history/HistoryDigitalCollectionDocLibrary/4.132.43.en.100.pdf> .

^{ppppppp} Available at: http://www.itu.int/dms_pubrec/itu-r/rec/f/r-rec-f.1500-0-200005-i!pdf-e.pdf .

^{qqqqqqq} Bhutan, Cameroon, South Korea, the Russian Federation, India, Indonesia, Iran, Iraq, Japan, Kazakhstan, Malaysia, Maldives, Mongolia, Myanmar, Uzbekistan, Pakistan, the Philippines, Kyrgyzstan, the Dem. People's Rep. of Korea, Sudan, Sri Lanka, Thailand and Viet Nam.

service allocation by HAPS in the above countries is further limited to operation in the HAPS-to-ground direction and shall not cause harmful interference to, nor claim protection from, other types of fixed-service systems or other co-primary services. Furthermore, the development of these other services shall not be constrained by HAPS. See Resolution 145 (Rev.WRC-12).

In the same countries, the bands 31.0-31.3 GHz for a fixed uplink (ground-to-HAPS) can be allocated for the use by HAPS limited to the territory of those countries and under the same conditions as described for the uplink (Article 5.543A ITU-R). Furthermore, systems using HAPS in these bands shall not cause harmful interference to the radio astronomy services that have a primary allocation in the bands 31.3-31.8 GHz. There are additional conditions on power flux-density values in order to ensure the protection of satellite passive services.

Article 5.543A ITU-R: *In Bhutan, Cameroon, Korea (Rep. of), the Russian Federation, India, Indonesia, Iran (Islamic Republic of), Iraq, Japan, Kazakhstan, Malaysia, Maldives, Mongolia, Myanmar, Uzbekistan, Pakistan, the Philippines, Kyrgyzstan, the Dem. People's Rep. of Korea, Sudan, Sri Lanka, Thailand and Viet Nam, the allocation to the fixed service in the frequency band 31-31.3 GHz may also be used by systems using high altitude platform stations (HAPS) in the ground-to-HAPS direction. The use of the frequency band 31-31.3 GHz by systems using HAPS is limited to the territory of the countries listed above and shall not cause harmful interference to, nor claim protection from, other types of fixed-service systems, systems in the mobile service and systems operated under No. 5.545. Furthermore, the development of these services shall not be constrained by HAPS. Systems using HAPS in the frequency band 31.3 GHz shall not cause harmful interference to the radio astronomy service having a primary allocation in the frequency band 31.3-31.8 GHz, taking into account the protection criterion as given in the most recent version of Recommendation ITU-R RA.769. In order to ensure the protection of satellite passive services, the level of unwanted power density into a HAPS ground station antenna in the frequency band 31.3-31.8 GHz shall be limited to -106 dB(W/MHz) under clear-sky conditions, and may be increased up to -100 dB(W/MHz) under rainy conditions to mitigate fading due to rain, provided the effective impact on the passive satellite does not exceed the impact under clear-sky conditions. See Resolution 145 (Rev.WRC-12).*

Resolution 145 (Rev. WRC-12)^{xxxxx} contains more specific provisions on the use of the bands 27.9-28.2 GHz and 31.0-31.3 GHz.

In addition to the above, five countries (Australia, Burkina Faso, Cote d'Ivoire, Mali and Nigeria) allow allocation the complementary bands 6,440-6,520 MHz (HAPS-to-ground) and 6,560-6,640 MHz (ground-to-HAPS) for fixed service (Article 5.457 ITU-R). These bands may be used within the territory of these countries, but their use requires explicit agreement with other national administrations whose territories are located within 1,000 km from the border of the national administration intending to use the HAPS

^{xxxxx} Available at: <http://search.itu.int/history/HistoryDigitalCollectionDocLibrary/4.133.43.en.100.pdf> .

gateway links. The use of these bands by the listed countries needs to comply with Resolution 150 (WRC-12) that specifies some of the technical requirements to antennas.

Article 5.457 ITU-R: *In Australia, Burkina Faso, Cote d'Ivoire, Mali and Nigeria, the allocation to the fixed service in the bands 6 440-6 520 MHz (HAPS-to-ground direction) and 6 560-6 640 MHz (ground-to-HAPS direction) may also be used by gateway links for high-altitude platform stations (HAPS) within the territory of these countries. Such use is limited to operation in HAPS gateway links and shall not cause harmful interference to, and shall not claim protection from, existing services, and shall be in compliance with Resolution 150 (WRC-12). Existing services shall not be constrained in future development by HAPS gateway links. The use of HAPS gateway links in these bands requires explicit agreement with other administrations whose territories are located within 1,000 kilometres from the border of an administration intending to use the HAPS gateway links.*

5.3.5 Frequencies for International Mobile Telecommunications (IMT)

In Regions 1 and 3^{ssssss}, the bands 1,885-1,980 MHz, 2,010-2,025 MHz and 2,110-2,170 MHz and, in Region 2^{tttttt}, the bands 1,885-1,980 MHz and 2,110-2,160 MHz may be used by HAPS as base stations to provide IMT (Article 5.388A ITU-R). In certain countries^{uuuuuu}, limitations are set on the co-channel power flux-density when using those frequencies by HAPS at the Earth's surface outside a country's borders unless explicit agreement of the affected administration is provided at the time of the notification of HAPS (Article 5.388B ITU-R). This is in order to protect other fixed and mobile services from co-channel interference.

Article 5.388A ITU-R: *In Regions 1 and 3, the bands 1,885-1,980 MHz, 2,010-2,025 MHz and 2,110-2,170 MHz and, in Region 2, the bands 1,885-1,980 MHz and 2,110-2,160 MHz may be used by high altitude platform stations as base stations to provide International Mobile Telecommunications (IMT), in accordance with Resolution 221 (Rev.WRC-07). Their use by IMT applications using high altitude platform stations as base stations does not preclude the use of these bands by any station in the services to which they are allocated and does not establish priority in the Radio Regulations.*

Article 5.388B ITU-R: *In Algeria, Saudi Arabia, Bahrain, Benin, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Comoros, Côte d'Ivoire, China, Cuba, Djibouti, Egypt, United Arab Emirates, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Gabon, Ghana, India, Iran (Islamic Republic of), Israel, Jordan, Kenya, Kuwait, Libya, Mali, Morocco, Mauritania, Nigeria, Oman, Uganda,*

^{ssssss} Roughly, Region 1 covers Europe, former Soviet Union and the whole Africa. Region 3 is Asia, Australia and Oceania. The ITU Regions are specified in Articles 5.2-5.22 ITU-R.

^{tttttt} Region 2 covers the Americas.

^{uuuuuu} Algeria, Saudi Arabia, Bahrain, Benin, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Comoros, Côte d'Ivoire, China, Cuba, Djibouti, Egypt, United Arab Emirates, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Gabon, Ghana, India, Iran (Islamic Republic of), Israel, Jordan, Kenya, Kuwait, Libya, Mali, Morocco, Mauritania, Nigeria, Oman, Uganda, Pakistan, Qatar, the Syrian Arab Republic, Senegal, Singapore, Sudan, South Sudan, Tanzania, Chad, Togo, Tunisia, Yemen, Zambia and Zimbabwe.

Pakistan, Qatar, the Syrian Arab Republic, Senegal, Singapore, Sudan, South Sudan, Tanzania, Chad, Togo, Tunisia, Yemen, Zambia and Zimbabwe, for the purpose of protecting fixed and mobile services, including IMT mobile stations, in their territories from co-channel interference, a high altitude platform station (HAPS) operating as an IMT base station in neighboring countries, in the bands referred to in No. 5.388A, shall not exceed a co-channel power flux-density of $-127 \text{ dB(W)/(m}^2 \cdot \text{MHz)}$ at the Earth's surface outside a country's borders unless explicit agreement of the affected administration is provided at the time of the notification of HAPS.

5.3.6 Additional Shared Frequency Bands

In 2011 the ITU adopted a Recommendation ITU-R F.1891 that provides the technical and operational characteristics for HAPS gateway links in the fixed service in the band 5,850-7,075 MHz. These additional bands are not exclusive to HAPS, but are shared with systems operating in the fixed, mobile, and fixed-satellite services. Their use by HAPS may have an impact on passive services such as the Earth exploration-satellite service and radio astronomy.

Nevertheless, the ITU permits national administrations their allocation for use by HAPS in order to enhance flexibility in the choice of spectrum for gateways and support the deployment and operation of HAPS networks.

In order to prevent harmful interference, the Recommendation ITU-R F.1891 limits the number of gateway links in HAPS systems and requires to employ higher performance antennas and higher transmitted power, which would permit the use of higher order modulation methods and more complex coding.

5.3.7 Notifications by National Regulators to the Bureau

Under certain circumstances, when a frequency is assigned to the transmitting and receiving stations by the national regulator, it needs to be notified to the Radiocommunications Bureau of the ITU (Article 11.2 ITU-R) that records and registers frequency assignments in the Master International Frequency Register. The conditions when a notification is necessary are, according to Articles 11.3-11.8 ITU-R, the following:

- if the use of that assignment is capable of causing harmful interference to any service of another administration; or
- if that assignment is to be used for international radiocommunication; or
- if that assignment is subject to a world or regional frequency allotment or assignment plan which does not have its own notification procedure; or
- if that assignment is subject to the coordination procedure of Article 9 ITU-R or is involved in such a case; or
- if it is desired to obtain international recognition for that assignment; or
- if it is a non-conforming assignment under No. 8.4 ITU-R and if the administration wishes to have it recorded for information.

In the case of HAPS, national regulators shall inform the Radiocommunications Bureau not earlier than five years in advance before the assignments of frequencies are brought

into use for fixed services (Article 11.26 ITU-R) and not earlier than three years in advance for mobile services (Article 11.26A ITU-R).

Article 11.26 ITU-R: Notices relating to assignments for high-altitude platform stations in the fixed service in the bands identified in Nos. 5.457, 5.537A, 5.543A, and 5.552A shall reach the Bureau not earlier than five years before the assignments are brought into use.

Article 11.26A ITU-R: Notices relating to assignments for high altitude platform stations operating as base stations to provide IMT in the bands identified in 5.388A shall reach the Bureau not earlier than three years before the assignments are brought into use.

Notifications about frequency bands for fixed services (see Article 5.552A ITU-R) and complementary bands for fixed services (see Article 5.543A ITU-R) shall be made (Articles 11.9-11.11 ITU-R):

8. for receiving HAPS, when the conditions under b), c) or e) mentioned above apply,
9. for the associated transmitting station, when any of the conditions under a)-f) apply.

5.3.8 Challenges

All these spectrum decisions were taken without the consideration of broadband. This is why the WRC-15 undertook to study spectrum needs for HAPS and commission several studies.

They are specifically looking at Regions 2 and 3 and at bands 38-39.5 GHz (for global use) and 21.4-22 GHz and 24.25-27.5 GHz (for Region 2). HAPS and the spectrum needs for them will be the big topic of the next WRC-19. This is why they commissioned several technical studies - in order to provide scientific basis for a potential decision/ ITU recommendation.

Additionally, as balloons are flying at lower heights than 20 km, some terrestrial frequency bands may be used by them for certain commercial services, subject to viability and feasibility studies.^{vvvvvv} For instance, by using the frequency bands between 2 GHz and 6 GHz, HAPS could deliver WiMAX mobile services.^{wwwwwww}

6 TECHNICAL CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

Given the analyses made in the previous sections, it turns out that using currently reliable and well-proven technology the needed platform would be heavy and complex in order to meet the current requirements and technical specifications, which were assembled to accommodate the maximum number of science cases possible. The weight and complexity are considerably far beyond the initial concepts that originally motivated the

^{vvvvvv} See, for instance, assessment by Grace, David and Mohorcic, Mihael (2010). Broadband Communications via High-Altitude Platforms. Wiley, pp. 96-113.

^{wwwwwww} Michailidis, Emmanouel and Kanatas, Athanasios (2016). Stratospheric channel models, in: Kanatas, Athanasios and Panagopoulos, Athanasios. Radio Wave Propagation and Channel Modeling for Earth-Space Systems, p. 302.

ORISON proposal, and what is more important, the costs of building and operating an astronomical observatory of this type would be high. In the end, operation costs would be in the order of 20,000 Euro per observing hour, according to crude estimates based on computations of the main costs that enter in the chain. This is an important weakness because this is a very high average cost compared to other state-of-the-art astronomical facilities.

Therefore, radical and aggressive ways of reducing mass, energy consumption and other critical key parameters would be needed in order to reduce costs. Consequently, the science that could be achieved would also be far more limited. In this section we make an overview of which strategies regarding simplifications and mass reductions might be feasible in the future and analyse the impact that this would have on the science output of the possible infrastructure.

Since ORISON aims at repeated and regular missions, the cost of operations is a recurring cost and as such will have a very significant influence on the cost per observing hour. As mentioned above, a first crude operations cost estimate showed prohibitively high costs per observation hour. For this reason, the analysis in the following will focus on primarily reducing the operations cost, however also keeping in mind effects on non-recurring costs such as development and hardware.

6.1 MASS REDUCTION STRATEGIES

The most straightforward strategy to reducing the mission cost would be to reduce the total gondola mass. A reduced gondola mass would consequently lead to a smaller required balloon, which in itself reduces cost in balloon hardware, but also in terms of ground handling. As mentioned in section 4.1, particularly if the total gondola mass could be reduced to less than 40 kg, mass reduction alone would reduce the launch cost to an amount likely compatible with the original ORISON idea. For this reason, in the following firstly the current mass drivers will be identified and potential mass reduction strategies will be described.

6.1.1 Identification of Mass Drivers

The current iteration mass budget in section 3.3.4. clearly shows several particular mass drivers for the total gondola mass. To provide more clarity, they will be subdivided into independent and dependent mass drivers. The independent drivers are:

- The telescope (100 kg);
- The science instrument (10 kg for the WFI, 40 kg for the MCI);
- The electronics mass (between 25 and 27 kg);
- The fine pointing system (15 kg).

The dependent drivers are:

- Part of the attitude actuators (particularly the reaction wheel (20 kg), but also the motors (20 kg in total)), dependent upon the total gondola mass (reaction wheel,

reaction wheel & pivot motors) and the telescope assembly mass (elevation motors);

- The batteries (between 16.4 kg for *Orison Light* & 118.8 kg for *Orison Infinity*, dependent upon the energy consumption).

In addition, the mechanical gondola structure is regarded as a semi-independent driver, given that it is dependent upon the mass of the subsystems and equipment that it has to accommodate, but that its mass can be reduced by applying independent strategies, e.g. the choice of material or the choice of protection it should offer to the carried components.

6.1.2 Potential Reduction in Telescope Mass

The telescope assumed in the baseline study in chapter 3 uses a carbon truss, but traditional glass-ceramics mirrors not optimized for small mass. By using modern, mass-optimized glass mirrors or mirrors made of carbon-fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP), the telescope mass can be reduced dramatically. The two approaches may actually offer two steps in mass reduction:

Light-weighted glass mirrors using sandwich structures instead of a solid structure can reduce the mass of a 0.5 m aperture telescope (total optical tube assembly including mirrors) to approximately 35 to 40 kg (compare commercially available products from DREAM Telescopes & Accessories Inc.^{xxxxxxx} or Hubble Optics^{yyyyyyy}).

CFRP mirrors can furthermore reduce the telescope mass (optical tube assembly including mirrors) to about 20 kg (compare products of Composite Mirror Applications Inc.^{zzzzzz}).

It should be noted that these telescopes are manufactured for ground-based applications and the changes necessary (and potential associated mass increase) to adapt them for use on a stratospheric balloon would need to be subject of further investigation. The light-weighted telescopes can also become comparably expensive (at the order of 50 kEUR). It would therefore likely make sense to take measures for their protection, e.g. performing as-soft-as-possible landings on steered parafoils.

It also should be noted that none of these telescopes include an actuated secondary mirror to correct defocus and coma caused by misalignment between the primary and the secondary mirror which may result from thermo-elastic deformations. The SUNRISE mission showed, however, that it can be sufficient to correct coma before flight [19]. Answering the question of whether this also applies for the light-weighted telescopes would need to be subject of further work.

^{xxxxxxx} <http://www.dreamscopes.com/>

^{yyyyyyy} <http://hubbleoptics.com/>

^{zzzzzz} <http://www.compositemirrors.com/>

Figure 6-1: Masses of commercially available ground-based telescopes employing different mirror technologies.

Masses are indicated for full optical tube assemblies (some telescopes uses trusses only). The mass for a 0.5 m aperture CFRP telescope is based on an interpolation between the existing 0.4 m and 1 m versions.

However, if pre-flight focus proves to be sufficient, defocus can be corrected by a focuser further down in the optical path, making the additional mass of an actuated secondary at the front of the optical tube unnecessary.

Another option to reduce the telescope mass would be to reduce the telescope aperture diameter from the 0.5 m baseline to e.g. 0.4 m. Figure 6-1 provides an indication of telescope masses that have been achieved with the different technologies.

6.1.3 Potential Reduction in Instrument Mass

The instrument mass estimate of the Multi Channel Imager in section 3.3.4. is based on using commercially available standard optics and optical components, in line with the strategy of preferably using commercially available parts. The resulting estimated mass of 45 kg is prohibitive for a mass-optimized ORISON version, however. If a Multi Channel Imager was to remain under consideration as a facility class instrument, it might thus be beneficial to consider accepting certain additional development effort for an optimized instrument. Currently ongoing developments at MPE for a small space instrument indicate that a full 4-channel imager can be built at around 10 kg mass.

A further consideration could be to reduce the scientific versatility of the Wide Field Imager to save mass, e.g. by excluding the filter wheel. An estimated mass saving of a couple of kg does not seem to justify the associated loss in scientific applicability and convenience.

6.1.4 Potential Reduction in Electronics Mass

The electronics mass estimate in section 3.3.4. is based on non-weight-optimized hardware and rather conservative. An option to reduce the mass of the electronics

systems could be to use systems designed for micro or nano satellites, which are typically more expensive, but highly mass-optimized. A suitable microsatellite main computer can be found at around 1 kg.

6.1.5 Potential Reduction in Fine Pointing System Mass

The fine pointing system mass of the ORISON baseline estimate in table 3-7: is based on the Sunrise image stabilization system. The Sunrise system, however, includes a correlated wavefront sensor that, with the associated optics, adds additional mass. For the purpose of ORISON, an adjusted two- or three-step pointing and image stabilization system would be sufficient, however. By sacrificing some of the light in the main optical path, a closed-loop fine image stabilisation system using the foreseen tip-tilt mirror as actuator and a regular image sensor as the main sensor could be implemented. By limiting the corrections to pointing corrections, a high-resolution image sensor (instead of a wavefront sensor) would be sufficient.

As mentioned already under section 6.1.2, de-focus could be corrected by a standard focuser in the optical path close to the instrument, thereby making it unnecessary for the image stabilization to fulfil this function as well.

Adapting the fine pointing system to the particular needs of ORISON would thus require some further development effort, but would also promise further mass savings.

6.1.6 Potential Reduction in Attitude Control Actuators Mass

The ORISON baseline mass estimate assumes the same reaction wheel and motors (for pivot, elevation, and the reaction wheel) for all three ORISON scenarios, which satisfy the *Orison Infinity* case. The *Orison Heavy* and *Orison Light* scenarios, however, do not need to carry solar arrays, which reduces the gondola area subjected to wind pressure and thereby the amplitude of disturbances caused by it. Additionally, the reduced total gondola mass in the *Orison Heavy* and *Orison Light* scenarios will lead to a reduced moment of inertia of the gondola compared to the *Orison Infinity* scenario. On this basis, the pivot motor and either the reaction wheel moment of inertia or the reaction wheel motor could be adjusted, leading to mass savings on these components.

6.1.7 Potential Reduction in Battery Mass

The batteries considered in the ORISON baseline are already chosen based on their specific energy density. A potential way to reduce the battery mass would be to reduce the whole system's power consumption. This might, in a limited fashion, be possible by focusing more on the energy consumption at the choice of electronic components (e.g. of the GNSS receiver, or by generally making use of components and subsystems designed for micro- or nanosatellite applications, as also mentioned above). Some energy consumption saving from part of the attitude control motors would also come along with a reduction of the total gondola mass.

6.1.8 Potential Reduction of the Gondola Mechanical Structure Mass

As mentioned above, the gondola structure mass can be regarded as a semi-dependent item. In addition to the mass savings that can be implemented in line with mass savings

of all components and subsystems to be carried, the gondola mass can be reduced with respect to the baseline design by:

- a) Reducing its protective function for the payload and/or some of the subsystems;
or
- b) Changing the gondola material (accepting higher cost).

Option a) would be contrary to the protection of a light-weighted, but potentially rather expensive telescope, which constitutes a large fraction of the payload (as mentioned in section 6.1.2). This option therefore does not appear desirable. Option b), however, does promise some mass reduction. The effect of changing from an aluminium structure to a carbon fibre structure becomes obvious in the low mass of the mechanical structure estimated for *Orison Light*, which assumes a carbon fibre structure.

6.1.9 Summary of Mass Saving Potential

A careful estimate of the potential mass saving associated with the strategies described above indicate that a total gondola mass of less than 200 kg might be realistic when using light-weighted 0.5 m telescopes with glass sandwich mirrors. When using light-weighted telescopes with CFRP mirrors, total gondola masses at the order of 160 kg seem possible. If a 0.4 m diameter telescope was used instead of a 0.5 m telescope, additional mass saving of around 8 % could be expected. It should be noted, however, that when using the light-weighted telescopes, it appears imperative to foresee steered landings in order to protect the more fragile payload. An additional mass of 15 to 35 kg for a steerable parafoil system thus would need to be added to the total suspended mass. Considering the difference of roughly 60 kg between a telescope with traditional mirrors and one with glass sandwich mirrors alone, this choice appears well justified, however.

6.2 CHANGE IN FLIGHT ALTITUDE

Another way to reduce operational effort would be to reduce the flight altitude requirement. The ORISON baseline concepts discussed so far have assumed a flight altitude of 30 km to guarantee optimal observation conditions. As the figures in section 3.1 indicate, observations in several regards are already excellent at 20 km:

The Fried parameter, even at 300 nm, is already larger than 0.7 m at 20 km for zenith angles of 60 deg or smaller, thus already allowing diffraction limited angular resolution of a 0.5 m telescope at 20 km;

The PSF-broadening effect of atmospheric Mie scattering is expected to be less than 0.02 arcsec at 20 km for zenith angles of 60 deg or smaller, so that atmospheric scattering also should not degrade the angular resolution performance at 20 km (see [2] for details on the degradation estimate);

Scintillation noise is reduced by about an order of magnitude compared to high ground-based observatories or by approx. a factor of 3 compared to SOFIA (even though still more than an order of magnitude higher than at 30 km).

While not all observations that would be possible at 30 km will still be possible at 20 km, particularly those relying upon high spatial/angular resolution still will be, and those requiring high photometric accuracy will also still benefit.

On the other hand, as figure 6-2 indicates, the balloon size for the same suspended mass can be drastically reduced when lowering the flight altitude from 30 to 20 km, thus making ground handling much easier. Figure 6-2 shows performance curves of available balloons from the French manufacturer Airstar Aerospace, with the individual balloon names referring to their volume in 1000 m³. A mission operating at 20 km can thus, assuming the same suspended mass, use a balloon 7 times smaller than one operating at 30 km.

Figure 6-2: Performance curves of selected zero pressure stratospheric balloons offered by the French manufacturer Airstar Aerospace. Data from <http://airstar.aero/fr/>.

6.3 CHANGE IN FLIGHT DURATION AND TRAJECTORY

Since a large part of the operational cost and effort is associated with the balloon launch itself, an increase of the flight and observation time can decrease the cost per observation hour. One option to drastically increase the observation time without adding the logistical complexity of launching from Antarctica would be flying superpressure balloons in the Southern hemisphere, e.g. from New Zealand. These would promise flight durations of 50 days and more. However, such flight times would require adaptations to the flight hardware (e.g. consideration of radiation effects on electronics) and the large ultra long duration superpressure balloons are not reliable yet (the flight-proven superpressure balloons regularly flown over several months by CNES are limited to ca. 50 kg payload at 20 km altitude).

A more workable solution would be to fly manoeuvrable balloons that allow station keeping over a certain area for longer periods of time, such as the ones offered by World View Inc. Using such balloons would likely mean accepting to fly at 20 km altitude at the moment. They are, for the moment, also offered for payloads of only up to 100 kg. Serious considerations of using this flight opportunity thus would require a closer investigation of their current and potential performance envelope.

6.4 CONCLUSION ON COST REDUCTION STRATEGIES

It has become obvious that likely not one strategy by itself can reduce the operations cost to the required amount. A combination of different strategies will need to be employed.

It has also become evident that this reduction cannot be achieved by using only traditional and commonly available ballooning subsystems, but that making use of state-of-the-art equipment from other fields will be necessary. This will require some additional effort in adaptation and development.

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